

a)

b)

a)

b)

Supplemental Material

Supplementary Figure Legends

Figure S1. (a) Immunoblotting of extracts from cells transfected with VP4-BAP (lanes 1, 3, and 4) and treated with lambda phosphatase (lane 4) or untreated (lane 3) or infected with rRV/VP4-BAP (lane 2). The shifted VP4-BAP band is indicated with a red point. Membranes were incubated with anti-VP4 and anti-alpha-tubulin. **(b)** Chromatogram of the sequence of gs 4 of rRV/VP4-BAP at the virus passages 6, 8, and 10. The site of the BAP tag and linker insertions are indicated. The reference sequence corresponds to pT₇-VP4-BAP.

Figure S2. Read obtained when particles of rRV/wt (grey open circle and square) and rRV/VP4-BAP (green full circle and square) were assayed directly in an ELISA when detected with guinea pig anti-RV followed with secondary antibody conjugated to HRP.

Figure S3. (a) Immunofluorescence of non-infected or rRV/wt- or rRV/VP4-BAP-infected MA104 cells fixed at 6 hpi with methanol and immunostained for detection of viroplasms (anti-NSP5, red) and actin-cytoskeleton (anti-actin, cyan). Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). Scale bar is 10 μ m. **(b)** Immunofluorescence of rRV/wt or rRV/VP4-BAP-infected MA104 cells at 20, 30, 40, and 50 VFU/cell. At 6 hpi, the cells were fixed with methanol and immunostained for the detection of viroplasms (anti-NSP5, red), microtubules (anti- α -tubulin, green), and actin cytoskeleton (anti-actin, cyan). Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). The scale bar is 20 μ m.

Figure S4. (a) Cytotoxicity assay of MA104 cells treated with SPL-FITC for 6 and 24 h at the indicated concentration. Cytotoxicity was determined by LDH release. Cells treated with buffer containing Triton X-100 were used as positive control. Data

represent the mean \pm SD from triplicate experiments. **(b)** Immunofluorescence microphotograph of MA104 cells fixed at 2, 4 and 8 h of treatment with 12.5, 25 and 50 μ M of SPL-FITC. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). Scale bar is 20 μ m. Plots for the quantification of the ratio of cells showing viroplasms **(c)** and the of viroplasm number **(d)** and size **(e)** per cells in MA104 cells infected with rRV/wt untreated (UT) or treated with 25 μ M SPL at +1 and +3 hpi. The data represent the mean \pm SEM using Welch ANOVA test. ns, not significant.

Figure S5. (a) *In silico* modeling of VP4-BAP blue, orange, pink, and green based on the VP4 crystal structure (PDB:3IYU).

Figure S6. (a) Immunofluorescence analysis of BHK cells expressing mCherry-VP5, untreated or treated with SPL (3.125- 50 μ M). SPL was added immediately after transfection. Cells were fixed in methanol at 24 hpt and immunostained for the detection of mCherry-VP5 (anti-mCherry-Alexa 680, cyan) and actin (anti- actin, red). Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). Scale bar is 10 μ m. **(b)** Immunoblot of lysates from BHK cells expressing mCherry-VP5, untreated and treated with SPL (3.125-50 μ M) at 24 hpt. The membrane was incubated with anti-dsRed2 and anti-beta actin for detection of mCherry-VP5 and actin, respectively. Fibrillarin was used as loading control.

TABLE S1 Primers and DNA synthetic fragments used in this study

Amplified DNA segment	Oligonucleotide sequence
VP4-SA11	fwd: 5'-gatcaagcttcacccatggcttcgctcatttataga-3' rev: 5'-gatcctcgagtcacaacctgcattgcataat-3'
pcDNA-VP4- KpnI/BamHI	Fwd (1) : 5'-gcgtaattggttgaaggtacc <u>caataatacagatagatggtt</u> -3' Rev (1) : 5'-aaccatctatctgtattatt <u>ggtac</u> cttcaacaattacgc-3' Fwd (2) : 5'-aagtataggacaatatggatc <u>ctt</u> actatccagtcggaaatt-3' Rev (2) : 5'-aatttcggact <u>g</u> gatagtaaggatccatattgtcctatactt-3'
pcDNA-VP4-BAP (blue)	5'- <u>ggtacca</u> ataat <u>tccggagg</u> gctgaacgacat <u>ttttgaagcacaga</u> agattgagtg ggcagaa <u>ggggctagc</u> accgatagatggctggcaaccat cctgattgagcccaactgcagagcgaaaatcgacttacaccatcttc gggattcaggagcagctgacagtcttaacactagtcaggaccagtgga agttatcgatgtggc caaa accacagctaattggcagtatcgggcagta <u>tggatcc</u> -3'
pcDNA-VP4-BAP (orange)	5'- <u>ggtacca</u> acaataactgaccgatggctggcaaccatcctgattgacc taac <u>tccggagg</u> gctgaatgat <u>atcttcgaagccc</u> gaaaaatcgagtg gc acgaaggc gctagcgtgcagagcgagaacagaacatacactatcttcggg attcaggaacagctgaccgtctccaatacatcccaggatcagtggaagtt tatcgacgtggtcaaaactaccgccaacggctctattgggcagtac <u>gga</u> <u>cc</u> -3'
pcDNA-VP4-BAP (pink)	5'- <u>ggtacca</u> ataatacagaccggtggctggctacaatcctgattgacc aaactgcagtcggaaaatagaacctatacaatcttcggcattcaggagc agctgactgtgtctaaccaccagc <u>tccggagg</u> cctgaatgacat <u>tttcgaa</u> gcacagaagattgagtg ggcagaa <u>ggggctagcc</u> aagatcaatggaagtt tatcgacgtcgtcaaaacaactgccaatggctcaatcggccaatat <u>gga</u> <u>cc</u> -3'
pcDNA-VP4-BAP (green)	5'- <u>ggtacca</u> ataatacagaccggtggctggctacaatcctgattgacc aaactgcagtcggaaaatagaacctatacaatcttcggcattcaggagc agctgactgtgtctaaccaccagc <u>tccggagg</u> cctgaatgacat <u>tttcgaa</u> gcacagaagattgagtg ggcagaa <u>ggggctagcc</u> aagatcaatggaagtt tatcgacgtcgtcaaaacaactgccaatggctcaatcggccaatat <u>gga</u> <u>cc</u> -3'
pT ₇ -VP4-BAP (green)	5'- <u>caattg</u> ctcagcaattcttatacagtagatttatccgatgagatacaag agattggatcaactaaatcacaaaatgtcacaattaatcctggaccatttgc gcaaacagggttatgctccagttactggggacctggagaaattaatgattct acgacagttgaaccattgctggatgggcttatcaaccaatgacattcaatc caccagtcgattattggatgttactggctccaacgacacctggcgaattgt tgaaggtaccaacaacaccgacaggtggctggccaccattctgatcagagccc aacgtgcagagtgaaaatcgcaactataccatctttggaatccaggagcagc tgacagtgagtaaacacttcacaggaccagtggaagtcatcgacgtcgtcaa aaccaca <u>tccggagg</u> actgaatgat <u>atctttgaagcacagaagattgagtg</u> cacgaagg gggctagcgc caaa acggctccattgggcagtatggatccttactat ccagtccgaaattatgtagttatgaagcataatgaaaaattatata <u>cata</u> <u>tg</u> -3'
pCI-VP4-GFP and pCI- VP4-BAP-GFP	fwd: 5'-ctataggttagcgcaccatggcttcgctcatttatag-3' rev: 5'-ggtaccacgcgtcaacctgcattgcataaatcag-3'

a) Restriction enzymes are in italics and underlined.

b) Inserted point mutations are underlined.

c) BAP tag is highlighted in bold.

TABLE S2 Primers used for quantitative real-time PCR

Species	Gene	Oligonucleotide sequence
<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	HPRT	Fwd: 5'-tgacactggcaaacgatgca-3' Rev: 5'-agtccttttcaccagcaagct-3'
<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	SDHA	Fwd: 5'-tggaacaagagggcatctg-3' Rev: 5'-ccaccaccgatcaaatcatg-3'
Simian RV SA11	VP6	Fwd: 5'-cattccagttaatgagaccac-3' Rev: 5'-gttacatttgctaatagagtttcac-3'
Simian RV SA11	NSP5	Fwd: 5'-tgaatccatagacacgcc-3' Rev: 5'-ctgcttcaaacgatccactcac-3'

Deep sequencing of genome segments of rRV/VP4-BAP at passages (PAS) 2, 6, 8, and 10. The sequences were obtained from the cDNA of RV particles in clarified supernatant recovered at 24 hpi of the indicated virus passage. The sequences of each genome segment at the indicated virus passage were built by aligning the reads to a reference sequence corresponding to the genome sequence present in the plasmid to prepare recombinant rRV-VP4-BAP by reverse genetics. The final alignment was performed using Clustal Omega multiple alignment tool present in SnapGene® (version 6.0.4).

GENOME SEGMENT 1:

VP1-SA11	GGCTATTAAAGCTGTACAATGGGGAAGTACAATCTAATCTTGTCAGAATATCTATCATTT	60
PAS10_VP1	GGCTATTAAAGCTGTACAATGGGGAAGTACAATCTAATCTTGTCAGAATATCTATCATTT	60
PAS8_VP1	GGCTATTAAAGCTGTACAATGGGGAAGTACAATCTAATCTTGTCAGAATATCTATCATTT	60
PAS6_VP1	GGCTATTAAAGCTGTACAATGGGGAAGTACAATCTAATCTTGTCAGAATATCTATCATTT	60
PAS2_VP1	GGCTATTAAAGCTGTACAATGGGGAAGTACAATCTAATCTTGTCAGAATATCTATCATTT	60
VP1-SA11	ATATATAATTCACAATCTGCAGTTCAAATCCAATATATTACTCTTCCAACAGTGAATTA	120
PAS10_VP1	ATATATAATTCACAATCTGCAGTTCAAATCCAATATATTACTCTTCCAACAGTGAATTA	120
PAS8_VP1	ATATATAATTCACAATCTGCAGTTCAAATCCAATATATTACTCTTCCAACAGTGAATTA	120
PAS6_VP1	ATATATAATTCACAATCTGCAGTTCAAATCCAATATATTACTCTTCCAACAGTGAATTA	120
PAS2_VP1	ATATATAATTCACAATCTGCAGTTCAAATCCAATATATTACTCTTCCAACAGTGAATTA	120
VP1-SA11	GAAAATAGATGTATTGAATTTCAATCCAAGTGTTTAGAGAACTCAAAGAATGGGTTATCG	180
PAS10_VP1	GAAAATAGATGTATTGAATTTCAATCCAAGTGTTTAGAGAACTCAAAGAATGGGTTATCG	180
PAS8_VP1	GAAAATAGATGTATTGAATTTCAATCCAAGTGTTTAGAGAACTCAAAGAATGGGTTATCG	180
PAS6_VP1	GAAAATAGATGTATTGAATTTCAATCCAAGTGTTTAGAGAACTCAAAGAATGGGTTATCG	180
PAS2_VP1	GAAAATAGATGTATTGAATTTCAATCCAAGTGTTTAGAGAACTCAAAGAATGGGTTATCG	180
VP1-SA11	TTAAGAAAGTTGTTGTTGAATATAATGATGTCATAGAAAATGCCACATTACTGTCAATA	240
PAS10_VP1	TTAAGAAAGTTGTTGTTGAATATAATGATGTCATAGAAAATGCCACATTACTGTCAATA	240
PAS8_VP1	TTAAGAAAGTTGTTGTTGAATATAATGATGTCATAGAAAATGCCACATTACTGTCAATA	240
PAS6_VP1	TTAAGAAAGTTGTTGTTGAATATAATGATGTCATAGAAAATGCCACATTACTGTCAATA	240
PAS2_VP1	TTAAGAAAGTTGTTGTTGAATATAATGATGTCATAGAAAATGCCACATTACTGTCAATA	240
VP1-SA11	CTATCATATTCTTACGACAAGTATAACGCTGTTGAAAGAAAATGGTGAAGTATGCGAAA	300
PAS10_VP1	CTATCATATTCTTACGACAAGTATAACGCTGTTGAAAGAAAATGGTGAAGTATGCGAAA	300
PAS8_VP1	CTATCATATTCTTACGACAAGTATAACGCTGTTGAAAGAAAATGGTGAAGTATGCGAAA	300
PAS6_VP1	CTATCATATTCTTACGACAAGTATAACGCTGTTGAAAGAAAATGGTGAAGTATGCGAAA	300
PAS2_VP1	CTATCATATTCTTACGACAAGTATAACGCTGTTGAAAGAAAATGGTGAAGTATGCGAAA	300
VP1-SA11	GGCAAACCATTTGGAGGCAGACTTAAACAGTGAATGAATTGGATTATGAGAACAATAAAATA	360
PAS10_VP1	GGCAAACCATTTGGAGGCAGACTTAAACAGTGAATGAATTGGATTATGAGAACAATAAAATA	360
PAS8_VP1	GGCAAACCATTTGGAGGCAGACTTAAACAGTGAATGAATTGGATTATGAGAACAATAAAATA	360
PAS6_VP1	GGCAAACCATTTGGAGGCAGACTTAAACAGTGAATGAATTGGATTATGAGAACAATAAAATA	360
PAS2_VP1	GGCAAACCATTTGGAGGCAGACTTAAACAGTGAATGAATTGGATTATGAGAACAATAAAATA	360
VP1-SA11	ACATCTGAATTATTTCCAACAGCGGAGGAATATACGGACTCACTAATGGATCCAGCAATT	420
PAS10_VP1	ACATCTGAATTATTTCCAACAGCGGAGGAATATACGGACTCACTAATGGATCCAGCAATT	420
PAS8_VP1	ACATCTGAATTATTTCCAACAGCGGAGGAATATACGGACTCACTAATGGATCCAGCAATT	420
PAS6_VP1	ACATCTGAATTATTTCCAACAGCGGAGGAATATACGGACTCACTAATGGATCCAGCAATT	420
PAS2_VP1	ACATCTGAATTATTTCCAACAGCGGAGGAATATACGGACTCACTAATGGATCCAGCAATT	420
VP1-SA11	TTAACTTCGCTATCATCAAATTTAAATGCAGTCATGTTCTGGTTGGAAAAACATGAAAAT	480

PAS10_VP1	TTAACTTCGCTATCATCAAATTTAAATGCAGTCATSTTCTGGTTGGAAAAACATGAAAAAT	480
PAS8_VP1	TTAACTTCGCTATCATCAAATTTAAATGCAGTCATSTTCTGGTTGGAAAAACATGAAAAAT	480
PAS6_VP1	TTAACTTCGCTATCATCAAATTTAAATGCAGTCATSTTCTGGTTGGAAAAACATGAAAAAT	480
PAS2_VP1	TTAACTTCGCTATCATCAAATTTAAATGCAGTCATSTTCTGGTTGGAAAAACATGAAAAAT	480
VP1-SA11	GATGTCGCTGAAAAACTTAAAGTTTATAAAAAGGAGATTAGACCTATTCCACCATAGTAGCC	540
PAS10_VP1	GATGTCGCTGAAAAACTTAAAGTTTATAAAAAGGAGATTAGACCTATTCCACCATAGTAGCC	540
PAS8_VP1	GATGTCGCTGAAAAACTTAAAGTTTATAAAAAGGAGATTAGACCTATTCCACCATAGTAGCC	540
PAS6_VP1	GATGTCGCTGAAAAACTTAAAGTTTATAAAAAGGAGATTAGACCTATTCCACCATAGTAGCC	540
PAS2_VP1	GATGTCGCTGAAAAACTTAAAGTTTATAAAAAGGAGATTAGACCTATTCCACCATAGTAGCC	540
VP1-SA11	TCAACGATAAAATAAATATGGCGTACCAAGGCATAACGCAAAGTACAGATATGAATACGAC	600
PAS10_VP1	TCAACGATAAAATAAATATGGCGTACCAAGGCATAACGCAAAGTACAGATATGAATACGAC	600
PAS8_VP1	TCAACGATAAAATAAATATGGCGTACCAAGGCATAACGCAAAGTACAGATATGAATACGAC	600
PAS6_VP1	TCAACGATAAAATAAATATGGCGTACCAAGGCATAACGCAAAGTACAGATATGAATACGAC	600
PAS2_VP1	TCAACGATAAAATAAATATGGCGTACCAAGGCATAACGCAAAGTACAGATATGAATACGAC	600
VP1-SA11	GTAATGAAAGATAAAACCGTACTACTTAGTGACATGGGCAAATTCCTCAATTGAAATGTTA	660
PAS10_VP1	GTAATGAAAGATAAAACCGTACTACTTAGTGACATGGGCAAATTCCTCAATTGAAATGTTA	660
PAS8_VP1	GTAATGAAAGATAAAACCGTACTACTTAGTGACATGGGCAAATTCCTCAATTGAAATGTTA	660
PAS6_VP1	GTAATGAAAGATAAAACCGTACTACTTAGTGACATGGGCAAATTCCTCAATTGAAATGTTA	660
PAS2_VP1	GTAATGAAAGATAAAACCGTACTACTTAGTGACATGGGCAAATTCCTCAATTGAAATGTTA	660
VP1-SA11	ATGTCAGTTTTCTCTCATGACGACTATTTGATAGCAAAAAGAGTTAATAGTGTTATCATAT	720
PAS10_VP1	ATGTCAGTTTTCTCTCATGACGACTATTTGATAGCAAAAAGAGTTAATAGTGTTATCATAT	720
PAS8_VP1	ATGTCAGTTTTCTCTCATGACGACTATTTGATAGCAAAAAGAGTTAATAGTGTTATCATAT	720
PAS6_VP1	ATGTCAGTTTTCTCTCATGACGACTATTTGATAGCAAAAAGAGTTAATAGTGTTATCATAT	720
PAS2_VP1	ATGTCAGTTTTCTCTCATGACGACTATTTGATAGCAAAAAGAGTTAATAGTGTTATCATAT	720
VP1-SA11	TCTAATAGATCTACTCTAGCAAAGTTAGTGTCATACCAATGTGCGATTTTGGTAGCCTTG	780
PAS10_VP1	TCTAATAGATCTACTCTAGCAAAGTTAGTGTCATACCAATGTGCGATTTTGGTAGCCTTG	780
PAS8_VP1	TCTAATAGATCTACTCTAGCAAAGTTAGTGTCATACCAATGTGCGATTTTGGTAGCCTTG	780
PAS6_VP1	TCTAATAGATCTACTCTAGCAAAGTTAGTGTCATACCAATGTGCGATTTTGGTAGCCTTG	780
PAS2_VP1	TCTAATAGATCTACTCTAGCAAAGTTAGTGTCATACCAATGTGCGATTTTGGTAGCCTTG	780
VP1-SA11	GTGGATATTAATGGAACATTTATTACAAATGAAGAATTAGAATTGGAATTTTCAAATAAA	840
PAS10_VP1	GTGGATATTAATGGAACATTTATTACAAATGAAGAATTAGAATTGGAATTTTCAAATAAA	840
PAS8_VP1	GTGGATATTAATGGAACATTTATTACAAATGAAGAATTAGAATTGGAATTTTCAAATAAA	840
PAS6_VP1	GTGGATATTAATGGAACATTTATTACAAATGAAGAATTAGAATTGGAATTTTCAAATAAA	840
PAS2_VP1	GTGGATATTAATGGAACATTTATTACAAATGAAGAATTAGAATTGGAATTTTCAAATAAA	840
VP1-SA11	TATGTACGAGCAATAGTTCGGGATCAAACATTTGACGAATTAATCAAATGCTTGACAAT	900
PAS10_VP1	TATGTACGAGCAATAGTTCGGGATCAAACATTTGACGAATTAATCAAATGCTTGACAAT	900
PAS8_VP1	TATGTACGAGCAATAGTTCGGGATCAAACATTTGACGAATTAATCAAATGCTTGACAAT	900
PAS6_VP1	TATGTACGAGCAATAGTTCGGGATCAAACATTTGACGAATTAATCAAATGCTTGACAAT	900
PAS2_VP1	TATGTACGAGCAATAGTTCGGGATCAAACATTTGACGAATTAATCAAATGCTTGACAAT	900
VP1-SA11	ATGAGGAAAGCTGGATTAGTTGACATACCTAAGATGATACAGGACTGGTTAGTTGATCGT	960
PAS10_VP1	ATGAGGAAAGCTGGATTAGTTGACATACCTAAGATGATACAGGACTGGTTAGTTGATCGT	960
PAS8_VP1	ATGAGGAAAGCTGGATTAGTTGACATACCTAAGATGATACAGGACTGGTTAGTTGATCGT	960
PAS6_VP1	ATGAGGAAAGCTGGATTAGTTGACATACCTAAGATGATACAGGACTGGTTAGTTGATCGT	960
PAS2_VP1	ATGAGGAAAGCTGGATTAGTTGACATACCTAAGATGATACAGGACTGGTTAGTTGATCGT	960
VP1-SA11	TCTATCGAAAAATTTCCATTAATGGCTAAGATATATTCATGGTCGTTTCATGTTGGATTT	1020
PAS10_VP1	TCTATCGAAAAATTTCCATTAATGGCTAAGATATATTCATGGTCGTTTCATGTTGGATTT	1020
PAS8_VP1	TCTATCGAAAAATTTCCATTAATGGCTAAGATATATTCATGGTCGTTTCATGTTGGATTT	1020
PAS6_VP1	TCTATCGAAAAATTTCCATTAATGGCTAAGATATATTCATGGTCGTTTCATGTTGGATTT	1020
PAS2_VP1	TCTATCGAAAAATTTCCATTAATGGCTAAGATATATTCATGGTCGTTTCATGTTGGATTT	1020
VP1-SA11	AGAAAACAAAAAATGCTAGATGCTGCGCTGGATCAATTGAAAACCTGAGTATACAGAAAAAT	1080
PAS10_VP1	AGAAAACAAAAAATGCTAGATGCTGCGCTGGATCAATTGAAAACCTGAGTATACAGAAAAAT	1080
PAS8_VP1	AGAAAACAAAAAATGCTAGATGCTGCGCTGGATCAATTGAAAACCTGAGTATACAGAAAAAT	1080
PAS6_VP1	AGAAAACAAAAAATGCTAGATGCTGCGCTGGATCAATTGAAAACCTGAGTATACAGAAAAAT	1080
PAS2_VP1	AGAAAACAAAAAATGCTAGATGCTGCGCTGGATCAATTGAAAACCTGAGTATACAGAAAAAT	1080
VP1-SA11	GTGGACGATGAAATGTATCGGGAATATACAATGTTAATAAGAGATGAAGTAGTTAAAAATG	1140
PAS10_VP1	GTGGACGATGAAATGTATCGGGAATATACAATGTTAATAAGAGATGAAGTAGTTAAAAATG	1140
PAS8_VP1	GTGGACGATGAAATGTATCGGGAATATACAATGTTAATAAGAGATGAAGTAGTTAAAAATG	1140
PAS6_VP1	GTGGACGATGAAATGTATCGGGAATATACAATGTTAATAAGAGATGAAGTAGTTAAAAATG	1140
PAS2_VP1	GTGGACGATGAAATGTATCGGGAATATACAATGTTAATAAGAGATGAAGTAGTTAAAAATG	1140

VP1-SA11	CTTGAAGAACCAGTTAAACATGATGATCACTTGCTACGAGATTCTGAGTTAGCTGGTTTA	1200
PAS10_VP1	CTTGAAGAACCAGTTAAACATGATGATCACTTGCTACGAGATTCTGAGTTAGCTGGTTTA	1200
PAS8_VP1	CTTGAAGAACCAGTTAAACATGATGATCACTTGCTACGAGATTCTGAGTTAGCTGGTTTA	1200
PAS6_VP1	CTTGAAGAACCAGTTAAACATGATGATCACTTGCTACGAGATTCTGAGTTAGCTGGTTTA	1200
PAS2_VP1	CTTGAAGAACCAGTTAAACATGATGATCACTTGCTACGAGATTCTGAGTTAGCTGGTTTA	1200
VP1-SA11	CTATCAATGTCGTCAGCATCGAATGGTGAGTCAAGGCAGCTAAAGTTTGGTAGGAAAACA	1260
PAS10_VP1	CTATCAATGTCGTCAGCATCGAATGGTGAGTCAAGGCAGCTAAAGTTTGGTAGGAAAACA	1260
PAS8_VP1	CTATCAATGTCGTCAGCATCGAATGGTGAGTCAAGGCAGCTAAAGTTTGGTAGGAAAACA	1260
PAS6_VP1	CTATCAATGTCGTCAGCATCGAATGGTGAGTCAAGGCAGCTAAAGTTTGGTAGGAAAACA	1260
PAS2_VP1	CTATCAATGTCGTCAGCATCGAATGGTGAGTCAAGGCAGCTAAAGTTTGGTAGGAAAACA	1260
VP1-SA11	ATTTTTTCAACTAAAAAGAATATGCATGTCATGGATGATATGGCTAACGAAAGATACACG	1320
PAS10_VP1	ATTTTTTCAACTAAAAAGAATATGCATGTCATGGATGATATGGCTAACGAAAGATACACG	1320
PAS8_VP1	ATTTTTTCAACTAAAAAGAATATGCATGTCATGGATGATATGGCTAACGAAAGATACACG	1320
PAS6_VP1	ATTTTTTCAACTAAAAAGAATATGCATGTCATGGATGATATGGCTAACGAAAGATACACG	1320
PAS2_VP1	ATTTTTTCAACTAAAAAGAATATGCATGTCATGGATGATATGGCTAACGAAAGATACACG	1320
VP1-SA11	CCTGGTATAATACCACCAGTGAATGTTGATAAACCAATACCATTAGGAAGAAGAGATGTT	1380
PAS10_VP1	CCTGGTATAATACCACCAGTGAATGTTGATAAACCAATACCATTAGGAAGAAGAGATGTT	1380
PAS8_VP1	CCTGGTATAATACCACCAGTGAATGTTGATAAACCAATACCATTAGGAAGAAGAGATGTT	1380
PAS6_VP1	CCTGGTATAATACCACCAGTGAATGTTGATAAACCAATACCATTAGGAAGAAGAGATGTT	1380
PAS2_VP1	CCTGGTATAATACCACCAGTGAATGTTGATAAACCAATACCATTAGGAAGAAGAGATGTT	1380
VP1-SA11	CCAGGAAGAAGGACTAGAATAATATTCATTCTGCCATACGAATATTTTCATAGCACAGCAC	1440
PAS10_VP1	CCAGGAAGAAGGACTAGAATAATATTCATTCTGCCATACGAATATTTTCATAGCACAGCAC	1440
PAS8_VP1	CCAGGAAGAAGGACTAGAATAATATTCATTCTGCCATACGAATATTTTCATAGCACAGCAC	1440
PAS6_VP1	CCAGGAAGAAGGACTAGAATAATATTCATTCTGCCATACGAATATTTTCATAGCACAGCAC	1440
PAS2_VP1	CCAGGAAGAAGGACTAGAATAATATTCATTCTGCCATACGAATATTTTCATAGCACAGCAC	1440
VP1-SA11	GCTGTAGTTGAAAAAATGTTGATTTACGCAAAACATACGAGAGAATACGCTGAATTTTAT	1500
PAS10_VP1	GCTGTAGTTGAAAAAATGTTGATTTACGCAAAACATACGAGAGAATACGCTGAATTTTAT	1500
PAS8_VP1	GCTGTAGTTGAAAAAATGTTGATTTACGCAAAACATACGAGAGAATACGCTGAATTTTAT	1500
PAS6_VP1	GCTGTAGTTGAAAAAATGTTGATTTACGCAAAACATACGAGAGAATACGCTGAATTTTAT	1500
PAS2_VP1	GCTGTAGTTGAAAAAATGTTGATTTACGCAAAACATACGAGAGAATACGCTGAATTTTAT	1500
VP1-SA11	TCACAATCAAACCAATTATTGTCTACACGGCGATGTAACGCGTTTTTTGTCTAATAACACA	1560
PAS10_VP1	TCACAATCAAACCAATTATTGTCTACACGGCGATGTAACGCGTTTTTTGTCTAATAACACA	1560
PAS8_VP1	TCACAATCAAACCAATTATTGTCTACACGGCGATGTAACGCGTTTTTTGTCTAATAACACA	1560
PAS6_VP1	TCACAATCAAACCAATTATTGTCTACACGGCGATGTAACGCGTTTTTTGTCTAATAACACA	1560
PAS2_VP1	TCACAATCAAACCAATTATTGTCTACACGGCGATGTAACGCGTTTTTTGTCTAATAACACA	1560
VP1-SA11	ATGGTCTTGTATACGGATGTATCTCAGTGGGATTCGCTCAGCATAATACACAGCCATTT	1620
PAS10_VP1	ATGGTCTTGTATACGGATGTATCTCAGTGGGATTCGCTCAGCATAATACACAGCCATTT	1620
PAS8_VP1	ATGGTCTTGTATACGGATGTATCTCAGTGGGATTCGCTCAGCATAATACACAGCCATTT	1620
PAS6_VP1	ATGGTCTTGTATACGGATGTATCTCAGTGGGATTCGCTCAGCATAATACACAGCCATTT	1620
PAS2_VP1	ATGGTCTTGTATACGGATGTATCTCAGTGGGATTCGCTCAGCATAATACACAGCCATTT	1620
VP1-SA11	AGGAAAGGAATAATAATGGGACTGGACATATTAGCTAACATGACTAATGATGCTAAAGTT	1680
PAS10_VP1	AGGAAAGGAATAATAATGGGACTGGACATATTAGCTAACATGACTAATGATGCTAAAGTT	1680
PAS8_VP1	AGGAAAGGAATAATAATGGGACTGGACATATTAGCTAACATGACTAATGATGCTAAAGTT	1680
PAS6_VP1	AGGAAAGGAATAATAATGGGACTGGACATATTAGCTAACATGACTAATGATGCTAAAGTT	1680
PAS2_VP1	AGGAAAGGAATAATAATGGGACTGGACATATTAGCTAACATGACTAATGATGCTAAAGTT	1680
VP1-SA11	CTTCAGACATTTAACTTTATACAAACAAACACAAATCAATCTCATGGATTTCATACGTTCAA	1740
PAS10_VP1	CTTCAGACATTTAACTTTATACAAACAAACACAAATCAATCTCATGGATTTCATACGTTCAA	1740
PAS8_VP1	CTTCAGACATTTAACTTTATACAAACAAACACAAATCAATCTCATGGATTTCATACGTTCAA	1740
PAS6_VP1	CTTCAGACATTTAACTTTATACAAACAAACACAAATCAATCTCATGGATTTCATACGTTCAA	1740
PAS2_VP1	CTTCAGACATTTAACTTTATACAAACAAACACAAATCAATCTCATGGATTTCATACGTTCAA	1740
VP1-SA11	ATACCAGATGGCAACGTCATTAAGAAAATACAATACGGGGCAGTAGCATCAGGAGAGAAA	1800
PAS10_VP1	ATACCAGATGGCAACGTCATTAAGAAAATACAATACGGGGCAGTAGCATCAGGAGAGAAA	1800
PAS8_VP1	ATACCAGATGGCAACGTCATTAAGAAAATACAATACGGGGCAGTAGCATCAGGAGAGAAA	1800
PAS6_VP1	ATACCAGATGGCAACGTCATTAAGAAAATACAATACGGGGCAGTAGCATCAGGAGAGAAA	1800
PAS2_VP1	ATACCAGATGGCAACGTCATTAAGAAAATACAATACGGGGCAGTAGCATCAGGAGAGAAA	1800
VP1-SA11	CAAACGAAAGCAGCAAATTCATAGCAAATTTGGCACTGATTAACCGTTTTTGTACCGT	1860
PAS10_VP1	CAAACGAAAGCAGCAAATTCATAGCAAATTTGGCACTGATTAACCGTTTTTGTACCGT	1860
PAS8_VP1	CAAACGAAAGCAGCAAATTCATAGCAAATTTGGCACTGATTAACCGTTTTTGTACCGT	1860

PAS6_VP1	CAAACGAAAGCAGCAAATTC AATAGCAAATTTGGCACTGATTA AAAACGGTTTTGTACCGT	1860
PAS2_VP1	CAAACGAAAGCAGCAAATTC AATAGCAAATTTGGCACTGATTA AAAACGGTTTTGTACCGT	1860
VP1-SA11	ATTTCTAACAAACATTCATTCGCAACAAAAATAATAAGAGTTGATGGAGATGATAACTAT	1920
PAS10_VP1	ATTTCTAACAAACATTCATTCGCAACAAAAATAATAAGAGTTGATGGAGATGATAACTAT	1920
PAS8_VP1	ATTTCTAACAAACATTCATTCGCAACAAAAATAATAAGAGTTGATGGAGATGATAACTAT	1920
PAS6_VP1	ATTTCTAACAAACATTCATTCGCAACAAAAATAATAAGAGTTGATGGAGATGATAACTAT	1920
PAS2_VP1	ATTTCTAACAAACATTCATTCGCAACAAAAATAATAAGAGTTGATGGAGATGATAACTAT	1920
VP1-SA11	GCGGTGCTACAATTTAATACAGAGGTGACTAAGCAGATGATCCAAGACGTATCGAACGAT	1980
PAS10_VP1	GCGGTGCTACAATTTAATACAGAGGTGACTAAGCAGATGATCCAAGACGTATCGAACGAT	1980
PAS8_VP1	GCGGTGCTACAATTTAATACAGAGGTGACTAAGCAGATGATCCAAGACGTATCGAACGAT	1980
PAS6_VP1	GCGGTGCTACAATTTAATACAGAGGTGACTAAGCAGATGATCCAAGACGTATCGAACGAT	1980
PAS2_VP1	GCGGTGCTACAATTTAATACAGAGRTGACTAAGCAGATGATCCAAGACGTATCGAACGAT	1980
VP1-SA11	GTAAGAGAAACTTATGCACGCATGAATGCTAAAGTTAAAGCTCTGGTATCCACAGTAGGA	2040
PAS10_VP1	GTAAGAGAAACTTATGCACGCATGAATGCTAAAGTTAAAGCTCTGGTATCCACAGTAGGA	2040
PAS8_VP1	GTAAGAGAAACTTATGCACGCATGAATGCTAAAGTTAAAGCTCTGGTATCCACAGTAGGA	2040
PAS6_VP1	GTAAGAGAAACTTATGCACGCATGAATGCTAAAGTTAAAGCTCTGGTATCCACAGTAGGA	2040
PAS2_VP1	GTAAGAGAAACTTATGCACGCATGAATGCTAAAGTTAAAGCTCTGGTATCCACAGTAGGA	2040
VP1-SA11	ATAGAAATTGCTAAAAGGTACATTCGAGGTGGAAAAATATTTTTTCGAGCTGGAATAAAT	2100
PAS10_VP1	ATAGAAATTGCTAAAAGGTACATTCGAGGTGGAAAAATATTTTTTCGAGCTGGAATAAAT	2100
PAS8_VP1	ATAGAAATTGCTAAAAGGTACATTCGAGGTGGAAAAATATTTTTTCGAGCTGGAATAAAT	2100
PAS6_VP1	ATAGAAATTGCTAAAAGGTACATTCGAGGTGGAAAAATATTTTTTCGAGCTGGAATAAAT	2100
PAS2_VP1	ATAGAAATTGCTAAAAGGTACATTCGAGGTGGAAAAATATTTTTTCGAGCTGGAATAAAT	2100
VP1-SA11	CTACTTAATAATGAAAAGAGAGGGCAGAGTACGCAGTGGGATCAAGCAGCAATTTTATAT	2160
PAS10_VP1	CTACTTAATAATGAAAAGAGAGGGCAGAGTACGCAGTGGGATCAAGCAGCAATTTTATAT	2160
PAS8_VP1	CTACTTAATAATGAAAAGAGAGGGCAGAGTACGCAGTGGGATCAAGCAGCAATTTTATAT	2160
PAS6_VP1	CTACTTAATAATGAAAAGAGAGGGCAGAGTACGCAGTGGGATCAAGCAGCAATTTTATAT	2160
PAS2_VP1	CTACTTAATAATGAAAAGAGAGGGCAGAGTACGCAGTGGGATCAAGCAGCAATTTTATAT	2160
VP1-SA11	TCAAATTATATTGTAATAGACTTAGAGGATTTGAAACTGATAGGGAGTTTATTTTAACT	2220
PAS10_VP1	TCAAATTATATTGTAATAGACTTAGAGGATTTGAAACTGATAGGGAGTTTATTTTAACT	2220
PAS8_VP1	TCAAATTATATTGTAATAGACTTAGAGGATTTGAAACTGATAGGGAGTTTATTTTAACT	2220
PAS6_VP1	TCAAATTATATTGTAATAGACTTAGAGGATTTGAAACTGATAGGGAGTTTATTTTAACT	2220
PAS2_VP1	TCAAATTATATTGTAATAGACTTAGAGGATTTGAAACTGATAGGGAGTTTATTTTAACT	2220
VP1-SA11	AAGATAATGCAGATGACGTCAGTCGCAATTACTGGATCATTAAAGACTATTTCTTCTGAA	2280
PAS10_VP1	AAGATAATGCAGATGACGTCAGTCGCAATTACTGGATCATTAAAGACTATTTCTTCTGAA	2280
PAS8_VP1	AAGATAATGCAGATGACGTCAGTCGCAATTACTGGATCATTAAAGACTATTTCTTCTGAA	2280
PAS6_VP1	AAGATAATGCAGATGACGTCAGTCGCAATTACTGGATCATTAAAGACTATTTCTTCTGAA	2280
PAS2_VP1	AAGATAATGCAGATGACGTCAGTCGCAATTACTGGATCATTAAAGACTATTTCTTCTGAA	2280
VP1-SA11	CGCGTATTAAC TACGAATTC AACATTTAAAGTATTTGACTCGGAGGATTTTATTATAGAG	2340
PAS10_VP1	CGCGTATTAAC TACGAATTC AACATTTAAAGTATTTGACTCGGAGGATTTTATTATAGAG	2340
PAS8_VP1	CGCGTATTAAC TACGAATTC AACATTTAAAGTATTTGACTCGGAGGATTTTATTATAGAG	2340
PAS6_VP1	CGCGTATTAAC TACGAATTC AACATTTAAAGTATTTGACTCGGAGGATTTTATTATAGAG	2340
PAS2_VP1	CGCGTATTAAC TACGAATTC AACATTTAAAGTATTTGACTCGGAGGATTTTATTATAGAG	2340
VP1-SA11	TACGGAACGACTGATGACGAAGTATATATACAAAGAGCGTTTCATGTCTTTATCAAGTCAG	2400
PAS10_VP1	TACGGAACGACTGATGACGAAGTATATATACAAAGAGCGTTTCATGTCTTTATCAAGTCAG	2400
PAS8_VP1	TACGGAACGACTGATGACGAAGTATATATACAAAGAGCGTTTCATGTCTTTATCAAGTCAG	2400
PAS6_VP1	TACGGAACGACTGATGACGAAGTATATATACAAAGAGCGTTTCATGTCTTTATCAAGTCAG	2400
PAS2_VP1	TACGGAACGACYGATGACGAAGTATATATACAAAGAGCGTTTCATGTCTTTATCAAGTCAG	2400
VP1-SA11	AAATCAGGAATAGCCGATGAGATAGCGGCATCATCAACATTTAAAAATTACGTCACGAGA	2460
PAS10_VP1	AAATCAGGAATAGCCGATGAGATAGCGGCATCATCAACATTTAAAAATTACGTCACGAGA	2460
PAS8_VP1	AAATCAGGAATAGCCGATGAGATAGCGGCATCATCAACATTTAAAAATTACGTCACGAGA	2460
PAS6_VP1	AAATCAGGAATAGCCGATGAGATAGCGGCATCATCAACATTTAAAAATTACGTCACGAGA	2460
PAS2_VP1	AAATCAGGAATAGCCGATGAGATAGCGGCATCATCAACATTTAAAAATTACGTCACGAGA	2460
VP1-SA11	CTATCTGAACAGTTATTATTTTCAAAGAATAATATAGTGTCCAGAGGAATAGCTTTGACT	2520
PAS10_VP1	CTATCTGAACAGTTATTATTTTCAAAGAATAATATAGTGTCCAGAGGAATAGCTTTGACT	2520
PAS8_VP1	CTATCTGAACAGTTATTATTTTCAAAGAATAATATAGTGTCCAGAGGAATAGCTTTGACT	2520
PAS6_VP1	CTATCTGAACAGTTATTATTTTCAAAGAATAATATAGTGTCCAGAGGAATAGCTTTGACT	2520
PAS2_VP1	CTATCTGAACAGTTATTATTTTCAAAGAATAATATAGTGTCCAGAGGAATAGCTTTGACT	2520
VP1-SA11	GAAAAAGCGAAATTGAATTCATACGCTCCAATATCGCTTGAGAAAAGACGTGCACAGATA	2580

PAS10_VP1	GAAAAAGCGAAATTGAATTCATACGCTCCAATATCGCTTGAGAAAAGACGTGCACAGATA	2580
PAS8_VP1	GAAAAAGCGAAATTGAATTCATACGCTCCAATATCGCTTGAGAAAAGACGTGCACAGATA	2580
PAS6_VP1	GAAAAAGCGAAATTGAATTCATACGCTCCAATATCGCTTGAGAAAAGACGTGCACAGATA	2580
PAS2_VP1	GAAAAAGCGAAATTGAATTCATACGCTCCAATATCGCTTGAGAAAAGACGTGCACAGATA	2580
VP1-SA11	TCAGCTTTATTGACTATGTTGCAGAAACCGGTCACCTTCAAATCAAGTAAAATAACAATA	2640
PAS10_VP1	TCAGCTTTATTGACTATGTTGCAGAAACCGGTCACCTTCAAATCAAGTAAAATAACAATA	2640
PAS8_VP1	TCAGCTTTATTGACTATGTTGCAGAAACCGGTCACCTTCAAATCAAGTAAAATAACAATA	2640
PAS6_VP1	TCAGCTTTATTGACTATGTTGCAGAAACCGGTCACCTTCAAATCAAGTAAAATAACAATA	2640
PAS2_VP1	TCAGCTTTATTGACTATGTTGCAGAAACCGGTCACCTTCAAATCAAGTAAAATAACAATA	2640
VP1-SA11	AATGACATACTCAGAGATATAAAACCATTTTTTACAGTAAAGTGATGCACACTTACCTATA	2700
PAS10_VP1	AATGACATACTCAGAGATATAAAACCATTTTTTACAGTAAAGTGATGCACACTTACCTATA	2700
PAS8_VP1	AATGACATACTCAGAGATATAAAACCATTTTTTACAGTAAAGTGATGCACACTTACCTATA	2700
PAS6_VP1	AATGACATACTCAGAGATATAAAACCATTTTTTACAGTAAAGTGATGCACACTTACCTATA	2700
PAS2_VP1	RATGACATACTCAGAGATATAAAACCATTTTTTACAGTAAAGTGATGCACACTTACCTATA	2700
VP1-SA11	CAATACCAAAAAATTTATGCCAACTTTGCCAGATAACGTACAGTATATAAATCAATGTATA	2760
PAS10_VP1	CAATACCAAAAAATTTATGCCAACTTTGCCAGATAACGTACAGTATATAAATCAATGTATA	2760
PAS8_VP1	CAATACCAAAAAATTTATGCCAACTTTGCCAGATAACGTACAGTATATAAATCAATGTATA	2760
PAS6_VP1	CAATACCAAAAAATTTATGCCAACTTTGCCAGATAACGTACAGTATATAAATCAATGTATA	2760
PAS2_VP1	CAATACCAAAAAATTTATGCCAACTTTGCCAGATAACGTACAGTATATAAATCAATGTATA	2760
VP1-SA11	GGATCCAGAACTTATCAAATTGAAGATGACGGTTCGAAGTCAGCCATATCTAGACTAATA	2820
PAS10_VP1	GGATCCAGAACTTATCAAATTGAAGATGACGGTTCGAAGTCAGCCATATCTAGACTAATA	2820
PAS8_VP1	GGATCCAGAACTTATCAAATTGAAGATGACGGTTCGAAGTCAGCCATATCTAGACTAATA	2820
PAS6_VP1	GGATCCAGAACTTATCAAATTGAAGATGACGGTTCGAAGTCAGCCATATCTAGACTAATA	2820
PAS2_VP1	GGATCCAGAACTTATCAAATTGAAGATGACGGTTCGAAGTCAGCCATATCTAGACTAATA	2820
VP1-SA11	TCAAAGTATTCAGTTTATAAGCCATCAATTGAAGAATTGTATAAAGTGATTTTCATTGCAT	2880
PAS10_VP1	TCAAAGTATTCAGTTTATAAGCCATCAATTGAAGAATTGTATAAAGTGATTTTCATTGCAT	2880
PAS8_VP1	TCAAAGTATTCAGTTTATAAGCCATCAATTGAAGAATTGTATAAAGTGATTTTCATTGCAT	2880
PAS6_VP1	TCAAAGTATTCAGTTTATAAGCCATCAATTGAAGAATTGTATAAAGTGATTTTCATTGCAT	2880
PAS2_VP1	TCAAAGTATTCAGTTTATAAGCCATCAATTGAAGAATTGTATAAAGTGATTTTCATTGCAT	2880
VP1-SA11	GAAAACGAAATACAATTATATCTGATTTTCATTAGGAATACCGAAAATAGACGCTGACACG	2940
PAS10_VP1	GAAAACGAAATACAATTATATCTGATTTTCATTAGGAATACCGAAAATAGACGCTGACACG	2940
PAS8_VP1	GAAAACGAAATACAATTATATCTGATTTTCATTAGGAATACCGAAAATAGACGCTGACACG	2940
PAS6_VP1	GAAAACGAAATACAATTATATCTGATTTTCATTAGGAATACCGAAAATAGACGCTGACACG	2940
PAS2_VP1	GAAAACGAAATACAATTATATCTGATTTTCATTAGGAATACCGAAAATAGACGCTGACACG	2940
VP1-SA11	TATGTTGGATCAAAGATTTATTTCTCAAGATAAGTATAGAATACTAGAATCATAACGTGTAC	3000
PAS10_VP1	TATGTTGGATCAAAGATTTATTTCTCAAGATAAGTATAGAATACTAGAATCATAACGTGTAC	3000
PAS8_VP1	TATGTTGGATCAAAGATTTATTTCTCAAGATAAGTATAGAATACTAGAATCATAACGTGTAC	3000
PAS6_VP1	TATGTTGGATCAAAGATTTATTTCTCAAGATAAGTATAGAATACTAGAATCATAACGTGTAC	3000
PAS2_VP1	TATGTTGGATCAAAGATTTATTTCTCAAGATAAGTATAGAATACTAGAATCATAACGTGTAC	3000
VP1-SA11	AATTTATTGTCCATTAATTATGGATGCTATCAATTATTTGATTTCAATTCACCGGACTTG	3060
PAS10_VP1	AATTTATTGTCCATTAATTATGGATGCTATCAATTATTTGATTTCAATTCACCGGACTTG	3060
PAS8_VP1	AATTTATTGTCCATTAATTATGGATGCTATCAATTATTTGATTTCAATTCACCGGACTTG	3060
PAS6_VP1	AATTTATTGTCCATTAATTATGGATGCTATCAATTATTTGATTTCAATTCACCGGACTTG	3060
PAS2_VP1	AATTTATTGTCCATTAATTATGGATGCTATCAATTATTTGATTTCAATTCACCGGACTTG	3060
VP1-SA11	GAGAAGCTGATAAGAATACCATTTAAGGGAAAAATACCAGCTGTTACATTCATATTACAC	3120
PAS10_VP1	GAGAAGCTGATAAGAATACCATTTAAGGGAAAAATACCAGCTGTTACATTCATATTACAC	3120
PAS8_VP1	GAGAAGCTGATAAGAATACCATTTAAGGGAAAAATACCAGCTGTTACATTCATATTACAC	3120
PAS6_VP1	GAGAAGCTGATAAGAATACCATTTAAGGGAAAAATACCAGCTGTTACATTCATATTACAC	3120
PAS2_VP1	GAGAAGCTGATAAGAATACCATTTAAGGGAAAAATACCAGCTGTTACATTCATATTACAC	3120
VP1-SA11	TTATATGCAAAGCTAGAAGTTATAAACTACGCTATAAAAAATGGTTCATGGATAAGCCTA	3180
PAS10_VP1	TTATATGCAAAGCTAGAAGTTATAAACTACGCTATAAAAAATGGTTCATGGATAAGCCTA	3180
PAS8_VP1	TTATATGCAAAGCTAGAAGTTATAAACTACGCTATAAAAAATGGTTCATGGATAAGCCTA	3180
PAS6_VP1	TTATATGCAAAGCTAGAAGTTATAAACTACGCTATAAAAAATGGTTCATGGATAAGCCTA	3180
PAS2_VP1	TTATATGCAAAGCTAGAAGTTATAAACTACGCTATAAAAAATGGTTCATGGATAAGCCTA	3180
VP1-SA11	TTTTGCAATTACCCTAAATCAGAAATGATAAAATTTATGGAAGAAGATGTGGAACATCACC	3240
PAS10_VP1	TTTTGCAATTACCCTAAATCAGAAATGATAAAATTTATGGAAGAAGATGTGGAACATCACC	3240
PAS8_VP1	TTTTGCAATTACCCTAAATCAGAAATGATAAAATTTATGGAAGAAGATGTGGAACATCACC	3240
PAS6_VP1	TTTTGCAATTACCCTAAATCAGAAATGATAAAATTTATGGAAGAAGATGTGGAACATCACC	3240
PAS2_VP1	TTTTGCAATTACCCTAAATCAGAAATGATAAAATTTATGGAAGAAGATGTGGAACATCACC	3240

VP1-SA11	TCATTACGTTTCGCCGTACACTAACGCGAACTTCTTTCAAGATTAGAACGCTTAGATGTGA	3300
PAS10_VP1	TCATTACGTTTCGCCGTACACTAACGCGAACTTCTTTCAAGATTAGAACGCTTAGATGTGA	3300
PAS8_VP1	TCATTACGTTTCGCCGTACACTAACGCGAACTTCTTTCAAGATTAGAACGCTTAGATGTGA	3300
PAS6_VP1	TCATTACGTTTCGCCGTACACTAACGCGAACTTCTTTCAAGATTAGAACGCTTAGATGTGA	3300
PAS2_VP1	TCATTACGTTTCGCCGTACACTAACGCGAACTTCTTTCAAGATTAGAACGCTTAGATGTGA	3300
VP1-SA11	CC	3302
PAS10_VP1	CC	3302
PAS8_VP1	CC	3302
PAS6_VP1	CC	3302
PAS2_VP1	CC	3302

GENOME SEGMENT 2:

VP2-SA11	GGCTATTAAAGGCTCAATGGCGTATCGAAAACGTGGAGCGCGTGTGAGACGAATCTAAA	60
PAS10_VP2	GGCTATTAAAGGCTCAATGGCGTATCGAAAACGTGGAGCGCGTGTGAGACGAATCTAAA	60
PAS8_VP2	GGCTATTAAAGGCTCAATGGCGTATCGAAAACGTGGAGCGCGTGTGAGACGAATCTAAA	60
PAS6_VP2	GGCTATTAAAGGCTCAATGGCGTATCGAAAACGTGGAGCGCGTGTGAGACGAATCTAAA	60
PAS2_VP2	NNNNNNNNNNNNNTCAATGGCGTATCGAAAACGTGGRGCGCGTGTGAGACGAATCTAAA	60
VP2-SA11	ACAAGATGAACGAATGCAAGAAAAAGAAGATAGCAAGAACATTAATAATGACAGTCCTAA	120
PAS10_VP2	ACAAGATGAACGAATGCAAGAAAAAGAAGATAGCAAGAACATTAATAATGACAGTCCTAA	120
PAS8_VP2	ACAAGATGAACGAATGCAAGAAAAAGAAGATAGCAAGAACATTAATAATGACAGTCCTAA	120
PAS6_VP2	ACAAGATGAACGAATGCAAGAAAAAGAAGATAGCAAGAACATTAATAATGACAGTCCTAA	120
PAS2_VP2	ACAAGATGAACGAATGCAAGAAAAAGAAGATAGCAAGAACATTAATAATGACAGTCCTAA	120
VP2-SA11	ATCACAATTATCAGAAAAAGTATTATCTAAGAAAGAAGAGATAATTACAGATAATCAAGA	180
PAS10_VP2	ATCACAATTATCAGAAAAAGTATTATCTAAGAAAGAAGAGATAATTACAGATAATCAAGA	180
PAS8_VP2	ATCACAATTATCAGAAAAAGTATTATCTAAGAAAGAAGAGATAATTACAGATAATCAAGA	180
PAS6_VP2	ATCACAATTATCAGAAAAAGTATTATCTAAGAAAGAAGAGATAATTACAGATAATCAAGA	180
PAS2_VP2	ATCACAATTATCAGAAAAAGTATTATCTAAGAAAGAAGAGATAATTACAGATAATCAAGA	180
VP2-SA11	AGAAGTTAAGATATCTGATGAGGTAATAAAGAAAGTTCGAAACAGTTGTT	240
PAS10_VP2	AGAAGTTAAGATATCTGATGAGGTAATAAAGAAAGTTCGAAACAGTTGTT	240
PAS8_VP2	AGAAGTTAAGATATCTGATGAGGTAATAAAGAAAGTTCGAAACAGTTGTT	240
PAS6_VP2	AGAAGTTAAGATATCTGATGAGGTAATAAAGAAAGTTCGAAACAGTTGTT	240
PAS2_VP2	AGAAGTTAAGATATCTGATGAGGTAATAAAGAAAGTTCGAAACAGTTGTT	240
VP2-SA11	AGAAGTACTTAAAAACAAAAGAGGAACATCAAAAAGAAGTTCAGTATGAAATATTACAAA	300
PAS10_VP2	AGAAGTACTTAAAAACAAAAGAGGAACATCAAAAAGAAGTTCAGTATGAAATATTACAAA	300
PAS8_VP2	AGAAGTACTTAAAAACAAAAGAGGAACATCAAAAAGAAGTTCAGTATGAAATATTACAAA	300
PAS6_VP2	AGAAGTACTTAAAAACAAAAGAGGAACATCAAAAAGAAGTTCAGTATGAAATATTACAAA	300
PAS2_VP2	AGAAGTACTTAAAAACAAAAGAGGAACATCAAAAAGAAGTTCAGTATGAAATATTACAAA	300
VP2-SA11	AACTATCCCTACATTTGAACCAAAAAGAGTCAATACTCAAAAAATTAGAAGACATAAAACC	360
PAS10_VP2	AACTATCCCTACATTTGAACCAAAAAGAGTCAATACTCAAAAAATTAGAAGACATAAAACC	360
PAS8_VP2	AACTATCCCTACATTTGAACCAAAAAGAGTCAATACTCAAAAAATTAGAAGACATAAAACC	360
PAS6_VP2	AACTATCCCTACATTTGAACCAAAAAGAGTCAATACTCAAAAAATTAGAAGACATAAAACC	360
PAS2_VP2	AACTATCCCTACATTTGAACCAAAAAGAGTCAATACTCAAAAAATTAGAAGACATAAAACC	360
VP2-SA11	AGAACAAGCAAAGAAACAACTAAACTGTTTTCGAATATTTGAACCGAAACAATTGCCTAT	420
PAS10_VP2	AGAACAAGCAAAGAAACAACTAAACTGTTTTCGAATATTTGAACCGAAACAATTGCCTAT	420
PAS8_VP2	AGAACAAGCAAAGAAACAACTAAACTGTTTTCGAATATTTGAACCGAAACAATTGCCTAT	420
PAS6_VP2	AGAACAAGCAAAGAAACAACTAAACTGTTTTCGAATATTTGAACCGAAACAATTGCCTAT	420
PAS2_VP2	AGAACAAGCAAAGAAACAACTAAACTGTTTTCGAATATTTGAACCGAAACAATTGCCTAT	420
VP2-SA11	TTATAGAGCTAATGGAGAAAGAGAGCTTCGTAATAGATGGTATTGGAAATTGAAACGAGA	480
PAS10_VP2	TTATAGAGCTAATGGAGAAAGAGAGCTTCGTAATAGATGGTATTGGAAATTGAAACGAGA	480
PAS8_VP2	TTATAGAGCTAATGGAGAAAGAGAGCTTCGTAATAGATGGTATTGGAAATTGAAACGAGA	480
PAS6_VP2	TTATAGAGCTAATGGAGAAAGAGAGCTTCGTAATAGATGGTATTGGAAATTGAAACGAGA	480
PAS2_VP2	TTATAGAGCTAATGGAGAAAGAGAGCTTCGTAATAGATGGTATTGGAAATTGAAACGAGA	480
VP2-SA11	TACTCTTCTGATGGAGATTATGATGTTAGAGAGTATTTTTTAAATTTATATGATCAAGT	540
PAS10_VP2	TACTCTTCTGATGGAGATTATGATGTTAGAGAGTATTTTTTAAATTTATATGATCAAGT	540
PAS8_VP2	TACTCTTCTGATGGAGATTATGATGTTAGAGAGTATTTTTTAAATTTATATGATCAAGT	540
PAS6_VP2	TACTCTTCTGATGGAGATTATGATGTTAGAGAGTATTTTTTAAATTTATATGATCAAGT	540
PAS2_VP2	TACTCTTCTGATGGAGATTATGATGTTAGAGAGTATTTTTTAAATTTATATGATCAAGT	540

VP2-SA11	ATTAATGGAAATGCCGGATTATCTATTACTTAAAGATATGGCTGTAGAGAATAAAAAATTC	600
PAS10_VP2	ATTAATGGAAATGCCGGATTATCTATTACTTAAAGATATGGCTGTAGAGAATAAAAAATTC	600
PAS8_VP2	ATTAATGGAAATGCCGGATTATCTATTACTTAAAGATATGGCTGTAGAGAATAAAAAATTC	600
PAS6_VP2	ATTAATGGAAATGCCGGATTATCTATTACTTAAAGATATGGCTGTAGAGAATAAAAAATTC	600
PAS2_VP2	ATTAATGGAAATGCCGGATTATCTATTACTTAAAGATATGRCTGTAGAGAATAAAAAATTC	600
VP2-SA11	AAGGGATGCTGGCAAAGTAGTTGATTTCTGAAACAGCCGCAATATGCGATGCTATTTTTCA	660
PAS10_VP2	AAGGGATGCTGGCAAAGTAGTTGATTTCTGAAACAGCCGCAATATGCGATGCTATTTTTCA	660
PAS8_VP2	AAGGGATGCTGGCAAAGTAGTTGATTTCTGAAACAGCCGCAATATGCGATGCTATTTTTCA	660
PAS6_VP2	AAGGGATGCTGGCAAAGTAGTTGATTTCTGAAACAGCCGCAATATGCGATGCTATTTTTCA	660
PAS2_VP2	AAGGGATGCTGGCAAAGTAGTTGATTTCTGAAACAGCCGCAATATGCGATGCTATTTTTCA	660
VP2-SA11	AGATGAAGAAACCGAAGGTGCAGTAAGAAGATTCATAGCTGAGATGAGACAACGAGTTCA	720
PAS10_VP2	AGATGAAGAAACCGAAGGTGCAGTAAGAAGATTCATAGCTGAGATGAGACAACGAGTTCA	720
PAS8_VP2	AGATGAAGAAACCGAAGGTGCAGTAAGAAGATTCATAGCTGAGATGAGACAACGAGTTCA	720
PAS6_VP2	AGATGAAGAAACCGAAGGTGCAGTAAGAAGATTCATAGCTGAGATGAGACAACGAGTTCA	720
PAS2_VP2	AGATGAAGAAACCGAAGGTGCAGTAAGAAGAWTCATAGCTGAGATGAGACAACGAGTTCA	720
VP2-SA11	AGCTGATCGAAATGTAGTCAATTTATCCATCTATATTTGCATCCAATTGACCATGCGTTTAA	780
PAS10_VP2	AGCTGATCGAAATGTAGTCAATTTATCCATCTATATTTGCATCCAATTGACCATGCGTTTAA	780
PAS8_VP2	AGCTGATCGAAATGTAGTCAATTTATCCATCTATATTTGCATCCAATTGACCATGCGTTTAA	780
PAS6_VP2	AGCTGATCGAAATGTAGTCAATTTATCCATCTATATTTGCATCCAATTGACCATGCGTTTAA	780
PAS2_VP2	AGCTGATCGAAATGTAGTCAATTTATCCATCTATATTTGCATCCAATTGACCATGCGTTTAA	780
VP2-SA11	CGAATACTTCTTACAACATCAGTTGGTAGAACCATTAAATAATGATATCATTTTCAATTA	840
PAS10_VP2	CGAATACTTCTTACAACATCAGTTGGTAGAACCATTAAATAATGATATCATTTTCAATTA	840
PAS8_VP2	CGAATACTTCTTACAACATCAGTTGGTAGAACCATTAAATAATGATATCATTTTCAATTA	840
PAS6_VP2	CGAATACTTCTTACAACATCAGTTGGTAGAACCATTAAATAATGATATCATTTTCAATTA	840
PAS2_VP2	CGAATACTTCTTACAACATCAGTTGGTAGAACCATTAAATAATGATATCATTTTCAATTA	840
VP2-SA11	CATACCAGAGAGAATAAGAAATGATGTCAACTATATATTTAAATATGGACAGGAATTTACC	900
PAS10_VP2	CATACCAGAGAGAATAAGAAATGATGTCAACTATATATTTAAATATGGACAGGAATTTACC	900
PAS8_VP2	CATACCAGAGAGAATAAGAAATGATGTCAACTATATATTTAAATATGGACAGGAATTTACC	900
PAS6_VP2	CATACCAGAGAGAATAAGAAATGATGTCAACTATATATTTAAATATGGACAGGAATTTACC	900
PAS2_VP2	CATACCAGAGAGAATAAGAAATGATGTCAACTATATATTTAAATATGGACAGGAATTTACC	900
VP2-SA11	GTCTACTGCTAGATATATCAGACCAAACCTTGCTACAAGATAGGTTAAATTTACATGATAA	960
PAS10_VP2	GTCTACTGCTAGATATATCAGACCAAACCTTGCTACAAGATAGGTTAAATTTACATGATAA	960
PAS8_VP2	GTCTACTGCTAGATATATCAGACCAAACCTTGCTACAAGATAGGTTAAATTTACATGATAA	960
PAS6_VP2	GTCTACTGCTAGATATATCAGACCAAACCTTGCTACAAGATAGGTTAAATTTACATGATAA	960
PAS2_VP2	GTCTACTGCTAGATATATCAGACCAAACCTTGCTACAAGATAGGTTAAATTTACATGATAA	960
VP2-SA11	TTTTGAGTCACTCTGGGATACTATAACTACATCTAATTATATTTTTAGCAAGATCTGTGGT	1020
PAS10_VP2	TTTTGAGTCACTCTGGGATACTATAACTACATCTAATTATATTTTTAGCAAGATCTGTGGT	1020
PAS8_VP2	TTTTGAGTCACTCTGGGATACTATAACTACATCTAATTATATTTTTAGCAAGATCTGTGGT	1020
PAS6_VP2	TTTTGAGTCACTCTGGGATACTATAACTACATCTAATTATATTTTTAGCAAGATCTGTGGT	1020
PAS2_VP2	TTTTGAGTCACTCTGGGATACTATAACTACATCTAATTATATTTTTAGCAAGATCTGTGGT	1020
VP2-SA11	GCCAGACCTAAAAGAATTAGTATCTACTGAGGCACAAATCCAGAAAAATGTCACAAGATTT	1080
PAS10_VP2	GCCAGACCTAAAAGAATTAGTATCTACTGAGGCACAAATCCAGAAAAATGTCACAAGATTT	1080
PAS8_VP2	GCCAGACCTAAAAGAATTAGTATCTACTGAGGCACAAATCCAGAAAAATGTCACAAGATTT	1080
PAS6_VP2	GCCAGACCTAAAAGAATTAGTATCTACTGAGGCACAAATCCAGAAAAATGTCACAAGATTT	1080
PAS2_VP2	GCCAGACCTAAAAGAATTAGTATCTACTGAGGCACAAATCCAGAAAAATGTCACAAGATTT	1080
VP2-SA11	GCAATTGGAAGCTTTGACAATACAATCAGAGACTCAGTTTTTAACAGGTATAAACTCACA	1140
PAS10_VP2	GCAATTGGAAGCTTTGACAATACAATCAGAGACTCAGTTTTTAACAGGTATAAACTCACA	1140
PAS8_VP2	GCAATTGGAAGCTTTGACAATACAATCAGAGACTCAGTTTTTAACAGGTATAAACTCACA	1140
PAS6_VP2	GCAATTGGAAGCTTTGACAATACAATCAGAGACTCAGTTTTTAACAGGTATAAACTCACA	1140
PAS2_VP2	GCAATTGGAAGCTTTGACAATACAATCAGAGACTCAGTTTTTAACAGGTATAAACTCACA	1140
VP2-SA11	AGCCGCTAATGATTGTTTTAAAACCTTTGATTGCTGCTATGTTGAGTCAGAGAACCATGTC	1200
PAS10_VP2	AGCCGCTAATGATTGTTTTAAAACCTTTGATTGCTGCTATGTTGAGTCAGAGAACCATGTC	1200
PAS8_VP2	AGCCGCTAATGATTGTTTTAAAACCTTTGATTGCTGCTATGTTGAGTCAGAGAACCATGTC	1200
PAS6_VP2	AGCCGCTAATGATTGTTTTAAAACCTTTGATTGCTGCTATGTTGAGTCAGAGAACCATGTC	1200
PAS2_VP2	AGCCGCTAATGATTGTTTTAAAACCTTTGATTGCTGCTATGTTGAGTCAGAGAACCATGTC	1200
VP2-SA11	ATTAGATTTTCGTAACGACAAATTACATGTCACCTTATTTTCAGGCATGTGGTTACTACTGT	1260
PAS10_VP2	ATTAGATTTTCGTAACGACAAATTACATGTCACCTTATTTTCAGGCATGTGGTTACTACTGT	1260
PAS8_VP2	ATTAGATTTTCGTAACGACAAATTACATGTCACCTTATTTTCAGGCATGTGGTTACTACTGT	1260
PAS6_VP2	ATTAGATTTTCGTAACGACAAATTACATGTCACCTTATTTTCAGGCATGTGGTTACTACTGT	1260

PAS2_VP2	ATTAGATTTTCGTAACGACAAATTACATGTCACCTTATTTTCAGGCATGTGGTTACTCACTGT	1260
VP2-SA11	GATTCCAAATGATATGTTTATAAGAGAATCATTAGTAGCATGTCAACTAGCCATAATAAAA	1320
PAS10_VP2	GATTCCAAATGATATGTTTATAAGAGAATCATTAGTAGCATGTCAACTAGCCATAATAAAA	1320
PAS8_VP2	GATTCCAAATGATATGTTTATAAGAGAATCATTAGTAGCATGTCAACTAGCCATAATAAAA	1320
PAS6_VP2	GATTCCAAATGATATGTTTATAAGAGAATCATTAGTAGCATGTCAACTAGCCATAATAAAA	1320
PAS2_VP2	GATTCCAAATGATATGTTTATAAGAGAATCATTAGTAGCATGTCAACTAGCCATAATAAAA	1320
VP2-SA11	TACCATTGTTTTATCCGGCATTCCGGAATGCAAAGAATGCATTATAGGAATGGTGATCCACA	1380
PAS10_VP2	TACCATTGTTTTATCCGGCATTCCGGAATGCAAAGAATGCATTATAGGAATGGTGATCCACA	1380
PAS8_VP2	TACCATTGTTTTATCCGGCATTCCGGAATGCAAAGAATGCATTATAGGAATGGTGATCCACA	1380
PAS6_VP2	TACCATTGTTTTATCCGGCATTCCGGAATGCAAAGAATGCATTATAGGAATGGTGATCCACA	1380
PAS2_VP2	TACCATTGTTTTATCCGGCATTCCGGAATGCAAAGAATGCATTATAGGAATGGTGATCCACA	1380
VP2-SA11	GACTCCCTTTCAAATTCAGAGCAACAGATTCAAATTTTCAGGTAGCTAATTGGTTACA	1440
PAS10_VP2	GACTCCCTTTCAAATTCAGAGCAACAGATTCAAATTTTCAGGTAGCTAATTGGTTACA	1440
PAS8_VP2	GACTCCCTTTCAAATTCAGAGCAACAGATTCAAATTTTCAGGTAGCTAATTGGTTACA	1440
PAS6_VP2	GACTCCCTTTCAAATTCAGAGCAACAGATTCAAATTTTCAGGTAGCTAATTGGTTACA	1440
PAS2_VP2	GACTCCCTTTCAAATTCAGAGCAACAGATTCAAATTTTCAGGTAGCTAATTGGTTACA	1440
VP2-SA11	TTTTGTTAATTATAATCAGTTTAGACAAGTAGTGATTTGATGGAGTGTAAATCAAGTCTT	1500
PAS10_VP2	TTTTGTTAATTATAATCAGTTTAGACAAGTAGTGATTTGATGGAGTGTAAATCAAGTCTT	1500
PAS8_VP2	TTTTGTTAATTATAATCAGTTTAGACAAGTAGTGATTTGATGGAGTGTAAATCAAGTCTT	1500
PAS6_VP2	TTTTGTTAATTATAATCAGTTTAGACAAGTAGTGATTTGATGGAGTGTAAATCAAGTCTT	1500
PAS2_VP2	TTTTGTTAATTATAATCAGTTTAGACAAGTAGTGATTTGATGGAGTGTAAATCAAGTCTT	1500
VP2-SA11	GAATGATAATATAAGAAATGGTCATGTAGTCAACCAATTAATGGAAGCTCTGATGCAATT	1560
PAS10_VP2	GAATGATAATATAAGAAATGGTCATGTAGTCAACCAATTAATGGAAGCTCTGATGCAATT	1560
PAS8_VP2	GAATGATAATATAAGAAATGGTCATGTAGTCAACCAATTAATGGAAGCTCTGATGCAATT	1560
PAS6_VP2	GAATGATAATATAAGAAATGGTCATGTAGTCAACCAATTAATGGAAGCTCTGATGCAATT	1560
PAS2_VP2	GAATGATAATATAAGAAATGGTCATGTAGTCAACCAATTAATGGAAGCTCTGATGCAATT	1560
VP2-SA11	ATCTAGACAACAGTTTCCACAATGCCAGTTGATTATAAAAGATCTATACAGAGAGGAAT	1620
PAS10_VP2	ATCTAGACAACAGTTTCCACAATGCCAGTTGATTATAAAAGATCTATACAGAGAGGAAT	1620
PAS8_VP2	ATCTAGACAACAGTTTCCACAATGCCAGTTGATTATAAAAGATCTATACAGAGAGGAAT	1620
PAS6_VP2	ATCTAGACAACAGTTTCCACAATGCCAGTTGATTATAAAAGATCTATACAGAGAGGAAT	1620
PAS2_VP2	ATCTAGACAACAGTTTCCACAATGCCAGTTGATTATAAAAGATCTATACAGAGAGGAAT	1620
VP2-SA11	TTTGCTGCTTTCTAACAGACTTGGTCAGCTTGTTCGATTTAACAAGATTGTTATCATACAA	1680
PAS10_VP2	TTTGCTGCTTTCTAACAGACTTGGTCAGCTTGTTCGATTTAACAAGATTGTTATCATACAA	1680
PAS8_VP2	TTTGCTGCTTTCTAACAGACTTGGTCAGCTTGTTCGATTTAACAAGATTGTTATCATACAA	1680
PAS6_VP2	TTTGCTGCTTTCTAACAGACTTGGTCAGCTTGTTCGATTTAACAAGATTGTTATCATACAA	1680
PAS2_VP2	TTTGCTGCTTTCTAACAGACTTGGTCAGCTTGTTCGATTTAACAAGATTGTTATCATACAA	1680
VP2-SA11	TTATGAGACATTAATGGCATGCATAACAATGAATATGCAGCATGTTCAAACATTAACAAC	1740
PAS10_VP2	TTATGAGACATTAATGGCATGCATAACAATGAATATGCAGCATGTTCAAACATTAACAAC	1740
PAS8_VP2	TTATGAGACATTAATGGCATGCATAACAATGAATATGCAGCATGTTCAAACATTAACAAC	1740
PAS6_VP2	TTATGAGACATTAATGGCATGCATAACAATGAATATGCAGCATGTTCAAACATTAACAAC	1740
PAS2_VP2	TTATGAGACATTAATGGCATGCATAACAATGAATATGCAGCATGTTCAAACATTAACAAC	1740
VP2-SA11	TGAAAAATTGCAATTAACATCAGTAACATCATTATGTATGCTAATTGGAAATGCTACGGT	1800
PAS10_VP2	TGAAAAATTGCAATTAACATCAGTAACATCATTATGTATGCTAATTGGAAATGCTACGGT	1800
PAS8_VP2	TGAAAAATTGCAATTAACATCAGTAACATCATTATGTATGCTAATTGGAAATGCTACGGT	1800
PAS6_VP2	TGAAAAATTGCAATTAACATCAGTAACATCATTATGTATGCTAATTGGAAATGCTACGGT	1800
PAS2_VP2	TGAAAAATTGCAATTAACATCAGTAACATCATTATGTATGCTAATTGGAAATGCTACGGT	1800
VP2-SA11	TATACCGAGTCCGCAAACATTGTTCCATTACTATAATGTGAATGTCAATTTTCATTCAA	1860
PAS10_VP2	TATACCGAGTCCGCAAACATTGTTCCATTACTATAATGTGAATGTCAATTTTCATTCAA	1860
PAS8_VP2	TATACCGAGTCCGCAAACATTGTTCCATTACTATAATGTGAATGTCAATTTTCATTCAA	1860
PAS6_VP2	TATACCGAGTCCGCAAACATTGTTCCATTACTATAATGTGAATGTCAATTTTCATTCAA	1860
PAS2_VP2	TATACCGAGTCCGCAAACATTGTTCCATTACTATAATGTGAATGTCAATTTTCATTCAA	1860
VP2-SA11	TTATAATGAAAGAATTAATGACGCAGTTGCAATTTATAACTGCGGCAAATAGATTAAATTT	1920
PAS10_VP2	TTATAATGAAAGAATTAATGACGCAGTTGCAATTTATAACTGCGGCAAATAGATTAAATTT	1920
PAS8_VP2	TTATAATGAAAGAATTAATGACGCAGTTGCAATTTATAACTGCGGCAAATAGATTAAATTT	1920
PAS6_VP2	TTATAATGAAAGAATTAATGACGCAGTTGCAATTTATAACTGCGGCAAATAGATTAAATTT	1920
PAS2_VP2	TTATAATGAAAGAATTAATGACGCAGTTGCAATTTATAACTGCGGCAAATAGATTAAATTT	1920
VP2-SA11	ATATCAAAGAAAAATGAAATCAATAGTTGAGGACTTCTGAAAAGATTACAGATATTTGA	1980
PAS10_VP2	ATATCAAAGAAAAATGAAATCAATAGTTGAGGACTTCTGAAAAGATTACAGATATTTGA	1980

PAS8_VP2	ATATCAAAAGAAAATGAAATCAATAGTTGAGGACTTCTGAAAAGATTACAGATATTTGA	1980
PAS6_VP2	ATATCAAAAGAAAATGAAATCAATAGTTGAGGACTTCTGAAAAGATTACAGATATTTGA	1980
PAS2_VP2	ATATCAAAAGAAAATGAAATCAATAGTTGAGGACTTCTGAAAAGATTACAGATATTTGA	1980
VP2-SA11	TGTTGCGAGAGTACCAGATGACCAAATGTATAGATTGAGAGATAGATTAAGACTATTACC	2040
PAS10_VP2	TGTTGCGAGAGTACCAGATGACCAAATGTATAGATTGAGAGATAGATTAAGACTATTACC	2040
PAS8_VP2	TGTTGCGAGAGTACCAGATGACCAAATGTATAGATTGAGAGATAGATTAAGACTATTACC	2040
PAS6_VP2	TGTTGCGAGAGTACCAGATGACCAAATGTATAGATTGAGAGATAGATTAAGACTATTACC	2040
PAS2_VP2	TGTTGCGAGAGTACCAGATGACCAAATGTATAGATTGAGAGATAGATTAAGACTATTACC	2040
VP2-SA11	AGTTGAAATAAGAAGATTAGATATTTTAATTTGATAGCAATGAATATGGAACAGATTGA	2100
PAS10_VP2	AGTTGAAATAAGAAGATTAGATATTTTAATTTGATAGCAATGAATATGGAACAGATTGA	2100
PAS8_VP2	AGTTGAAATAAGAAGATTAGATATTTTAATTTGATAGCAATGAATATGGAACAGATTGA	2100
PAS6_VP2	AGTTGAAATAAGAAGATTAGATATTTTAATTTGATAGCAATGAATATGGAACAGATTGA	2100
PAS2_VP2	AGTTGAAATAAGAAGATTAGATATTTTAATTTGATAGCAATGAATATGGAACAGATTGA	2100
VP2-SA11	ACGTGCATCAGATAAAAATTGCACAAGGAGTTATAATAGCATACCGAGATATGCAGTTAGA	2160
PAS10_VP2	ACGTGCATCAGATAAAAATTGCACAAGGAGTTATAATAGCATACCGAGATATGCAGTTAGA	2160
PAS8_VP2	ACGTGCATCAGATAAAAATTGCACAAGGAGTTATAATAGCATACCGAGATATGCAGTTAGA	2160
PAS6_VP2	ACGTGCATCAGATAAAAATTGCACAAGGAGTTATAATAGCATACCGAGATATGCAGTTAGA	2160
PAS2_VP2	ACGTGCATCAGATAAAAATTGCACAAGGAGTTATAATAGCATACCGAGATATGCAGTTAGA	2160
VP2-SA11	ACGAGATGAGATGTATGGTTACGTCAATATTGCCAGAACTTGGACGGATTTCAACAAAT	2220
PAS10_VP2	ACGAGATGAGATGTATGGTTACGTCAATATTGCCAGAACTTGGACGGATTTCAACAAAT	2220
PAS8_VP2	ACGAGATGAGATGTATGGTTACGTCAATATTGCCAGAACTTGGACGGATTTCAACAAAT	2220
PAS6_VP2	ACGAGATGAGATGTATGGTTACGTCAATATTGCCAGAACTTGGACGGATTTCAACAAAT	2220
PAS2_VP2	ACGAGATGAGATGTATGGTTACGTCAATATTGCCAGAACTTGGACGGATTTCAACAAAT	2220
VP2-SA11	AAATCTTGAAGAAATTGATGAGATCAGGAGATTATGCTCAAATTACTAACATGCTACTTAA	2280
PAS10_VP2	AAATCTTGAAGAAATTGATGAGATCAGGAGATTATGCTCAAATTACTAACATGCTACTTAA	2280
PAS8_VP2	AAATCTTGAAGAAATTGATGAGATCAGGAGATTATGCTCAAATTACTAACATGCTACTTAA	2280
PAS6_VP2	AAATCTTGAAGAAATTGATGAGATCAGGAGATTATGCTCAAATTACTAACATGCTACTTAA	2280
PAS2_VP2	AAATCTTGAAGAAATTGATGAGATCAGGAGATTATGCTCAAATTACTAACATGCTACTTAA	2280
VP2-SA11	TAATCAACCAGTAGCTTTAGTTGGAGCGCTACCATTTATAACGGATTCATCAGTGATTTTC	2340
PAS10_VP2	TAATCAACCAGTAGCTTTAGTTGGAGCGCTACCATTTATAACGGATTCATCAGTGATTTTC	2340
PAS8_VP2	TAATCAACCAGTAGCTTTAGTTGGAGCGCTACCATTTATAACGGATTCATCAGTGATTTTC	2340
PAS6_VP2	TAATCAACCAGTAGCTTTAGTTGGAGCGCTACCATTTATAACGGATTCATCAGTGATTTTC	2340
PAS2_VP2	TAATCAACCAGTAGCTTTAGTTGGAGCGCTACCATTTATAACGGATTCATCAGTGATTTTC	2340
VP2-SA11	GTTAATAGCTAAACTAGATGCAACCGTTTTTGCACAGATTGTCAAACCTTAGAAAGGTCGA	2400
PAS10_VP2	GTTAATAGCTAAACTAGATGCAACCGTTTTTGCACAGATTGTCAAACCTTAGAAAGGTCGA	2400
PAS8_VP2	GTTAATAGCTAAACTAGATGCAACCGTTTTTGCACAGATTGTCAAACCTTAGAAAGGTCGA	2400
PAS6_VP2	GTTAATAGCTAAACTAGATGCAACCGTTTTTGCACAGATTGTCAAACCTTAGAAAGGTCGA	2400
PAS2_VP2	GTTAATAGCTAAACTAGATGCAACCGTTTTTGCACAGATTGTCAAACCTTAGAAAGGTCGA	2400
VP2-SA11	CACGTTAAAACCCATCCTATATAAGATAAATTCAGATTCTAATGACTTTTATTTGGTGGC	2460
PAS10_VP2	CACGTTAAAACCCATCCTATATAAGATAAATTCAGATTCTAATGACTTTTATTTGGTGGC	2460
PAS8_VP2	CACGTTAAAACCCATCCTATATAAGATAAATTCAGATTCTAATGACTTTTATTTGGTGGC	2460
PAS6_VP2	CACGTTAAAACCCATCCTATATAAGATAAATTCAGATTCTAATGACTTTTATTTGGTGGC	2460
PAS2_VP2	CACGTTAAAACCCATCCTATATAAGATAAATTCAGATTCTAATGACTTTTATTTGGTGGC	2460
VP2-SA11	TAATTATGATTGGATTCCCTACATCTACTACAAAAGTGATAAAACAAGTTCACAACAATT	2520
PAS10_VP2	TAATTATGATTGGATTCCCTACATCTACTACAAAAGTGATAAAACAAGTTCACAACAATT	2520
PAS8_VP2	TAATTATGATTGGATTCCCTACATCTACTACAAAAGTGATAAAACAAGTTCACAACAATT	2520
PAS6_VP2	TAATTATGATTGGATTCCCTACATCTACTACAAAAGTGATAAAACAAGTTCACAACAATT	2520
PAS2_VP2	TAATTATGATTGGATTCCCTACATCTACTACAAAAGTGATAAAACAAGTTCACAACAATT	2520
VP2-SA11	TGATTTTAGAGCGTCAATGCATATGTTAACGTC TAACCTAACATTTACCGTATATTCAGA	2580
PAS10_VP2	TGATTTTAGAGCGTCAATGCATATGTTAACGTC TAACCTAACATTTACCGTATATTCAGA	2580
PAS8_VP2	TGATTTTAGAGCGTCAATGCATATGTTAACGTC TAACCTAACATTTACCGTATATTCAGA	2580
PAS6_VP2	TGATTTTAGAGCGTCAATGCATATGTTAACGTC TAACCTAACATTTACCGTATATTCAGA	2580
PAS2_VP2	TGATTTTAGAGCGTCAATGCATATGTTAACGTC TAACCTAACATTTACCGTATATTCAGA	2580
VP2-SA11	TTTGCTTGCGTTCGTTTCAGCTGATACTGTTGAACCAATTAATGCTGTTGCTTTTGATAA	2640
PAS10_VP2	TTTGCTTGCGTTCGTTTCAGCTGATACTGTTGAACCAATTAATGCTGTTGCTTTTGATAA	2640
PAS8_VP2	TTTGCTTGCGTTCGTTTCAGCTGATACTGTTGAACCAATTAATGCTGTTGCTTTTGATAA	2640
PAS6_VP2	TTTGCTTGCGTTCGTTTCAGCTGATACTGTTGAACCAATTAATGCTGTTGCTTTTGATAA	2640
PAS2_VP2	TTTGCTTGCGTTCGTTTCAGCTGATACTGTTGAACCAATTAATGCTGTTGCTTTTGATAA	2640

PAS10_VP3	TAGATTATCTAACAGAGTATTTAGGGATAAGTTATCCCATCATTATGAAAGAACATAA	660
PAS8_VP3	TAGATTATCTAACAGAGTATTTAGGGATAAGTTATCCCATCATTATGAAAGAACATAA	660
PAS6_VP3	TAGATTATCTAACAGAGTATTTAGGGATAAGTTATCCCATCATTATGAAAGAACATAA	660
PAS2_VP3	TAGATTATCTAACAGAGTATTTAGGGATAAGTTATCCCATCATTATGAAAGAACATAA	660
VP3-SA11	GAATGTAGTGAACGTTGGTCCGCGTAATGAATCTATGTTTACATTTTAAATTATCCAAC	720
PAS10_VP3	GAATGTAGTGAACGTTGGTCCGCGTAATGAATCTATGTTTACATTTTAAATTATCCAAC	720
PAS8_VP3	GAATGTAGTGAACGTTGGTCCGCGTAATGAATCTATGTTTACATTTTAAATTATCCAAC	720
PAS6_VP3	GAATGTAGTGAACGTTGGTCCGCGTAATGAATCTATGTTTACATTTTAAATTATCCAAC	720
PAS2_VP3	GAATGTAGTGAACGTTGGTCCGCGTAATGAATCTATGTTTACATTTTAAATTATCCAAC	720
VP3-SA11	TATAAAACAATTTTCAAATGGTGCGTATTTAGTAAAAGATACTATAAAATTTAAACAAGA	780
PAS10_VP3	TATAAAACAATTTTCAAATGGTGCGTATTTAGTAAAAGATACTATAAAATTTAAACAAGA	780
PAS8_VP3	TATAAAACAATTTTCAAATGGTGCGTATTTAGTAAAAGATACTATAAAATTTAAACAAGA	780
PAS6_VP3	TATAAAACAATTTTCAAATGGTGCGTATTTAGTAAAAGATACTATAAAATTTAAACAAGA	780
PAS2_VP3	TATAAAACAATTTTCAAATGGTGCGTATTTAGTAAAAGATACTATAAAATTTAAACAAGA	780
VP3-SA11	ACGATGGTTAGGTAAGGATATCTCAGTTTGATATGGTCAGTATAAAAATATGCTGAA	840
PAS10_VP3	ACGATGGTTAGGTAAGGATATCTCAGTTTGATATGGTCAGTATAAAAATATGCTGAA	840
PAS8_VP3	ACGATGGTTAGGTAAGGATATCTCAGTTTGATATGGTCAGTATAAAAATATGCTGAA	840
PAS6_VP3	ACGATGGTTAGGTAAGGATATCTCAGTTTGATATGGTCAGTATAAAAATATGCTGAA	840
PAS2_VP3	ACGATGGTTAGGTAAGGATATCTCRGTTTGATATGGTCAGTATAAAAATATGCTGAA	840
VP3-SA11	TGTTCTTACAGCAATTTATTATTACTATAATTTATATAAAAAGTAAACCAATTATATATAT	900
PAS10_VP3	TGTTCTTACAGCAATTTATTATTACTATAATTTATATAAAAAGTAAACCAATTATATATAT	900
PAS8_VP3	TGTTCTTACAGCAATTTATTATTACTATAATTTATATAAAAAGTAAACCAATTATATATAT	900
PAS6_VP3	TGTTCTTACAGCAATTTATTATTACTATAATTTATATAAAAAGTAAACCAATTATATATAT	900
PAS2_VP3	TGTTCTTACAGCAATTTATTATTACTATAATTTATATAAAAAGTAAACCAATTATATATAT	900
VP3-SA11	GATCGGATCTGCTCCATCTTATTGGATATATGACGTTAGGCATTATCCGATTTTTTCTT	960
PAS10_VP3	GATCGGATCTGCTCCATCTTATTGGATATATGACGTTAGGCATTATCCGATTTTTTCTT	960
PAS8_VP3	GATCGGATCTGCTCCATCTTATTGGATATATGACGTTAGGCATTATCCGATTTTTTCTT	960
PAS6_VP3	GATCGGATCTGCTCCATCTTATTGGATATATGACGTTAGGCATTATCCGATTTTTTCTT	960
PAS2_VP3	GATCGGATCTGCTCCATCTTATTGGATATATGACGTTAGGCATTATCCGATTTTTTCTT	960
VP3-SA11	TGAAACTTGGGATCCATTGGACACACCATATTCATCAATCCATCACAAGAATTATTTTT	1020
PAS10_VP3	TGAAACTTGGGATCCATTGGACACACCATATTCATCAATCCATCACAAGAATTATTTTT	1020
PAS8_VP3	TGAAACTTGGGATCCATTGGACACACCATATTCATCAATCCATCACAAGAATTATTTTT	1020
PAS6_VP3	TGAAACTTGGGATCCATTGGACACACCATATTCATCAATCCATCACAAGAATTATTTTT	1020
PAS2_VP3	TGAAACTTGGGATCCATTGGACACACCATATTCATCAATCCATCACAAGAATTATTTTT	1020
VP3-SA11	TATAAATGATGTGAAGAACTGAAGGATAACTCAATATTGTATATTGATATAAGAACCGA	1080
PAS10_VP3	TATAAATGATGTGAAGAACTGAAGGATAACTCAATATTGTATATTGATATAAGAACCGA	1080
PAS8_VP3	TATAAATGATGTGAAGAACTGAAGGATAACTCAATATTGTATATTGATATAAGAACCGA	1080
PAS6_VP3	TATAAATGATGTGAAGAACTGAAGGATAACTCAATATTGTATATTGATATAAGAACCGA	1080
PAS2_VP3	TATAAATGATGTGAAGAACTGAAGGATAACTCAATATTGTATATTGATATAAGAACCGA	1080
VP3-SA11	TAGGGCAATGCTGATTGGAAAAATGGAGAAAGACAGTAGAAGAACAACTATTAATAA	1140
PAS10_VP3	TAGGGCAATGCTGATTGGAAAAATGGAGAAAGACAGTAGAAGAACAACTATTAATAA	1140
PAS8_VP3	TAGGGCAATGCTGATTGGAAAAATGGAGAAAGACAGTAGAAGAACAACTATTAATAA	1140
PAS6_VP3	TAGGGCAATGCTGATTGGAAAAATGGAGAAAGACAGTAGAAGAACAACTATTAATAA	1140
PAS2_VP3	TAGGGCAATGCTGATTGGAAAAATGGAGAAAGACAGTAGAAGAACAACTATTAATAA	1140
VP3-SA11	TTTGGACATAGCTTATGAATATTTACGAACGGGTAAAGCGAAGGTGTGTTGTGTTAAGAT	1200
PAS10_VP3	TTTGGACATAGCTTATGAATATTTACGAACGGGTAAAGCGAAGGTGTGTTGTGTTAAGAT	1200
PAS8_VP3	TTTGGACATAGCTTATGAATATTTACGAACGGGTAAAGCGAAGGTGTGTTGTGTTAAGAT	1200
PAS6_VP3	TTTGGACATAGCTTATGAATATTTACGAACGGGTAAAGCGAAGGTGTGTTGTGTTAAGAT	1200
PAS2_VP3	TTTGGACATAGCTTATGAATATTTACGAACGGGTAAAGCGAAGGTGTGTTGTGTTAAGAT	1200
VP3-SA11	GACAGCTATGGATTTGGAAGTCCCAATTTTCAGCTAAATTTACTGCACCACCAACTACGGA	1260
PAS10_VP3	GACAGCTATGGATTTGGAAGTCCCAATTTTCAGCTAAATTTACTGCACCACCAACTACGGA	1260
PAS8_VP3	GACAGCTATGGATTTGGAAGTCCCAATTTTCAGCTAAATTTACTGCACCACCAACTACGGA	1260
PAS6_VP3	GACAGCTATGGATTTGGAAGTCCCAATTTTCAGCTAAATTTACTGCACCACCAACTACGGA	1260
PAS2_VP3	GACAGCTATGGATTTGGAAGTCCCAATTTTCAGCTAAATTTACTGCACCACCAACTACGGA	1260
VP3-SA11	AATAAGATCAGAATTTTATTTATTACTAGATACTTGGGATTTAACTAACATTAGGAGGTT	1320
PAS10_VP3	AATAAGATCAGAATTTTATTTATTACTAGATACTTGGGATTTAACTAACATTAGGAGGTT	1320
PAS8_VP3	AATAAGATCAGAATTTTATTTATTACTAGATACTTGGGATTTAACTAACATTAGGAGGTT	1320
PAS6_VP3	AATAAGATCAGAATTTTATTTATTACTAGATACTTGGGATTTAACTAACATTAGGAGGTT	1320
PAS2_VP3	AATAAGATCAGAATTTTATTTATTACTAGATACTTGGGATTTAACTAACATTAGGAGGTT	1320

VP3-SA11	CATTCCCTAAAGGCGTGTATATTCATTTATAAACAATATAATAACTGAAAATGTGTTTAT	1380
PAS10_VP3	CATTCCCTAAAGGCGTGTATATTCATTTATAAACAATATAATAACTGAAAATGTGTTTAT	1380
PAS8_VP3	CATTCCCTAAAGGCGTGTATATTCATTTATAAACAATATAATAACTGAAAATGTGTTTAT	1380
PAS6_VP3	CATTCCCTAAAGGCGTGTATATTCATTTATAAACAATATAATAACTGAAAATGTGTTTAT	1380
PAS2_VP3	CATTCCCTAAAGGCGTGTATATTCATTTATAAACAATATAATAACTGAAAATGTGTTTAT	1380
VP3-SA11	TCAACAACCATTTAAAGTAAAAGTACTGAATGATAGTTATATTGTAGCGTTATATGCATT	1440
PAS10_VP3	TCAACAACCATTTAAAGTAAAAGTACTGAATGATAGTTATATTGTAGCGTTATATGCATT	1440
PAS8_VP3	TCAACAACCATTTAAAGTAAAAGTACTGAATGATAGTTATATTGTAGCGTTATATGCATT	1440
PAS6_VP3	TCAACAACCATTTAAAGTAAAAGTACTGAATGATAGTTATATTGTAGCGTTATATGCATT	1440
PAS2_VP3	TCAACAACCATTTAAAGTAAAAGTACTGAATGATAGTTATATTGTAGCGTTATATGCATT	1440
VP3-SA11	ATCAAATGATTTTAATAATAGATCAGAAGTAATTAATTAATTAATAATCAGAAACAATC	1500
PAS10_VP3	ATCAAATGATTTTAATAATAGATCAGAAGTAATTAATTAATTAATAATCAGAAACAATC	1500
PAS8_VP3	ATCAAATGATTTTAATAATAGATCAGAAGTAATTAATTAATTAATAATCAGAAACAATC	1500
PAS6_VP3	ATCAAATGATTTTAATAATAGATCAGAAGTAATTAATTAATTAATAATCAGAAACAATC	1500
PAS2_VP3	ATCAAATGATTTTAATAATAGATCAGAAGTAATTAATTAATTAATAATCAGAAACAATC	1500
VP3-SA11	TCTAATAACTGTTAGAATAAATAATACGTTTAAAGGATGAACCAAAAAGTTGGGTTCAAAAA	1560
PAS10_VP3	TCTAATAACTGTTAGAATAAATAATACGTTTAAAGGATGAACCAAAAAGTTGGGTTCAAAAA	1560
PAS8_VP3	TCTAATAACTGTTAGAATAAATAATACGTTTAAAGGATGAACCAAAAAGTTGGGTTCAAAAA	1560
PAS6_VP3	TCTAATAACTGTTAGAATAAATAATACGTTTAAAGGATGAACCAAAAAGTTGGGTTCAAAAA	1560
PAS2_VP3	TCTAATAACTGTTAGAATAAATAATACGTTTAAAGGATGAACCAAAAAGTTGGGTTCAAAAA	1560
VP3-SA11	TATCTATGATTGGACCTTTCTTCCAACCGACTTTGATACCAAAGAAGCTATAATTACTTC	1620
PAS10_VP3	TATCTATGATTGGACCTTTCTTCCAACCGACTTTGATACCAAAGAAGCTATAATTACTTC	1620
PAS8_VP3	TATCTATGATTGGACCTTTCTTCCAACCGACTTTGATACCAAAGAAGCTATAATTACTTC	1620
PAS6_VP3	TATCTATGATTGGACCTTTCTTCCAACCGACTTTGATACCAAAGAAGCTATAATTACTTC	1620
PAS2_VP3	TATCTATGATTGGACCTTTCTTCCAACCGACTTTGATACCAAAGAAGCTATAATTACTTC	1620
VP3-SA11	ATACGACGGTTGTTTAGGACTCTTTGGTTTGTCTATATCGTTAGCATCAAACCAACAGG	1680
PAS10_VP3	ATACGACGGTTGTTTAGGACTCTTTGGTTTGTCTATATCGTTAGCATCAAACCAACAGG	1680
PAS8_VP3	ATACGACGGTTGTTTAGGACTCTTTGGTTTGTCTATATCGTTAGCATCAAACCAACAGG	1680
PAS6_VP3	ATACGACGGTTGTTTAGGACTCTTTGGTTTGTCTATATCGTTAGCATCAAACCAACAGG	1680
PAS2_VP3	ATACGACGGTTGTTTAGGACTCTTTGGTTTGTCTATATCGTTAGCATCAAACCAACAGG	1680
VP3-SA11	GAATAATCATTATTCATTTTAAAGTGGTACAGATAAGTATTATAAATTTGGATCAATTTGC	1740
PAS10_VP3	GAATAATCATTATTCATTTTAAAGTGGTACAGATAAGTATTATAAATTTGGATCAATTTGC	1740
PAS8_VP3	GAATAATCATTATTCATTTTAAAGTGGTACAGATAAGTATTATAAATTTGGATCAATTTGC	1740
PAS6_VP3	GAATAATCATTATTCATTTTAAAGTGGTACAGATAAGTATTATAAATTTGGATCAATTTGC	1740
PAS2_VP3	GAATAATCATTATTCATTTTAAAGTGGTACAGATAAGTATTATAAATTTGGATCAATTTGC	1740
VP3-SA11	TAATCACACCAGTATATCGAGAAGATCACACCAAATTAGGTTTTCGGAATCTGCTACTTC	1800
PAS10_VP3	TAATCACACCAGTATATCGAGAAGATCACACCAAATTAGGTTTTCGGAATCTGCTACTTC	1800
PAS8_VP3	TAATCACACCAGTATATCGAGAAGATCACACCAAATTAGGTTTTCGGAATCTGCTACTTC	1800
PAS6_VP3	TAATCACACCAGTATATCGAGAAGATCACACCAAATTAGGTTTTCGGAATCTGCTACTTC	1800
PAS2_VP3	TAATCACACCAGTATATCGAGAAGATSACACCAAATTAGGTTTTCGGAATCTGCTACTTC	1800
VP3-SA11	ATATTCAGGTTATATATTTAGAGATTTGTCCAATAATAATTTTAATCTAATTGGTACTAA	1860
PAS10_VP3	ATATTCAGGTTATATATTTAGAGATTTGTCCAATAATAATTTTAATCTAATTGGTACTAA	1860
PAS8_VP3	ATATTCAGGTTATATATTTAGAGATTTGTCCAATAATAATTTTAATCTAATTGGTACTAA	1860
PAS6_VP3	ATATTCAGGTTATATATTTAGAGATTTGTCCAATAATAATTTTAATCTAATTGGTACTAA	1860
PAS2_VP3	ATATTCAGGTTATATATTTAGAGATTTGTCCAATAATAATTTTAATCTAATTGGTACTAA	1860
VP3-SA11	TATAGAGAATTCAGTATCAGGTCATGTATATAATGCTTTAATTTATTATAGATATAATTA	1920
PAS10_VP3	TATAGAGAATTCAGTATCAGGTCATGTATATAATGCTTTAATTTATTATAGATATAATTA	1920
PAS8_VP3	TATAGAGAATTCAGTATCAGGTCATGTATATAATGCTTTAATTTATTATAGATATAATTA	1920
PAS6_VP3	TATAGAGAATTCAGTATCAGGTCATGTATATAATGCTTTAATTTATTATAGATATAATTA	1920
PAS2_VP3	TATAGAGAATTCAGTATCAGGTCATGTATATAATGCTTTAATTTATTATAGATATAATTA	1920
VP3-SA11	TTCATTTGATCTTAAACGCTGGATTTATTTACATTCATAGATAAAAGTTGATATAGAAGG	1980
PAS10_VP3	TTCATTTGATCTTAAACGCTGGATTTATTTACATTCATAGATAAAAGTTGATATAGAAGG	1980
PAS8_VP3	TTCATTTGATCTTAAACGCTGGATTTATTTACATTCATAGATAAAAGTTGATATAGAAGG	1980
PAS6_VP3	TTCATTTGATCTTAAACGCTGGATTTATTTACATTCATAGATAAAAGTTGATATAGAAGG	1980
PAS2_VP3	TTCATTTGATCTTAAACGCTGGATTTATTTACATTCATAGATAAAAGTTGATATAGARGG	1980
VP3-SA11	AGGAAAGTATTATGAACACGCACCAATAGAATTAATTTATGCATGTAGATCAGCAAAAAGA	2040
PAS10_VP3	AGGAAAGTATTATGAACACGCACCAATAGAATTAATTTATGCATGTAGATCAGCAAAAAGA	2040
PAS8_VP3	AGGAAAGTATTATGAACACGCACCAATAGAATTAATTTATGCATGTAGATCAGCAAAAAGA	2040

PAS6_VP3	AGGAAAGTATTATGAACACGCACCAATAGAATTAATTTATGCATGTAGATCAGCAAAAAGA	2040
PAS2_VP3	AGGAAAGTATTATGAACACGCACCAATAGAATTAATTTATGCATGTAGATCAGCAAAAAGA	2040
VP3-SA11	ATTTGCTACATTGCAGGATGACTTAACTGTATTGAGATATTCAAACGAAATAGAGAATTA	2100
PAS10_VP3	ATTTGCTACATTGCAGGATGACTTAACTGTATTGAGATATTCAAACGAAATAGAGAATTA	2100
PAS8_VP3	ATTTGCTACATTGCAGGATGACTTAACTGTATTGAGATATTCAAACGAAATAGAGAATTA	2100
PAS6_VP3	ATTTGCTACATTGCAGGATGACTTAACTGTATTGAGATATTCAAACGAAATAGAGAATTA	2100
PAS2_VP3	ATTTGCTACATTGCAGGATGACTTAACTGTATTGAGATATTCAAACGAAATAGAGAATTA	2100
VP3-SA11	TATTAATACAGTATATAGTATAACATACGCTGATGATCCGAATTACTTTATCGGAATACA	2160
PAS10_VP3	TATTAATACAGTATATAGTATAACATACGCTGATGATCCGAATTACTTTATCGGAATACA	2160
PAS8_VP3	TATTAATACAGTATATAGTATAACATACGCTGATGATCCGAATTACTTTATCGGAATACA	2160
PAS6_VP3	TATTAATACAGTATATAGTATAACATACGCTGATGATCCGAATTACTTTATCGGAATACA	2160
PAS2_VP3	TATTAATACAGTATATAGTATAACATACGCTGATGATCCGAATTACTTTATCGGAATACA	2160
VP3-SA11	ATTTAGAAATATACCATATAAAATATGATGTTAAAATACCGCATTTAACCTTCGGAGTATT	2220
PAS10_VP3	ATTTAGAAATATACCATATAAAATATGATGTTAAAATACCGCATTTAACCTTCGGAGTATT	2220
PAS8_VP3	ATTTAGAAATATACCATATAAAATATGATGTTAAAATACCGCATTTAACCTTCGGAGTATT	2220
PAS6_VP3	ATTTAGAAATATACCATATAAAATATGATGTTAAAATACCGCATTTAACCTTCGGAGTATT	2220
PAS2_VP3	ATTTAGAAATATACCATATAAAATATGATGTTAAAATACCGCATTTAACCTTCGGAGTATT	2220
VP3-SA11	ACATATTTCTGATAACATGGTGCCAGACGTGATTGACATACTAAAGATAATGAAGAATGA	2280
PAS10_VP3	ACATATTTCTGATAACATGGTGCCAGACGTGATTGACATACTAAAGATAATGAAGAATGA	2280
PAS8_VP3	ACATATTTCTGATAACATGGTGCCAGACGTGATTGACATACTAAAGATAATGAAGAATGA	2280
PAS6_VP3	ACATATTTCTGATAACATGGTGCCAGACGTGATTGACATACTAAAGATAATGAAGAATGA	2280
PAS2_VP3	ACATATTTCTGATAACATGGTGCCAGACGTGATTGACATACTAAAGATAATGAAGAATGA	2280
VP3-SA11	ATTATTTAAAATGGATATTACGACCAGTTATACATATATGTTATCAGATGGAATCTACGT	2340
PAS10_VP3	ATTATTTAAAATGGATATTACGACCAGTTATACATATATGTTATCAGATGGAATCTACGT	2340
PAS8_VP3	ATTATTTAAAATGGATATTACGACCAGTTATACATATATGTTATCAGATGGAATCTACGT	2340
PAS6_VP3	ATTATTTAAAATGGATATTACGACCAGTTATACATATATGTTATCAGATGGAATCTACGT	2340
PAS2_VP3	ATTATTTAAAATGGATATTACGACCAGTTATACATATATGTTATCAGATGGAATCTACGT	2340
VP3-SA11	AGCAAATGTTAGTGGAGTATTATCTACATACTTTAAAATCTATAACGTATTTTATAAAAA	2400
PAS10_VP3	AGCAAATGTTAGTGGAGTATTATCTACATACTTTAAAATCTATAACGTATTTTATAAAAA	2400
PAS8_VP3	AGCAAATGTTAGTGGAGTATTATCTACATACTTTAAAATCTATAACGTATTTTATAAAAA	2400
PAS6_VP3	AGCAAATGTTAGTGGAGTATTATCTACATACTTTAAAATCTATAACGTATTTTATAAAAA	2400
PAS2_VP3	AGCAAATGTTAGTGGAGTATTATCTACATACTTTAAAATCTATAACGTATTTTATAAAAA	2400
VP3-SA11	TCAAATAACTTTTGGCCAATCCAGAATGTTTATTCGGCACATAACATTAAGCTTCAATAA	2460
PAS10_VP3	TCAAATAACTTTTGGCCAATCCAGAATGTTTATTCGGCACATAACATTAAGCTTCAATAA	2460
PAS8_VP3	TCAAATAACTTTTGGCCAATCCAGAATGTTTATTCGGCACATAACATTAAGCTTCAATAA	2460
PAS6_VP3	TCAAATAACTTTTGGCCAATCCAGAATGTTTATTCGGCACATAACATTAAGCTTCAATAA	2460
PAS2_VP3	TCAAATAACTTTTGGCCAATCCAGAATGTTTATTCGGCACATAACATTAAGCTTCAATAA	2460
VP3-SA11	CATGAGAACAGTAAGGATAGAGACTACTAAATTACAAATTAATCCATTTATTTAAGAAA	2520
PAS10_VP3	CATGAGAACAGTAAGGATAGAGACTACTAAATTACAAATTAATCCATTTATTTAAGAAA	2520
PAS8_VP3	CATGAGAACAGTAAGGATAGAGACTACTAAATTACAAATTAATCCATTTATTTAAGAAA	2520
PAS6_VP3	CATGAGAACAGTAAGGATAGAGACTACTAAATTACAAATTAATCCATTTATTTAAGAAA	2520
PAS2_VP3	CATGAGAACAGTAAGGATAGAGACTACTAAATTACAAATTAATCCATTTATTTAAGAAA	2520
VP3-SA11	GATTAAGGGTGATACAGTGTTTGATATGGTTGAGTGAGCTAAAAACTTAACACACTAGTC	2580
PAS10_VP3	GATTAAGGGTGATACAGTGTTTGATATGGTTGAGTGAGCTAAAAACTTAACACACTAGTC	2580
PAS8_VP3	GATTAAGGGTGATACAGTGTTTGATATGGTTGAGTGAGCTAAAAACTTAACACACTAGTC	2580
PAS6_VP3	GATTAAGGGTGATACAGTGTTTGATATGGTTGAGTGAGCTAAAAACTTAACACACTAGTC	2580
PAS2_VP3	GATTAAGGGTGATACAGTGTTTGATATGGTTGAGTGAGCTAAAAACTTAACACACTAGTC	2580
VP3-SA11	ATGATGTGACC 2591	
PAS10_VP3	ATGATGTGACC 2591	
PAS8_VP3	ATGATGTGACC 2591	
PAS6_VP3	ATGATGTGACC 2591	
PAS2_VP3	ATGATGTGACC 2591	

GENOME SEGMENT 4 :

VP4-BAP-GREEN	GGCTATAAAATGGCTTCGCTCATTTATAGACAATTGCTCACGAATTCCTTATACAGTAGAT	60
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GGCTATAAAATGGCTTCGCTCATTTATAGACAATTGCTCACGAATTCCTTATACAGTAGAT	60
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GGCTATAAAATGGCTTCGCTCATTTATAGACAATTGCTCACGAATTCCTTATACAGTAGAT	60
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GGCTATAAAATGGCTTCGCTCATTTATAGACAATTGCTCACGAATTCCTTATACAGTAGAT	60

PAS2_VP4_BAP NNNNNNNNNNNGCTTCGCTCATTTATAGMCAATTGCTCACGAATTCTTATACAGTAGAT 60

VP4-BAP-GREEN TTATCCGATGAGATACAAGAGATTGGATCAACTAAATCACAAAATGTCACAATTAATCCT 120
PAS10_VP4_BAP TTATCCGATGAGATACAAGAGATTGGATCAACTAAATCACAAAATGTCACAATTAATCCT 120
PAS8_VP4_BAP TTATCCGATGAGATACAAGAGATTGGATCAACTAAATCACAAAATGTCACAATTAATCCT 120
PAS6_VP4_BAP TTATCCGATGAGATACAAGAGATTGGATCAACTAAATCACAAAATGTCACAATTAATCCT 120
PAS2_VP4_BAP TTATCCGATGAGATACAAGAGATTGGATCAACTAAATCACAAAATGTCACAATTAATCCT 120

VP4-BAP-GREEN GGACCATTTGCGCAAACAGGTTATGCTCCAGTTAACTGGGGACCTGGAGAAATTAATGAT 180
PAS10_VP4_BAP GGACCATTTGCGCAAACAGGTTATGCTCCAGTTAACTGGGGACCTGGAGAAATTAATGAT 180
PAS8_VP4_BAP GGACCATTTGCGCAAACAGGTTATGCTCCAGTTAACTGGGGACCTGGAGAAATTAATGAT 180
PAS6_VP4_BAP GGACCATTTGCGCAAACAGGTTATGCTCCAGTTAACTGGGGACCTGGAGAAATTAATGAT 180
PAS2_VP4_BAP GGACCATTTGCGCAAACAGGTTATGCTCCAGTTAACTGGGGACCTGGAGAAATTAATGAT 180

VP4-BAP-GREEN TCTACGACAGTTGAACCATTGCTGGATGGGCCTTATCAACCAATGACATTCAATCCACCA 240
PAS10_VP4_BAP TCTACGACAGTTGAACCATTGCTGGATGGGCCTTATCAACCAATGACATTCAATCCACCA 240
PAS8_VP4_BAP TCTACGACAGTTGAACCATTGCTGGATGGGCCTTATCAACCAATGACATTCAATCCACCA 240
PAS6_VP4_BAP TCTACGACAGTTGAACCATTGCTGGATGGGCCTTATCAACCAATGACATTCAATCCACCA 240
PAS2_VP4_BAP TCTACGACAGTTGAACCATTGCTGGATGGGCCTTATCAACCAATGACATTCAATCCACCA 240

VP4-BAP-GREEN GTCGATTATTGGATGTTACTGGCTCCAACGACACCTGGCGTAATTGTTGAAGGTACCAAC 300
PAS10_VP4_BAP GTCGATTATTGGATGTTACTGGCTCCAACGACACCTGGCGTAATTGTTGAAGGTACCAAC 300
PAS8_VP4_BAP GTCGATTATTGGATGTTACTGGCTCCAACGACACCTGGCGTAATTGTTGAAGGTACCAAC 300
PAS6_VP4_BAP GTCGATTATTGGATGTTACTGGCTCCAACGACACCTGGCGTAATTGTTGAAGGTACCAAC 300
PAS2_VP4_BAP GTCGATTATTGGATGTTACTGGCTCCAACGACACCTGGCGTAATTGTTGAAGGTACCAAC 300

VP4-BAP-GREEN AACACCGACAGTGGCTGGCCACCATTCTGATCGAGCCCAACGTGCAGAGTGAAAATCGC 360
PAS10_VP4_BAP AACACCGACAGTGGCTGGCCACCATTCTGATCGAGCCCAACGTGCAGAGTGAAAATCGC 360
PAS8_VP4_BAP AACACCGACAGTGGCTGGCCACCATTCTGATCGAGCCCAACGTGCAGAGTGAAAATCGC 360
PAS6_VP4_BAP AACACCGACAGTGGCTGGCCACCATTCTGATCGAGCCCAACGTGCAGAGTGAAAATCGC 360
PAS2_VP4_BAP AACACCGACAGTGGCTGGCCACCATTCTGATCGAGCCCAACGTGCAGAGTGAAAATCGC 360

VP4-BAP-GREEN ACTTATACCATCTTTGGAATCCAGGAGCAGCTGACAGTGAGTAACACTTCACAGGACCAG 420
PAS10_VP4_BAP ACTTATACCATCTTTGGDATCCAGGAGCAGCTGACAGTGAGTAACACTTCACAGGACCAG 420
PAS8_VP4_BAP ACTTATACCATCTTTGGRATCCAGGAGCAGCTGACAGTGAGTAACACTTCACAGGACCAG 420
PAS6_VP4_BAP ACTTATACCATCTTTGGRATCCAGGAGCAGCTGACAGTGAGTAACACTTCACAGGACCAG 420
PAS2_VP4_BAP ACTTATACCATCTTTGGAATCCAGGAGCAGCTGACAGTGAGTAACACTTCACAGGACCAG 420

VP4-BAP-GREEN TGGAAGTTCATCGACGTCGTCAAACCACATCCGGAGGACTGAATGATATCTTTGAAGCA 480
PAS10_VP4_BAP TGGAAGTTCATCGACGTCGTCAAACCACATCCGGAGGACTGAATGATATCTTTGAAGCA 480
PAS8_VP4_BAP TGGAAGTTCATCGACGTCGTCAAACCACATCCGGAGGACTGAATGATATCTTTGAAGCA 480
PAS6_VP4_BAP TGGAAGTTCATCGACGTCGTCAAACCACATCCGGAGGACTGAATGATATCTTTGAAGCA 480
PAS2_VP4_BAP TGGAAGTTCATCGACGTCGTCAAACCACATCCGGAGGACTGAATGATATCTTTGAAGCA 480

VP4-BAP-GREEN CAGAAGATTGAGTGGCAGCAAGGGGCTAGCGCAAACGGCTCCATTGGGCAGTATGGATCC 540
PAS10_VP4_BAP CAGAAGATTGAGTGGCAGCAAGGGGCTAGCGCAAACGGCTCCATTGGGCAGTATGGATCC 540
PAS8_VP4_BAP CAGAAGATTGAGTGGCAGCAAGGGGCTAGCGCAAACGGCTCCATTGGGCAGTATGGATCC 540
PAS6_VP4_BAP CAGAAGATTGAGTGGCAGCAAGGGGCTAGCGCAAACGGCTCCATTGGGCAGTATGGATCC 540
PAS2_VP4_BAP CAGAAGATTGAGTGGCAGCAAGGGGCTAGCGCAAACGGCTCCATTGGGCAGTATGGATCC 540

VP4-BAP-GREEN TTTACTATCCAGTCCGAAATTATATGCAGTTATGAAGCATAATGAAAAATTATATACATAT 600
PAS10_VP4_BAP TTTACTATCCAGTCCGAAATTATATGCAGTTATGAAGCATAATGAAAAATTATATACATAT 600
PAS8_VP4_BAP TTTACTATCCAGTCCGAAATTATATGCAGTTATGAAGCATAATGAAAAATTATATACATAT 600
PAS6_VP4_BAP TTTACTATCCAGTCCGAAATTATATGCAGTTATGAAGCATAATGAAAAATTATATACATAT 600
PAS2_VP4_BAP TTTACTATCCAGTCCGAAATTATATGCAGTTATGAAGCATAATGAAAAATTATATACATAT 600

VP4-BAP-GREEN GAAGGACAGACACCTAACGCTAGGACAGCACATTATTCAACAACGAATTATGATTCGTGT 660
PAS10_VP4_BAP GAAGGACAGACACCTAACGCTAGGACAGCACATTATTCAACAACGAATTATGATTCGTGT 660
PAS8_VP4_BAP GAAGGACAGACACCTAACGCTAGGACAGCACATTATTCAACAACGAATTATGATTCGTGT 660
PAS6_VP4_BAP GAAGGACAGACACCTAACGCTAGGACAGCACATTATTCAACAACGAATTATGATTCGTGT 660
PAS2_VP4_BAP GAAGGACAGACACCTAACGCTAGGACAGCACATTATTCAACAACGAATTATGATTCGTGT 660

VP4-BAP-GREEN AACATGACTGCTTTTTGTGACTTTTATATAATTCCTAGATCTGAAGAGTCTAAATGTACG 720
PAS10_VP4_BAP AACATGACTGCTTTTTGTGACTTTTATATAATTCCTAGATCTGAAGAGTCTAAATGTACG 720
PAS8_VP4_BAP AACATGACTGCTTTTTGTGACTTTTATATAATTCCTAGATCTGAAGAGTCTAAATGTACG 720
PAS6_VP4_BAP AACATGACTGCTTTTTGTGACTTTTATATAATTCCTAGATCTGAAGAGTCTAAATGTACG 720
PAS2_VP4_BAP AACATGACTGCTTTTTGTGACTTTTATATAATTCCTAGATCTGAAGAGTCTAAATGTACG 720

VP4-BAP-GREEN GAATACATTAATAATGGATTACCACCAATACAAAATACTAGAAATGTTGTACCATTATCG 780
PAS10_VP4_BAP GAATACATTAATAATGGATTACCACCAATACAAAATACTAGAAATGTTGTACCATTATCG 780

PAS8_VP4_BAP	GAATACATTAATAATGGATTACCACCAATACAAAATACTAGAAATGTTGTACCATTATCG	780
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GAATACATTAATAATGGATTACCACCAATACAAAATACTAGAAATGTTGTACCATTATCG	780
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GAATACATTAATAATGGATTACCACCAATACAAAATACTAGAAATGTTGTACCATTATCG	780
VP4-BAP-GREEN	TTGACTGCTAGAGATGTAATACACTATAGAGCTCAAGCTAATGAAGATATTGTGATATCC	840
PAS10_VP4_BAP	TTGACTGCTAGAGATGTAATACACTATAGAGCTCAAGCTAATGAAGATATTGTGATATCC	840
PAS8_VP4_BAP	TTGACTGCTAGAGATGTAATACACTATAGAGCTCAAGCTAATGAAGATATTGTGATATCC	840
PAS6_VP4_BAP	TTGACTGCTAGAGATGTAATACACTATAGAGCTCAAGCTAATGAAGATATTGTGATATCC	840
PAS2_VP4_BAP	WTGACTGCTAGAGATGTAATACACTATAGAGCTCAAGCTAATGAAGATATTGTGATATCC	840
VP4-BAP-GREEN	AAGACATCATTATGGAAAGAAATGCAATATAATAGAGATATAACTATTAGATTTAAATTT	900
PAS10_VP4_BAP	AAGACATCATTATGGAAAGAAATGCAATATAATAGAGATATAACTATTAGATTTAAATTT	900
PAS8_VP4_BAP	AAGACATCATTATGGAAAGAAATGCAATATAATAGAGATATAACTATTAGATTTAAATTT	900
PAS6_VP4_BAP	AAGACATCATTATGGAAAGAAATGCAATATAATAGAGATATAACTATTAGATTTAAATTT	900
PAS2_VP4_BAP	AAGACATCATTATGGAAAGAAATGCAATATAATAGAGATATAACTATTAGATTTAAATTT	900
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GCAAATACAATTATAAAATCAGGAGGGCTGGGATATAAGTGGTCAGAAATATCATTTAAG	960
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GCAAATACAATTATAAAATCAGGAGGGCTGGGATATAAGTGGTCAGAAATATCATTTAAG	960
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GCAAATACAATTATAAAATCAGGAGGGCTGGGATATAAGTGGTCAGAAATATCATTTAAG	960
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GCAAATACAATTATAAAATCAGGAGGGCTGGGATATAAGTGGTCAGAAATATCATTTAAG	960
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GCAAATACAATTATAAAATCAGGAGGGCTGGGATATAAGTGGTCAGAAATATCATTTAAG	960
VP4-BAP-GREEN	CCAGCGAATTATCAATACACATATACTCGTGATGGTGAAGAAGTTACCGCACATACTACT	1020
PAS10_VP4_BAP	CCAGCGAATTATCAATACACATATACTCGTGATGGTGAAGAAGTTACCGCACATACTACT	1020
PAS8_VP4_BAP	CCAGCGAATTATCAATACACATATACTCGTGATGGTGAAGAAGTTACCGCACATACTACT	1020
PAS6_VP4_BAP	CCAGCGAATTATCAATACACATATACTCGTGATGGTGAAGAAGTTACCGCACATACTACT	1020
PAS2_VP4_BAP	CCAGCGAATTATCAATACACATATACTCGTGATGGTGAAGAAGTTACCGCACATACTACT	1020
VP4-BAP-GREEN	TGTTTCAGTGAATGGCGTTAATGACTTCAGTTTTAATGGAGGATATTTACCAACTGATTTT	1080
PAS10_VP4_BAP	TGTTTCAGTGAATGGCGTTAATGACTTCAGTTTTAATGGAGGATATTTACCAACTGATTTT	1080
PAS8_VP4_BAP	TGTTTCAGTGAATGGCGTTAATGACTTCAGTTTTAATGGAGGATATTTACCAACTGATTTT	1080
PAS6_VP4_BAP	TGTTTCAGTGAATGGCGTTAATGACTTCAGTTTTAATGGAGGATATTTACCAACTGATTTT	1080
PAS2_VP4_BAP	TGTTTCAGTGAATGGCGTTAATGACTTCAGTTTTAATGGAGGATATTTACCAACTGATTTT	1080
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GTTGTATCTAAATTTGAAGTAATTAAGAGAAATTCATACGCTATATCGATTACTGGGAT	1140
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GTTGTATCTAAATTTGAAGTAATTAAGAGAAATTCATACGCTATATCGATTACTGGGAT	1140
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GTTGTATCTAAATTTGAAGTAATTAAGAGAAATTCATACGCTATATCGATTACTGGGAT	1140
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GTTGTATCTAAATTTGAAGTAATTAAGAGAAATTCATACGCTATATCGATTACTGGGAT	1140
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GTTGTATCTAAATTTGAAGTAATTAAGAGAAATTCATACGCTATATCGATTACTGGGAT	1140
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GATTCACAAGCATTTTCGTAACGTGGTGTATGTCCGATCGTTAGCAGCAAACCTTGAATTCA	1200
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GATTCACAAGCATTTTCGTAACGTGGTGTATGTCCGATCGTTAGCAGCAAACCTTGAATTCA	1200
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GATTCACAAGCATTTTCGTAACGTGGTGTATGTCCGATCGTTAGCAGCAAACCTTGAATTCA	1200
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GATTCACAAGCATTTTCGTAACGTGGTGTATGTCCGATCGTTAGCAGCAAACCTTGAATTCA	1200
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GATTCACAAGCATTTTCGTAACGTGGTGTATGTCCGATCGTTAGCAGCAAACCTTGAATTCA	1200
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GTTATGTGTACTGGAGGCAGCTATAATTTTAGTCTACCAGTTGGACAATGGCCTGTTTTA	1260
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GTTATGTGTACTGGAGGCAGCTATAATTTTAGTCTACCAGTTGGACAATGGCCTGTTTTA	1260
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GTTATGTGTACTGGAGGCAGCTATAATTTTAGTCTACCAGTTGGACAATGGCCTGTTTTA	1260
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GTTATGTGTACTGGAGGCAGCTATAATTTTAGTCTACCAGTTGGACAATGGCCTGTTTTA	1260
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GTTATGTGTACTGGAGGCAGCTATAATTTTAGTCTACCAGTTGGACAATGGCCTGTTTTA	1260
VP4-BAP-GREEN	ACTGGGGGAGCAGTTTCTTTACATTCAGCTGGTGTAACTATCTACTCAATTTACAGAT	1320
PAS10_VP4_BAP	ACTGGGGGAGCAGTTTCTTTACATTCAGCTGGTGTAACTATCTACTCAATTTACAGAT	1320
PAS8_VP4_BAP	ACTGGGGGAGCAGTTTCTTTACATTCAGCTGGTGTAACTATCTACTCAATTTACAGAT	1320
PAS6_VP4_BAP	ACTGGGGGAGCAGTTTCTTTACATTCAGCTGGTGTAACTATCTACTCAATTTACAGAT	1320
PAS2_VP4_BAP	ACTGGGGGAGCAGTTTCTTTACATTCAGCTGGTGTAACTATCTACTCAATTTACAGAT	1320
VP4-BAP-GREEN	TTCGTATCATTAATTCATTAAGATTTAGATTTAGACTAGCTGTCGAAGAACCACACTTT	1380
PAS10_VP4_BAP	TTCGTATCATTAATTCATTAAGATTTAGATTTAGACTAGCTGTCGAAGAACCACACTTT	1380
PAS8_VP4_BAP	TTCGTATCATTAATTCATTAAGATTTAGATTTAGACTAGCTGTCGAAGAACCACACTTT	1380
PAS6_VP4_BAP	TTCGTATCATTAATTCATTAAGATTTAGATTTAGACTAGCTGTCGAAGAACCACACTTT	1380
PAS2_VP4_BAP	TTCGTATCATTAATTCATTAAGATTTAGATTTAGACTAGCTGTCGAAGAACCACACTTT	1380
VP4-BAP-GREEN	AAACTGACTAGAACTAGATTAGATAGATTGTATGGTCTGCCTGCTGCAGATCCAAATAAT	1440
PAS10_VP4_BAP	AAACTGACTAGAACTAGATTAGATAGATTGTATGGTCTGCCTGCTGCAGATCCAAATAAT	1440
PAS8_VP4_BAP	AAACTGACTAGAACTAGATTAGATAGATTGTATGGTCTGCCTGCTGCAGATCCAAATAAT	1440
PAS6_VP4_BAP	AAACTGACTAGAACTAGATTAGATAGATTGTATGGTCTGCCTGCTGCAGATCCAAATAAT	1440
PAS2_VP4_BAP	AAACTGACTAGAACTAGATTAGATAGATTGTATGGTCTGCCTGCTGCAGATCCAAATAAT	1440

VP4-BAP-GREEN	GGTAAAGAATATTTATGAAATTGCTGGACGATTTTCACTTATATCATTAGTGCCATCAAAT	1500
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GGTAAAGAATATTTATGAAATTGCTGGACGATTTTCACTTATATCATTAGTGCCATCAAAT	1500
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GGTAAAGAATATTTATGAAATTGCTGGACGATTTTCACTTATATCATTAGTGCCATCAAAT	1500
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GGTAAAGAATATTTATGAAATTGCTGGACGATTTTCACTTATATCATTAGTGCCATCAAAT	1500
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GGTAAAGAATATTTATGAAATTGCTGGACGATTTTCACTTATATCATTAGTGCCATCAAAT	1500
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GATGACTATCAGACTCCTATAGCAAACCTCAGTTACTGTACGACAAGATTTAGAAAGGCAG	1560
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GATGACTATCAGACTCCTATAGCAAACCTCAGTTACTGTACGACAAGATTTAGAAAGGCAG	1560
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GATGACTATCAGACTCCTATAGCAAACCTCAGTTACTGTACGACAAGATTTAGAAAGGCAG	1560
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GATGACTATCAGACTCCTATAGCAAACCTCAGTTACTGTACGACAAGATTTAGAAAGGCAG	1560
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GATGACTATCAGACTCCTATAGCAAACCTCAGTTACTGTACGACAAGATTTAGAAAGGCAG	1560
VP4-BAP-GREEN	TTAGGAGAACTAAGAGAAGAGTTTAAACGCTTTGTCTCAAGAAATTGCAATGTGCGAGTTA	1620
PAS10_VP4_BAP	TTAGGAGAACTAAGAGAAGAGTTTAAACGCTTTGTCTCAAGAAATTGCAATGTGCGAGTTA	1620
PAS8_VP4_BAP	TTAGGAGAACTAAGAGAAGAGTTTAAACGCTTTGTCTCAAGAAATTGCAATGTGCGAGTTA	1620
PAS6_VP4_BAP	TTAGGAGAACTAAGAGAAGAGTTTAAACGCTTTGTCTCAAGAAATTGCAATGTGCGAGTTA	1620
PAS2_VP4_BAP	TTAGGAGAACTAAGAGAAGAGTTTAAACGCTTTGTCTCAAGAAATTGCAATGTGCGAGTTA	1620
VP4-BAP-GREEN	ATCGATTTAGCGCTTCTACCATTAGATATGTTTCTCAATGTTTTCTGGCATTAAAAGTACT	1680
PAS10_VP4_BAP	ATCGATTTAGCGCTTCTACCATTAGATATGTTTCTCAATGTTTTCTGGCATTAAAAGTACT	1680
PAS8_VP4_BAP	ATCGATTTAGCGCTTCTACCATTAGATATGTTTCTCAATGTTTTCTGGCATTAAAAGTACT	1680
PAS6_VP4_BAP	ATCGATTTAGCGCTTCTACCATTAGATATGTTTCTCAATGTTTTCTGGCATTAAAAGTACT	1680
PAS2_VP4_BAP	ATCGATTTAGCGCTTCTACCATTAGATATGTTTCTCAATGTTTTCTGGCATTAAAAGTACT	1680
VP4-BAP-GREEN	ATTGATGCTGCAAAATCAATGGCTACTAATGTTATGAAAAAATTCAAAAAGTCAGGATTA	1740
PAS10_VP4_BAP	ATTGATGCTGCAAAATCAATGGCTACTAATGTTATGAAAAAATTCAAAAAGTCAGGATTA	1740
PAS8_VP4_BAP	ATTGATGCTGCAAAATCAATGGCTACTAATGTTATGAAAAAATTCAAAAAGTCAGGATTA	1740
PAS6_VP4_BAP	ATTGATGCTGCAAAATCAATGGCTACTAATGTTATGAAAAAATTCAAAAAGTCAGGATTA	1740
PAS2_VP4_BAP	ATTGATGCTGCAAAATCAATGGCTACTAATGTTATGAAAAAATTCAAAAAGTCAGGATTA	1740
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GCGAATTCAGTTTCAACACTGACAGATTCTTTATCAGACGCAGCATCATCAATATCAAGA	1800
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GCGAATTCAGTTTCAACACTGACAGATTCTTTATCAGACGCAGCATCATCAATATCAAGA	1800
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GCGAATTCAGTTTCAACACTGACAGATTCTTTATCAGACGCAGCATCATCAATATCAAGA	1800
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GCGAATTCAGTTTCAACACTGACAGATTCTTTATCAGACGCAGCATCATCAATATCAAGA	1800
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GCGAATTCAGTTTCAACACTGACAGATTCTTTATCAGACGCAGCATCATCAATATCAAGA	1800
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GGTTCATCTATACGTTTCGATTGGATCTTCAGCATCAGCATGGACGGATGTATCAACACAA	1860
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GGTTCATCTATACGTTTCGATTGGATCTTCAGCATCAGCATGGACGGATGTATCAACACAA	1860
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GGTTCATCTATACGTTTCGATTGGATCTTCAGCATCAGCATGGACGGATGTATCAACACAA	1860
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GGTTCATCTATACGTTTCGATTGGATCTTCAGCATCAGCATGGACGGATGTATCAACACAA	1860
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GGTTCATCTATACGTTTCGATTGGATCTTCAGCATCAGCATGGACGGATGTATCAACACAA	1860
VP4-BAP-GREEN	ATAACTGATATATCGTCATCAGTAAGTTTCAGTTTCGACACAAACGTCAACTATCAGTAGA	1920
PAS10_VP4_BAP	ATAACTGATATATCGTCATCAGTAAGTTTCAGTTTCGACACAAACGTCAACTATCAGTAGA	1920
PAS8_VP4_BAP	ATAACTGATATATCGTCATCAGTAAGTTTCAGTTTCGACACAAACGTCAACTATCAGTAGA	1920
PAS6_VP4_BAP	ATAACTGATATATCGTCATCAGTAAGTTTCAGTTTCGACACAAACGTCAACTATCAGTAGA	1920
PAS2_VP4_BAP	ATAACTGATATATCGTCATCAGTAAGTTTCAGTTTCGACACAAACGTCAACTATCAGTAGA	1920
VP4-BAP-GREEN	AGATTGAGACTAAAGGAAATGGCAACACAAACTGAGGGTATGAATTTTGATGATATATCA	1980
PAS10_VP4_BAP	AGATTGAGACTAAAGGAAATGGCAACACAAACTGAGGGTATGAATTTTGATGATATATCA	1980
PAS8_VP4_BAP	AGATTGAGACTAAAGGAAATGGCAACACAAACTGAGGGTATGAATTTTGATGATATATCA	1980
PAS6_VP4_BAP	AGATTGAGACTAAAGGAAATGGCAACACAAACTGAGGGTATGAATTTTGATGATATATCA	1980
PAS2_VP4_BAP	AGATTGAGACTAAAGGAAATGGCAACACAAACTGAGGGTATGAATTTTGATGATATATCA	1980
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GCGGCTGTTTTGAAGACTAAGATAGATAAATCGACTCAAATATCACCAAACACAATACCT	2040
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GCGGCTGTTTTGAAGACTAAGATAGATAAATCGACTCAAATATCACCAAACACAATACCT	2040
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GCGGCTGTTTTGAAGACTAAGATAGATAAATCGACTCAAATATCACCAAACACAATACCT	2040
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GCGGCTGTTTTGAAGACTAAGATAGATAAATCGACTCAAATATCACCAAACACAATACCT	2040
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GCGGCTGTTTTGAAGACTAAGATAGATAAATCGACTCAAATATCACCAAACACAATACCT	2040
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GACATTGTTACTGAAGCATCGGAAAAATTCATACCAAATAGGGCTTACC CGGTTATAAAC	2100
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GACATTGTTACTGAAGCATCGGAAAAATTCATACCAAATAGGGCTTACC CGGTTATAAAC	2100
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GACATTGTTACTGAAGCATCGGAAAAATTCATACCAAATAGGGCTTACC CGGTTATAAAC	2100
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GACATTGTTACTGAAGCATCGGAAAAATTCATACCAAATAGGGCTTACC CGGTTATAAAC	2100
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GACATTGTTACTGAAGCATCGGAAAAATTCATACCAAATAGGGCTTACC CGGTTATAAAC	2100
VP4-BAP-GREEN	AACGATGATGTGTTTGAAGCTGGAATTGATGGGAAATTTTTGCTTATAAAGTGGATACA	2160
PAS10_VP4_BAP	AACGATGATGTGTTTGAAGCTGGAATTGATGGGAAATTTTTGCTTATAAAGTGGATACA	2160
PAS8_VP4_BAP	AACGATGATGTGTTTGAAGCTGGAATTGATGGGAAATTTTTGCTTATAAAGTGGATACA	2160
PAS6_VP4_BAP	AACGATGATGTGTTTGAAGCTGGAATTGATGGGAAATTTTTGCTTATAAAGTGGATACA	2160

PAS2_VP4_BAP	AACGATGATGTGTTTGAAGCTGGAATTGATGGGAAATTTTTGCTTATAAAGTGGATACA	2160
VP4-BAP-GREEN	TTTGAGGAAATACCATTTGATGTACAAAAATTCGCTGACTTAGTTACAGATTCTCCAGTA	2220
PAS10_VP4_BAP	TTTGAGGAAATACCATTTGATGTACAAAAATTCGCTGACTTAGTTACAGATTCTCCAGTA	2220
PAS8_VP4_BAP	TTTGAGGAAATACCATTTGATGTACAAAAATTCGCTGACTTAGTTACAGATTCTCCAGTA	2220
PAS6_VP4_BAP	TTTGAGGAAATACCATTTGATGTACAAAAATTCGCTGACTTAGTTACAGATTCTCCAGTA	2220
PAS2_VP4_BAP	TTTGAGGAAATACCATTTGATGTACAAAAATTCGCTGACTTAGTTACAGATTCTCCAGTA	2220
VP4-BAP-GREEN	ATATCCGCTATAATTGATTTTAAAAACACTTAAAAATTTGAACGATAATTACGGCATTACT	2280
PAS10_VP4_BAP	ATATCCGCTATAATTGATTTTAAAAACACTTAAAAATTTGAACGATAATTACGGCATTACT	2280
PAS8_VP4_BAP	ATATCCGCTATAATTGATTTTAAAAACACTTAAAAATTTGAACGATAATTACGGCATTACT	2280
PAS6_VP4_BAP	ATATCCGCTATAATTGATTTTAAAAACACTTAAAAATTTGAACGATAATTACGGCATTACT	2280
PAS2_VP4_BAP	ATATCCGCTATAATTGATTTTAAAAACACTTAAAAATTTGAACGATAATTACGGCATTACT	2280
VP4-BAP-GREEN	AAGCAACAAGCATTTAATCTTTTAAAGATCTGACCCAAGAGTTTTACGTGAATTCATTAAT	2340
PAS10_VP4_BAP	AAGCAACAAGCATTTAATCTTTTAAAGATCTGACCCAAGAGTTTTACGTGAATTCATTAAT	2340
PAS8_VP4_BAP	AAGCAACAAGCATTTAATCTTTTAAAGATCTGACCCAAGAGTTTTACGTGAATTCATTAAT	2340
PAS6_VP4_BAP	AAGCAACAAGCATTTAATCTTTTAAAGATCTGACCCAAGAGTTTTACGTGAATTCATTAAT	2340
PAS2_VP4_BAP	AAGCAACAAGCATTTAATCTTTTAAAGATCTGACCCAAGAGTTTTACGTGAATTCATTAAT	2340
VP4-BAP-GREEN	CAGGACAATCCTATAATTAGAAATAGAATTGAACAACACTGATTATGCAATGCAGGTTGTGA	2400
PAS10_VP4_BAP	CAGGACAATCCTATAATTAGAAATAGAATTGAACAACACTGATTATGCAATGCAGGTTGTGA	2400
PAS8_VP4_BAP	CAGGACAATCCTATAATTAGAAATAGAATTGAACAACACTGATTATGCAATGCAGGTTGTGA	2400
PAS6_VP4_BAP	CAGGACAATCCTATAATTAGAAATAGAATTGAACAACACTGATTATGCAATGCAGGTTGTGA	2400
PAS2_VP4_BAP	CAGGACAATCCTATAATTAGAAATAGAATTGAACAACACTGATTATGCAATGCAGGTTGTGA	2400
VP4-BAP-GREEN	GTAATTTCTAGAGGATGTGACC	2422
PAS10_VP4_BAP	GTAATTTCTAGAGGATGTGACC	2422
PAS8_VP4_BAP	GTAATTTCTAGAGGATGTGACC	2422
PAS6_VP4_BAP	GTAATTTCTAGAGGATGTGACC	2422
PAS2_VP4_BAP	GTAATTTCTAGAGGATGNNNNN	2422

GENOME SEGMENT 5:

NSP1-SA11	GGCTTTTTTTTTGAAAAGTCTTGTGTTAGCCATGGCTACTTTTTAAAGATGCATGCTTTCAT	60
PAS10_NSP1	GGCTTTTTTTTTGAAAAGTCTTGTGTTAGCCATGGCTACTTTTTAAAGATGCATGCTTTCAT	60
PAS8_NSP1	GGCTTTTTTTTTGAAAAGTCTTGTGTTAGCCATGGCTACTTTTTAAAGATGCATGCTTTCAT	60
PAS6_NSP1	GGCTTTTTTTTTGAAAAGTCTTGTGTTAGCCATGGCTACTTTTTAAAGATGCATGCTTTCAT	60
PAS2_NSP1	NNNNNNNNNNAAAAAGYCTTGTGTTAGCCATGGCTACTTTTTAAAGATGCATGCTTTCAT	60
NSP1-SA11	TATCGTAGATTAAGTCTTTAAATCGGAGATTATGCAACATTGGTGCAAATTCATTTGG	120
PAS10_NSP1	TATCGTAGATTAAGTCTTTAAATCGGAGATTATGCAACATTGGTGCAAATTCATTTGG	120
PAS8_NSP1	TATCGTAGATTAAGTCTTTAAATCGGAGATTATGCAACATTGGTGCAAATTCATTTGG	120
PAS6_NSP1	TATCGTAGATTAAGTCTTTAAATCGGAGATTATGCAACATTGGTGCAAATTCATTTGG	120
PAS2_NSP1	TATCGTAGATTAAGTCTTTAAATCGGAGATTATGCAACATTGGTGCAAATTCATTTGG	120
NSP1-SA11	ATGCCAGTTCCTGATGCGAAAAATTAAGGGGTGGTGTTTAGAATGTTGTCAAATAGCTGAT	180
PAS10_NSP1	ATGCCAGTTCCTGATGCGAAAAATTAAGGGGTGGTGTTTAGAATGTTGTCAAATAGCTGAT	180
PAS8_NSP1	ATGCCAGTTCCTGATGCGAAAAATTAAGGGGTGGTGTTTAGAATGTTGTCAAATAGCTGAT	180
PAS6_NSP1	ATGCCAGTTCCTGATGCGAAAAATTAAGGGGTGGTGTTTAGAATGTTGTCAAATAGCTGAT	180
PAS2_NSP1	ATGCCAGTTCCTGATGCGAAAAATTAAGGGGTGGTGTTTAGAATGTTGTCAAATAGCTGAT	180
NSP1-SA11	TTAACCATTGTTATGGTTGCTCATTGCCGCATGTTTGCAAATGGTGTGTTTCAGAACAGA	240
PAS10_NSP1	TTAACCATTGTTATGGTTGCTCATTGCCGCATGTTTGCAAATGGTGTGTTTCAGAACAGA	240
PAS8_NSP1	TTAACCATTGTTATGGTTGCTCATTGCCGCATGTTTGCAAATGGTGTGTTTCAGAACAGA	240
PAS6_NSP1	TTAACCATTGTTATGGTTGCTCATTGCCGCATGTTTGCAAATGGTGTGTTTCAGAACAGA	240
PAS2_NSP1	TTAACCATTGTTATGGTTGCTCATTGCCGCATGTTTGCAAATGGTGTGTTTCAGAACAGA	240
NSP1-SA11	AGATGCTTCCTTGACAATGAACCTCATTGCTTAAAGCTTAGAAGTGTGAAACATCCAATT	300
PAS10_NSP1	AGATGCTTCCTTGACAATGAACCTCATTGCTTAAAGCTTAGAAGTGTGAAACATCCAATT	300
PAS8_NSP1	AGATGCTTCCTTGACAATGAACCTCATTGCTTAAAGCTTAGAAGTGTGAAACATCCAATT	300
PAS6_NSP1	AGATGCTTCCTTGACAATGAACCTCATTGCTTAAAGCTTAGAAGTGTGAAACATCCAATT	300
PAS2_NSP1	AGATGCTTCCTTGACAATGAACCTCATTGCTTAAAGCTTAGAAGTGTGAAACATCCAATT	300
NSP1-SA11	ACCAAAGACAAAATACAGTGTATCATAGACTTGTACAATATAATATTTCCAATTAATGAT	360
PAS10_NSP1	ACCAAAGACAAAATACAGTGTATCATAGACTTGTACAATATAATATTTCCAATTAATGAT	360
PAS8_NSP1	ACCAAAGACAAAATACAGTGTATCATAGACTTGTACAATATAATATTTCCAATTAATGAT	360
PAS6_NSP1	ACCAAAGACAAAATACAGTGTATCATAGACTTGTACAATATAATATTTCCAATTAATGAT	360
PAS2_NSP1	ACCAAAGACAAAATACAGTGTATCATAGACTTGTACAATATAATATTTCCAATTAATGAT	360

NSP1-SA11	AAAGTAATTAGAAAATTTGAAAGAATGATAAAGCAAAGAGAATGTAGGAATCAATATAAA	420
PAS10_NSP1	AAAGTAATTAGAAAATTTGAAAGAATGATAAAGCAAAGAGAATGTAGGAATCAATATAAA	420
PAS8_NSP1	AAAGTAATTAGAAAATTTGAAAGAATGATAAAGCAAAGAGAATGTAGGAATCAATATAAA	420
PAS6_NSP1	AAAGTAATTAGAAAATTTGAAAGAATGATAAAGCAAAGAGAATGTAGGAATCAATATAAA	420
PAS2_NSP1	AAAGTAATTAGAAAATTTGAAAGAATGATAAAGCAAAGAGAATGTAGGAATCAATATAAA	420
NSP1-SA11	ATTGAATGGTATAATCATTGCTGCTCCCAATTACATTAATGCTGCTGCATTTAAGTTT	480
PAS10_NSP1	ATTGAATGGTATAATCATTGCTGCTCCCAATTACATTAATGCTGCTGCATTTAAGTTT	480
PAS8_NSP1	ATTGAATGGTATAATCATTGCTGCTCCCAATTACATTAATGCTGCTGCATTTAAGTTT	480
PAS6_NSP1	ATTGAATGGTATAATCATTGCTGCTCCCAATTACATTAATGCTGCTGCATTTAAGTTT	480
PAS2_NSP1	ATTGAATGGTATAATCATTGCTGCTCCCAATTACATTAATGCTGCTGCATTTAAGTTT	480
NSP1-SA11	GATGAAAATAATCTTTATTATGTTTTGGGTTATATGAGAAATCAGTCAGTGATATATAT	540
PAS10_NSP1	GATGAAAATAATCTTTATTATGTTTTGGGTTATATGAGAAATCAGTCAGTGATATATAT	540
PAS8_NSP1	GATGAAAATAATCTTTATTATGTTTTGGGTTATATGAGAAATCAGTCAGTGATATATAT	540
PAS6_NSP1	GATGAAAATAATCTTTATTATGTTTTGGGTTATATGAGAAATCAGTCAGTGATATATAT	540
PAS2_NSP1	GATGAAAATAATCTTTATTATGTTTTGGGTTATATGAGAAATCAGTCAGTGATATATAT	540
NSP1-SA11	GCTCCATATAGAATTGTTAACTTTATAAATGAATTTGATAAATTTATGCTTGATCATATT	600
PAS10_NSP1	GCTCCATATAGAATTGTTAACTTTATAAATGAATTTGATAAATTTATGCTTGATCATATT	600
PAS8_NSP1	GCTCCATATAGAATTGTTAACTTTATAAATGAATTTGATAAATTTATGCTTGATCATATT	600
PAS6_NSP1	GCTCCATATAGAATTGTTAACTTTATAAATGAATTTGATAAATTTATGCTTGATCATATT	600
PAS2_NSP1	GCTCCATATAGAATTGTTAACTTTATAAATGAATTTGATAAATTTATGCTTGATCATATT	600
NSP1-SA11	AACTTTACAAGAATGTCCAATCTACCAATAGAGTTGAGAAACCATTACGCAAAGAAATAC	660
PAS10_NSP1	AACTTTACAAGAATGTCCAATCTACCAATAGAGTTGAGAAACCATTACGCAAAGAAATAC	660
PAS8_NSP1	AACTTTACAAGAATGTCCAATCTACCAATAGAGTTGAGAAACCATTACGCAAAGAAATAC	660
PAS6_NSP1	AACTTTACAAGAATGTCCAATCTACCAATAGAGTTGAGAAACCATTACGCAAAGAAATAC	660
PAS2_NSP1	AACTTTACAAGAATGTCCAATCTACCAATAGAGTTGAGAAACCATTACGCAAAGAAATAC	660
NSP1-SA11	TTCCAATTATCAAGACTGCCATCATCAAACCTAAAGCAAATTTACTTTTCAGATTTTACT	720
PAS10_NSP1	TTCCAATTATCAAGACTGCCATCATCAAACCTAAAGCAAATTTACTTTTCAGATTTTACT	720
PAS8_NSP1	TTCCAATTATCAAGACTGCCATCATCAAACCTAAAGCAAATTTACTTTTCAGATTTTACT	720
PAS6_NSP1	TTCCAATTATCAAGACTGCCATCATCAAACCTAAAGCAAATTTACTTTTCAGATTTTACT	720
PAS2_NSP1	TTCCAATTATCAAGACTGCCATCATCAAACCTAAAGCAAATTTACTTTTCAGATTTTACT	720
NSP1-SA11	AAAGAACTGTGATTTTTAATACTTTATACAAAAACGCCAGGAAGATCAATATACAGAAAT	780
PAS10_NSP1	AAAGAACTGTGATTTTTAATACTTTATACAAAAACGCCAGGAAGATCAATATACAGAAAT	780
PAS8_NSP1	AAAGAACTGTGATTTTTAATACTTTATACAAAAACGCCAGGAAGATCAATATACAGAAAT	780
PAS6_NSP1	AAAGAACTGTGATTTTTAATACTTTATACAAAAACGCCAGGAAGATCAATATACAGAAAT	780
PAS2_NSP1	AAAGAACTGTGATTTTTAATACTTTATACAAAAACGCCAGGAAGATCAATATACAGAAAT	780
NSP1-SA11	GTAAGTGAATTTAATTGGAGAGATGAATGGAGCTTTATTCTGATTTAAAAAATGATAAG	840
PAS10_NSP1	GTAAGTGAATTTAATTGGAGAGATGAATGGAGCTTTATTCTGATTTAAAAAATGATAAG	840
PAS8_NSP1	GTAAGTGAATTTAATTGGAGAGATGAATGGAGCTTTATTCTGATTTAAAAAATGATAAG	840
PAS6_NSP1	GTAAGTGAATTTAATTGGAGAGATGAATGGAGCTTTATTCTGATTTAAAAAATGATAAG	840
PAS2_NSP1	GTAAGTGAATTTAATTGGAGAGATGAATGGAGCTTTATTCTGATTTAAAAAATGATAAG	840
NSP1-SA11	AATAAATTAATTGCTGCAATGATGACGAGTAAGTATACTCGGTTCTATGCTCATGATAAT	900
PAS10_NSP1	AATAAATTAATTGCTGCAATGATGACGAGTAAGTATACTCGGTTCTATGCTCATGATAAT	900
PAS8_NSP1	AATAAATTAATTGCTGCAATGATGACGAGTAAGTATACTCGGTTCTATGCTCATGATAAT	900
PAS6_NSP1	AATAAATTAATTGCTGCAATGATGACGAGTAAGTATACTCGGTTCTATGCTCATGATAAT	900
PAS2_NSP1	AATAAATTAATTGCTGCAATGATGACGAGTAAGTATACTCGGTTCTATGCTCATGATAAT	900
NSP1-SA11	AATTTTGGAAGGTTGAAAATGACAATATTTGAGTTGGGACATCATTGTCAGCCTAAGTAC	960
PAS10_NSP1	AATTTTGGAAGGTTGAAAATGACAATATTTGAGTTGGGACATCATTGTCAGCCTAAGTAC	960
PAS8_NSP1	AATTTTGGAAGGTTGAAAATGACAATATTTGAGTTGGGACATCATTGTCAGCCTAAGTAC	960
PAS6_NSP1	AATTTTGGAAGGTTGAAAATGACAATATTTGAGTTGGGACATCATTGTCAGCCTAAGTAC	960
PAS2_NSP1	AATTTTGGAAGGTTGAAAATGACAATATTTGAGTTGGGACATCATTGTCAGCCTAAGTAC	960
NSP1-SA11	GTGGCATCTAATCACCAGGCAATGCTTCCGATATCCAGTACTGTAAATGGTGTAAATATA	1020
PAS10_NSP1	GTGGCATCTAATCACCAGGCAATGCTTCCGATATCCAGTACTGTAAATGGTGTAAATATA	1020
PAS8_NSP1	GTGGCATCTAATCACCAGGCAATGCTTCCGATATCCAGTACTGTAAATGGTGTAAATATA	1020
PAS6_NSP1	GTGGCATCTAATCACCAGGCAATGCTTCCGATATCCAGTACTGTAAATGGTGTAAATATA	1020
PAS2_NSP1	GTGGCATCTAATCACCAGGCAATGCTTCCGATATCCAGTACTGTAAATGGTGTAAATATA	1020
NSP1-SA11	AAATATTTTCTTAGTAAAATTTGATTTGGCGGATTCGTGATATGTATAATTTATTGATGGAA	1080
PAS10_NSP1	AAATATTTTCTTAGTAAAATTTGATTTGGCGGATTCGTGATATGTATAATTTATTGATGGAA	1080
PAS8_NSP1	AAATATTTTCTTAGTAAAATTTGATTTGGCGGATTCGTGATATGTATAATTTATTGATGGAA	1080

VP6-SA11	AATTTAATCAAATGATAATTACTATGAATGGAAATGAATTTCAAACCTGGAGGAATCGGTA	180
PAS10_VP6	AATTTAATCAAATGATAATTACTATGAATGGAAATGAATTTCAAACCTGGAGGAATCGGTA	180
PAS8_VP6	AATTTAATCAAATGATAATTACTATGAATGGAAATGAATTTCAAACCTGGAGGAATCGGTA	180
PAS6_VP6	AATTTAATCAAATGATAATTACTATGAATGGAAATGAATTTCAAACCTGGAGGAATCGGTA	180
PAS2_VP6	AATTTAATCAAATGATAATTACTATGAATGGAAATGAATTTCAAACCTGGAGGAATCGGTA	180
VP6-SA11	ATTTGCCAATTAGAAACTGGAATTTTAATTTCCGGTTACTTGGAACAACCTTTGCTGAACT	240
PAS10_VP6	ATTTGCCAATTAGAAACTGGAATTTTAATTTCCGGTTACTTGGAACAACCTTTGCTGAACT	240
PAS8_VP6	ATTTGCCAATTAGAAACTGGAATTTTAATTTCCGGTTACTTGGAACAACCTTTGCTGAACT	240
PAS6_VP6	ATTTGCCAATTAGAAACTGGAATTTTAATTTCCGGTTACTTGGAACAACCTTTGCTGAACT	240
PAS2_VP6	ATTTGCCAATTAGAAACTGGAATTTTAATTTCCGGTTACTTGGAACAACCTTTGCTGAACT	240
VP6-SA11	TAGACGCTAATTATGTTGAAACGGCAAGAAATACAATTGATTATTTTCGTGGATTTTGTAG	300
PAS10_VP6	TAGACGCTAATTATGTTGAAACGGCAAGAAATACAATTGATTATTTTCGTGGATTTTGTAG	300
PAS8_VP6	TAGACGCTAATTATGTTGAAACGGCAAGAAATACAATTGATTATTTTCGTGGATTTTGTAG	300
PAS6_VP6	TAGACGCTAATTATGTTGAAACGGCAAGAAATACAATTGATTATTTTCGTGGATTTTGTAG	300
PAS2_VP6	TAGACGCTAATTATGTTGAAACGGCAAGAAATACAATTGATTATTTTCGTGGATTTTGTAG	300
VP6-SA11	ACAATGTATGCATGGATGAGATGGTTAGAGAATCACAAGGAACGGGAATTGCACCTCAAT	360
PAS10_VP6	ACAATGTATGCATGGATGAGATGGTTAGAGAATCACAAGGAACGGGAATTGCACCTCAAT	360
PAS8_VP6	ACAATGTATGCATGGATGAGATGGTTAGAGAATCACAAGGAACGGGAATTGCACCTCAAT	360
PAS6_VP6	ACAATGTATGCATGGATGAGATGGTTAGAGAATCACAAGGAACGGGAATTGCACCTCAAT	360
PAS2_VP6	ACAATGTATGCATGGATGAGATGGTTAGAGAATCACAAGGAACGGGAATTGCACCTCAAT	360
VP6-SA11	CAGACTCGCTAAGAAAGCTGTCAGCCATTAAATTCAAAAGAATAAAATTTTGATAATTCGT	420
PAS10_VP6	CAGACTCGCTAAGAAAGCTGTCAGCCATTAAATTCAAAAGAATAAAATTTTGATAATTCGT	420
PAS8_VP6	CAGACTCGCTAAGAAAGCTGTCAGCCATTAAATTCAAAAGAATAAAATTTTGATAATTCGT	420
PAS6_VP6	CAGACTCGCTAAGAAAGCTGTCAGCCATTAAATTCAAAAGAATAAAATTTTGATAATTCGT	420
PAS2_VP6	CAGACTCGCTAAGAAAGCTGTCAGCCATTAAATTCAAAAGAATAAAATTTTGATAATTCGT	420
VP6-SA11	CGGAATACATAGAAAACCTGGAATTTGCAAAATAGAAGACAGAGGACAGGTTTCACTTTTC	480
PAS10_VP6	CGGAATACATAGAAAACCTGGAATTTGCAAAATAGAAGACAGAGGACAGGTTTCACTTTTC	480
PAS8_VP6	CGGAATACATAGAAAACCTGGAATTTGCAAAATAGAAGACAGAGGACAGGTTTCACTTTTC	480
PAS6_VP6	CGGAATACATAGAAAACCTGGAATTTGCAAAATAGAAGACAGAGGACAGGTTTCACTTTTC	480
PAS2_VP6	CGGAATACATAGAAAACCTGGAATTTGCAAAATAGAAGACAGAGGACAGGTTTCACTTTTC	480
VP6-SA11	ATAAACCAAACATTTTTCCTTATTTCAGCATCATTTTACACTAAATAGATCACAACCCGCTC	540
PAS10_VP6	ATAAACCAAACATTTTTCCTTATTTCAGCATCATTTTACACTAAATAGATCACAACCCGCTC	540
PAS8_VP6	ATAAACCAAACATTTTTCCTTATTTCAGCATCATTTTACACTAAATAGATCACAACCCGCTC	540
PAS6_VP6	ATAAACCAAACATTTTTCCTTATTTCAGCATCATTTTACACTAAATAGATCACAACCCGCTC	540
PAS2_VP6	ATAAACCAAACATTTTTCCTTATTTCAGCATCATTTTACACTAAATAGATCACAACCCGCTC	540
VP6-SA11	ATGATAATTTGATGGGCACAATGTGGTTAAACGCAGGATCGGAAATTCAGTCCGTTGGAT	600
PAS10_VP6	ATGATAATTTGATGGGCACAATGTGGTTAAACGCAGGATCGGAAATTCAGTCCGTTGGAT	600
PAS8_VP6	ATGATAATTTGATGGGCACAATGTGGTTAAACGCAGGATCGGAAATTCAGTCCGTTGGAT	600
PAS6_VP6	ATGATAATTTGATGGGCACAATGTGGTTAAACGCAGGATCGGAAATTCAGTCCGTTGGAT	600
PAS2_VP6	ATGATAATTTGATGGGCACAATGTGGTTAAACGCAGGATCGGAAATTCAGTCCGTTGGAT	600
VP6-SA11	TTGACTACTCATGTGCTATTAACGCACCAGCCAATATACAACAATTTGAGCATATTGTGC	660
PAS10_VP6	TTGACTACTCATGTGCTATTAACGCACCAGCCAATATACAACAATTTGAGCATATTGTGC	660
PAS8_VP6	TTGACTACTCATGTGCTATTAACGCACCAGCCAATATACAACAATTTGAGCATATTGTGC	660
PAS6_VP6	TTGACTACTCATGTGCTATTAACGCACCAGCCAATATACAACAATTTGAGCATATTGTGC	660
PAS2_VP6	TTGACTACTCATGTGCTATTAACGCACCAGCCAATATACAACAATTTGAGCATATTGTGC	660
VP6-SA11	CACTCCGAAGAGTGTTAACTACAGTACGATAAATCTTCTACCAGACCGGAAAGGTTTA	720
PAS10_VP6	CACTCCGAAGAGTGTTAACTACAGTACGATAAATCTTCTACCAGACCGGAAAGGTTTA	720
PAS8_VP6	CACTCCGAAGAGTGTTAACTACAGTACGATAAATCTTCTACCAGACCGGAAAGGTTTA	720
PAS6_VP6	CACTCCGAAGAGTGTTAACTACAGTACGATAAATCTTCTACCAGACCGGAAAGGTTTA	720
PAS2_VP6	CACTCCGAAGAGTGTTAACTACAGTACGATAAATCTTCTACCAGACCGGAAAGGTTTA	720
VP6-SA11	GTTTTCCAAGAGTGATCAATTCAGTACGAGGGCAACTACATGGTTTTTCAACCCAGTGA	780
PAS10_VP6	GTTTTCCAAGAGTGATCAATTCAGTACGAGGGCAACTACATGGTTTTTCAACCCAGTGA	780
PAS8_VP6	GTTTTCCAAGAGTGATCAATTCAGTACGAGGGCAACTACATGGTTTTTCAACCCAGTGA	780
PAS6_VP6	GTTTTCCAAGAGTGATCAATTCAGTACGAGGGCAACTACATGGTTTTTCAACCCAGTGA	780
PAS2_VP6	GTTTTCCAAGAGTGATCAATTCAGTACGAGGGCAACTACATGGTTTTTCAACCCAGTGA	780
VP6-SA11	TTCTCAGGCCGAATAACGTTGAAGTGGAGTTTCTATTTGAATGGACAGATAATAAACACTT	840
PAS10_VP6	TTCTCAGGCCGAATAACGTTGAAGTGGAGTTTCTATTTGAATGGACAGATAATAAACACTT	840
PAS8_VP6	TTCTCAGGCCGAATAACGTTGAAGTGGAGTTTCTATTTGAATGGACAGATAATAAACACTT	840

PAS6_VP6	TTCTCAGGCCGAATAACGTTGAAGTGGAGTTTCTATTGAATGGACAGATAATAAACACTT	840
PAS2_VP6	TTCTCAGGCCGAATAACGTTGAAGTGGAGTTTCTATTGAATGGACAGATAATAAACACTT	840
VP6-SA11	ATCAAGCAAGATTTGGAACATATCGTAGCTAGAAAATTTTGATACTATTAGACTATCATTC	900
PAS10_VP6	ATCAAGCAAGATTTGGAACATATCGTAGCTAGAAAATTTTGATACTATTAGACTATCATTC	900
PAS8_VP6	ATCAAGCAAGATTTGGAACATATCGTAGCTAGAAAATTTTGATACTATTAGACTATCATTC	900
PAS6_VP6	ATCAAGCAAGATTTGGAACATATCGTAGCTAGAAAATTTTGATACTATTAGACTATCATTC	900
PAS2_VP6	ATCAAGCAAGATTTGGAACATATCGTAGCTAGAAAATTTTGATACTATTAGACTATCATTC	900
VP6-SA11	AGTTAATGAGACCACCAAACATGACACCAGCAGTAGCAGTACTATTTCCGAATGCACAGC	960
PAS10_VP6	AGTTAATGAGACCACCAAACATGACACCAGCAGTAGCAGTACTATTTCCGAATGCACAGC	960
PAS8_VP6	AGTTAATGAGACCACCAAASATGACACCAGCAGTAGCAGTACTATTTCCGAATGCACAGC	960
PAS6_VP6	AGTTAATGAGACCACCAAACATGACACCAGCAGTAGCAGTACTATTTCCGAATGCACAGC	960
PAS2_VP6	AGTTAATGAGACCACCAAACATGACACCAGCAGTAGCAGTACTATTTCCGAATGCACAGC	960
VP6-SA11	CATTCGAACATCATGCAACAGTGGGATTGACACTTAGAATTGAGTCTGCAGTTTGTGAGT	1020
PAS10_VP6	CATTCGAACATCATGCAACAGTGGGATTGACACTTAGAATTGAGTCTGCAGTTTGTGAGT	1020
PAS8_VP6	CATTCGAACATCATGCAACAGTGGGATTGACACTTAGAATTGAGTCTGCAGTTTGTGAGT	1020
PAS6_VP6	CATTCGAACATCATGCAACAGTGGGATTGACACTTAGAATTGAGTCTGCAGTTTGTGAGT	1020
PAS2_VP6	CATTCGAACATCATGCAACAGTGGGATTGACACTTAGAATTGAGTCTGCAGTTTGTGAGT	1020
VP6-SA11	CTGTACTCGCCGATGCAAGTGAAACTCTATTAGCAAATGTAACATCCGTTAGGCAAGAGT	1080
PAS10_VP6	CTGTACTCGCCGATGCAAGTGAAACTCTATTAGCAAATGTAACATCCGTTAGGCAAGAGT	1080
PAS8_VP6	CTGTACTCGCCGATGCAAGTGAAACTCTATTAGCAAATGTAACATCCGTTAGGCAAGAGT	1080
PAS6_VP6	CTGTACTCGCCGATGCAAGTGAAACTCTATTAGCAAATGTAACATCCGTTAGGCAAGAGT	1080
PAS2_VP6	CTGTACTCGCCGATGCAAGTGAAACTCTATTAGCAAATGTAACATCCGTTAGGCAAGAGT	1080
VP6-SA11	ACGCAATACCAGTTGGACCAGTCTTTCCACCAGGTATGAACTGGACTGATTTAATCACCA	1140
PAS10_VP6	ACGCAATACCAGTTGGACCAGTCTTTCCACCAGGTATGAACTGGACTGATTTAATCACCA	1140
PAS8_VP6	ACGCAATACCAGTTGGACCAGTCTTTCCACCAGGTATGAACTGGACTGATTTAATCACCA	1140
PAS6_VP6	ACGCAATACCAGTTGGACCAGTCTTTCCACCAGGTATGAACTGGACTGATTTAATCACCA	1140
PAS2_VP6	ACGCAATACCAGTTGGACCAGTCTTTCCACCAGGTATGAACTGGACTGATTTAATCACCA	1140
VP6-SA11	ATTATTCACCGTCTAGGGAGGACAATTTGCAACGCGTATTTACAGTGGCTTCCATTAGAA	1200
PAS10_VP6	ATTATTCACCGTCTAGGGAGGACAATTTGCAACGCGTATTTACAGTGGCTTCCATTAGAA	1200
PAS8_VP6	ATTATTCACCGTCTAGGGAGGACAATTTGCAACGCGTATTTACAGTGGCTTCCATTAGAA	1200
PAS6_VP6	ATTATTCACCGTCTAGGGAGGACAATTTGCAACGCGTATTTACAGTGGCTTCCATTAGAA	1200
PAS2_VP6	ATTATTCACCGTCTAGGGAGGACAATTTGCAACGCGTATTTACAGTGGCTTCCATTAGAA	1200
VP6-SA11	GCATGCTCATTAATGAGGACCAAGCTAACAACCTTGGTATCCAACCTTTGGTGAGTATGTA	1260
PAS10_VP6	GCATGCTCATTAATGAGGACCAAGCTAACAACCTTGGTATCCAACCTTTGGTGAGTATGTA	1260
PAS8_VP6	GCATGCTCATTAATGAGGACCAAGCTAACAACCTTGGTATCCAACCTTTGGTGAGTATGTA	1260
PAS6_VP6	GCATGCTCATTAATGAGGACCAAGCTAACAACCTTGGTATCCAACCTTTGGTGAGTATGTA	1260
PAS2_VP6	GCATGCTCATTAATGAGGACCAAGCTAACAACCTTGGTATCCAACCTTTGGTGAGTATGTA	1260
VP6-SA11	GCTATATCAAGCTGTTTGAACTCTGTAAGTAAGGATGCGTATACGCATTGCTACACAGA	1320
PAS10_VP6	GCTATATCAAGCTGTTTGAACTCTGTAAGTAAGGATGCGTATACGCATTGCTACACAGA	1320
PAS8_VP6	GCTATATCAAGCTGTTTGAACTCTGTAAGTAAGGATGCGTATACGCATTGCTACACAGA	1320
PAS6_VP6	GCTATATCAAGCTGTTTGAACTCTGTAAGTAAGGATGCGTATACGCATTGCTACACAGA	1320
PAS2_VP6	GCTATATCAAGCTGTTTGAACTCTGTAAGTAAGGATGCGTATACGCATTGCTACACAGA	1320
VP6-SA11	GTAATCACTCAGATGGTATAGTGAGAGGATGTGACC	1356
PAS10_VP6	GTAATCACTCAGATGGTATAGTGAGAGGATGTGACC	1356
PAS8_VP6	GTAATCACTCAGATGGTATAGTGAGAGGATGTGACC	1356
PAS6_VP6	GTAATCACTCAGATGGTATAGTGAGAGGATGTGACC	1356
PAS2_VP6	GTAATCACTCAGATGGTATAGTGAGAGGATGTGACC	1356

GENOME SEGMENT 7 :

VP7-SA11	GGCTTTAAAAAGAGAGAATTTCCGTTTGGCTAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTTTAATGTATGGTAT	60
PAS10_VP7	GGCTTTAAAAAGAGAGAATTTCCGTTTGGCTAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTTTAATGTATGGTAT	60
PAS8_VP7	GGCTTTAAAAAGAGAGAATTTCCGTTTGGCTAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTTTAATGTATGGTAT	60
PAS6_VP7	GGCTTTAAAAAGAGAGAATTTCCGTTTGGCTAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTTTAATGTATGGTAT	60
PAS2_VP7	NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNTCCGTTTGGCTAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTTTAATGTATGGTAT	60
VP7-SA11	TGAATATAACCACAGTTCTAACCTTTCTGATATCGATTATTCTACTAAATTACATACTTAA	120
PAS10_VP7	TGAATATAACCACAGTTCTAACCTTTCTGATATCGATTATTCTACTAAATTACATACTTAA	120
PAS8_VP7	TGAATATAACCACAGTTCTAACCTTTCTGATATCGATTATTCTACTAAATTACATACTTAA	120
PAS6_VP7	TGAATATAACCACAGTTCTAACCTTTCTGATATCGATTATTCTACTAAATTACATACTTAA	120

PAS2_VP7 TGAATATAACCACAGTTCTAACCTTTCTGATATCGATTATTCTACTAAATTACATACTTAA 120

VP7-SA11 ATCATTAAC TAGAATAATGGACTTTATAATTTATAGATTTCTTTTTATAAATTGTGATATT 180
PAS10_VP7 ATCATTAAC TAGAATAATGGACTTTATAATTTATAGATTTCTTTTTATAAATTGTGATATT 180
PAS8_VP7 ATCATTAAC TAGAATAATGGACTTTATAATTTATAGATTTCTTTTTATAAATTGTGATATT 180
PAS6_VP7 ATCATTAAC TAGAATAATGGACTTTATAATTTATAGATTTCTTTTTATAAATTGTGATATT 180
PAS2_VP7 ATCATTAAC TAGAATAATGGACTTTATAATTTATAGATTTCTTTTTATAAATTGTGATATT 180

VP7-SA11 GTCACCATTTCAGAGCACAAAATTTATGGTATTAATCTTCCAATCACAGGCTCCATGGA 240
PAS10_VP7 GTCAYCATTTCTCAGAGCACAAAATTTATGGTATTAATCTTCCAATCACAGGCTCCATGGA 240
PAS8_VP7 GTCAYCATTTCTCAGAGCACAAAATTTATGGTATTAATCTTCCAATCACAGGCTCCATGGA 240
PAS6_VP7 GTCAYCATTTCTCAGAGCACAAAATTTATGGTATTAATCTTCCAATCACAGGCTCCATGGA 240
PAS2_VP7 GTCATCATTTCTCAGAGCACAAAATTTATGGTATTAATCTTCCAATCACAGGCTCCATGGA 240

VP7-SA11 CATTCGCATACGCTAATTCAACGCAAGAAGAACCATTCTCACTTCTACACTTTGCCTATA 300
PAS10_VP7 CATTCGCATACGCTAATTCAACGCAAGAAGAACCATTCTCACTTCTACACTTTGCCTATA 300
PAS8_VP7 CATTCGCATACGCTAATTCAACGCAAGAAGAACCATTCTCACTTCTACACTTTGCCTATA 300
PAS6_VP7 CATTCGCATACGCTAATTCAACGCAAGAAGAACCATTCTCACTTCTACACTTTGCCTATA 300
PAS2_VP7 CATTCGCATACGCTAATTCAACGCAAGAAGAACCATTCTCACTTCTACACTTTGCCTATA 300

VP7-SA11 TTATCCGACTGAGGCTGCGACTGAAATAAACGATAAATTCATGGAAAGACACACTGTCACA 360
PAS10_VP7 TTATCCGACTGAGGCTGCGACTGAAATAAACGATAAATTCATGGAAAGACACACTGTCACA 360
PAS8_VP7 TTATCCGACTGAGGCTGCGACTGAAATAAACGATAAATTCATGGAAAGACACACTGTCACA 360
PAS6_VP7 TTATCCGACTGAGGCTGCGACTGAAATAAACGATAAATTCATGGAAAGACACACTGTCACA 360
PAS2_VP7 TTATCCGACTGAGGCTGCGACTGAAATAAACGATAAATTCATGGAAAGACACACTGTCACA 360

VP7-SA11 ACTATTTCTTACGAAAGGGTGGCCAACTGGATCCGTATATTTTAAAGAATATACTAACAT 420
PAS10_VP7 ACTATTTCTTACGAAAGGGTGGCCAACTGGATCCGTATATTTTAAAGAATATACTAACAT 420
PAS8_VP7 ACTATTTCTTACGAAAGGGTGGCCAACTGGATCCGTATATTTTAAAGAATATACTAACAT 420
PAS6_VP7 ACTATTTCTTACGAAAGGGTGGCCAACTGGATCCGTATATTTTAAAGAATATACTAACAT 420
PAS2_VP7 ACTATTTCTTACGAAAGGGTGGCCAACTGGATCCGTATATTTTAAAGAATATACTAACAT 420

VP7-SA11 TGCATCGTTTTCTGTTGATCCGCAGTTGTATTGTGATTATAACGTAGTACTAATGAAATA 480
PAS10_VP7 TGCATCGTTTTCTGTTGATCCGCAGTTGTATTGTGATTATAACGTAGTACTAATGAAATA 480
PAS8_VP7 TGCATCGTTTTCTGTTGATCCGCAGTTGTATTGTGATTATAACGTAGTACTAATGAAATA 480
PAS6_VP7 TGCATCGTTTTCTGTTGATCCGCAGTTGTATTGTGATTATAACGTAGTACTAATGAAATA 480
PAS2_VP7 TGCATCGTTTTCTGTTGATCCGCAGTTGTATTGTGATTATAACGTAGTACTAATGAAATA 480

VP7-SA11 TGACGCGACGTTGCAATTGGATATGTCAGAACTTGCGGATCTAATATTAACGAATGGTT 540
PAS10_VP7 TGACGCGACGTTGCAATTGGATATGTCAGAACTTGCGGATCTAATATTAACGAATGGTT 540
PAS8_VP7 TGACGCGACGTTGCAATTGGATATGTCAGAACTTGCGGATCTAATATTAACGAATGGTT 540
PAS6_VP7 TGACGCGACGTTGCAATTGGATATGTCAGAACTTGCGGATCTAATATTAACGAATGGTT 540
PAS2_VP7 TGACGCGACGTTGCAATTGGATATGTCAGAACTTGCGGATCTAATATTAACGAATGGTT 540

VP7-SA11 GTGTAATCCAATGGATATTACTCTGTATTATTATCAGCAAAC TGACGAAGCGAATAAATG 600
PAS10_VP7 GTGTAATCCAATGGATATTACTCTGTATTATTATCAGCAAAC TGACGAAGCGAATAAATG 600
PAS8_VP7 GTGTAATCCAATGGATATTACTCTGTATTATTATCAGCAAAC TGACGAAGCGAATAAATG 600
PAS6_VP7 GTGTAATCCAATGGATATTACTCTGTATTATTATCAGCAAAC TGACGAAGCGAATAAATG 600
PAS2_VP7 GTGTAATCCAATGGATATTACTCTGTATTATTATCAGCAAAC TGACGAAGCGAATAAATG 600

VP7-SA11 GATATCAATGGGCTCATCATGTACAATTAAGTATGTCCACTTAATACAAAACCTTTGG 660
PAS10_VP7 GATATCAATGGGCTCATCATGTACAATTAAGTATGTCCACTTAATACAAAACCTTTGG 660
PAS8_VP7 GATATCAATGGGCTCATCATGTACAATTAAGTATGTCCACTTAATACAAAACCTTTGG 660
PAS6_VP7 GATATCAATGGGCTCATCATGTACAATTAAGTATGTCCACTTAATACAAAACCTTTGG 660
PAS2_VP7 GATATCAATGGGCTCATCATGTACAATTAAGTATGTCCACTTAATACAAAACCTTTGG 660

VP7-SA11 AATTGGATGCTTGACAAC TGATGCTACAACCTTTTGAAGAAGTTGCGACAGCTGAAAAGTT 720
PAS10_VP7 AATTGGATGCTTGACAAC TGATGCTACAACCTTTTGAAGAAGTTGCGACAGCTGAAAAGTT 720
PAS8_VP7 AATTGGATGCTTGACAAC TGATGCTACAACCTTTTGAAGAAGTTGCGACAGCTGAAAAGTT 720
PAS6_VP7 AATTGGATGCTTGACAAC TGATGCTACAACCTTTTGAAGAAGTTGCGACAGCTGAAAAGTT 720
PAS2_VP7 AATTGGATGCTTGACAAC TGATGCTACAACCTTTTGAAGAAGTTGCGACAGCTGAAAAGTT 720

VP7-SA11 GGTAATTACTGACGTGGTTGATGGCGTTAATCATAAGCTGGATGTCACAACAGCAACGTG 780
PAS10_VP7 GGTAATTACTGACGTGGTTGATGGCGTTAATCATAAGCTGGATGTCACAACAGCAACGTG 780
PAS8_VP7 GGTAATTACTGACGTGGTTGATGGCGTTAATCATAAGCTGGATGTCACAACAGCAACGTG 780
PAS6_VP7 GGTAATTACTGACGTGGTTGATGGCGTTAATCATAAGCTGGATGTCACAACAGCAACGTG 780
PAS2_VP7 GGTAATTACTGACGTGGTTGATGGCGTTAATCATAAGCTGGATGTCACAACAGCAACGTG 780

VP7-SA11 TACTATTAGAACTGTAAGAAATTTGGACCAAGAGAAAACGTAGCCGTTATACAAGTTGG 840
PAS10_VP7 TACTATTAGAACTGTAAGAAATTTGGACCAAGAGAAAACGTAGCCGTTATACAAGTTGG 840

PAS8_VP7	TACTATTAGAACTGTAAGAAATTTGGGACCAAGAGAAAACGTAGCCGTTATACAAGTTGG	840
PAS6_VP7	TACTATTAGAACTGTAAGAAATTTGGGACCAAGAGAAAACGTAGCCGTTATACAAGTTGG	840
PAS2_VP7	TACTATTAGAACTGTAAGAAATTTGGGACCAAGAGAAAACGTAGCCGTTATACAAGTTGG	840
VP7-SA11	TGGTTCTGACATCCTCGATATAACTGCTGATCCAACACTACTGCACCACAGACAGAACGGAT	900
PAS10_VP7	TGGTTCTGACATCCTCGATATAACTGCTGATCCAACACTACTGCACCACAGACAGAACGGAT	900
PAS8_VP7	TGGTTCTGACATCCTCGATATAACTGCTGATCCAACACTACTGCACCACAGACAGAACGGAT	900
PAS6_VP7	TGGTTCTGACATCCTCGATATAACTGCTGATCCAACACTACTGCACCACAGACAGAACGGAT	900
PAS2_VP7	TGGTTCTGACATCCTCGATATAACTGCTGATCCAACACTACTGCACCACAGACAGAACGGAT	900
VP7-SA11	GATGCGAATTAAC TGAAAAAATGGTGCCAAGTTTTTTATACTGTAGTAGACTATGTAGA	960
PAS10_VP7	GATGCGAATTAAC TGAAAAAATGGTGCCAAGTTTTTTATACTGTAGTAGACTATGTAGA	960
PAS8_VP7	GATGCGAATTAAC TGAAAAAATGGTGCCAAGTTTTTTATACTGTAGTAGACTATGTAGA	960
PAS6_VP7	GATGCGAATTAAC TGAAAAAATGGTGCCAAGTTTTTTATACTGTAGTAGACTATGTAGA	960
PAS2_VP7	GATGCGAATTAAC TGAAAAAATGGTGCCAAGTTTTTTATACTGTAGTAGACTATGTAGA	960
VP7-SA11	TCAGATAATACAAGTTATGTCCAAAAGATCAAGATCACTAAATTCAGCAGCATT TTTATTA	1020
PAS10_VP7	TCAGATAATACAAGTTATGTCCAAAAGATCAAGATCACTAAATTCAGCAGCATT TTTATTA	1020
PAS8_VP7	TCAGATAATACAAGTTATGTCCAAAAGATCAAGATCACTAAATTCAGCAGCATT TTTATTA	1020
PAS6_VP7	TCAGATAATACAAGTTATGTCCAAAAGATCAAGATCACTAAATTCAGCAGCATT TTTATTA	1020
PAS2_VP7	TCAGATAATACAAGTTATGTCCAAAAGATCAAGATCACTAAATTCAGCAGCATT TTTATTA	1020
VP7-SA11	CAGAGTGTAGGTATAA CTTAGGTTAGAATTGTATGATGTGACC	1063
PAS10_VP7	CAGAGTGTAGGTATAA CTTAGGTTAGAATTGTATGATGTGACC	1063
PAS8_VP7	CAGAGTGTAGGTATAA CTTAGGTTAGAATTGTATGATGTGACC	1063
PAS6_VP7	CAGAGTGTAGGTATAA CTTAGGTTAGAATTGTATGATGTGACC	1063
PAS2_VP7	CAGAGTGTAGGTATAA CTTAGGTTAGAATTGTATGATGTGACC	1063

GENOME SEGMENT 8:

NSP2-SA11	GGCTTTTAAAGCGTCTCAGTCGCGCTTTGAGCCTTGCGGTGTAGCCATGGCTGAGCTAGC	60
PAS10_NSP2	GGCTTTTAAAGCGTCTCAGTCGCGCTTTGAGCCTTGCGGTGTAGCCATGGCTGAGCTAGC	60
PAS8_NSP2	GGCTTTTAAAGCGTCTCAGTCRYCGTTTGGAGCCTTGCGGTGTAGCCATGGCTGAGCTAGC	60
PAS6_NSP2	GGCTTTTAAAGCGTCTCAGTCRYCGTTTGGAGCCTTGCGGTGTAGCCATGGCTGAGCTAGC	60
PAS2_NSP2	NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNCAGTCRCCGTTTGGAGCCTTGCGGTGTAGCCATGGCTGAGCTAGC	60
NSP2-SA11	TTGCTTTTGCATCCTCATTGGAGAATGATAGCTATAAATTTATTCCTTTTAATAAATTT	120
PAS10_NSP2	TTGCTTTTGYTATCCTCATTGGAGAAYGATAGCTATAAATTTATTCCTTTTAATAAATTT	120
PAS8_NSP2	TTGCTTTTGCATCCTCATTGGAGAATGATAGCTATAAATTTATTCCTTTTAATAAATTT	120
PAS6_NSP2	TTGCTTTTGCATCCTCATTGGAGAATGATAGCTATAAATTTATTCCTTTTAATAAATTT	120
PAS2_NSP2	TTGCTTTTGCATCCTCATTGGAGAATGATAGCTATAAATTTATTCCTTTTAATAAATTT	120
NSP2-SA11	AGCTATTAAGCTATGCTGACAGCTAAAGTAGACAAAAAGGACATGGATAAGTTTATGA	180
PAS10_NSP2	AGCWATWAATGCTATGYTGACAGCTAAAGTRGAYAAAAAGGACATGGATAAGTTTATGA	180
PAS8_NSP2	AGCTATTAAGCTATGCTGACAGCTAAAGTAGACAAAAAGGACATGGATAAGTTTATGA	180
PAS6_NSP2	AGCTATTAAGCTATGCTGACAGCTAAAGTAGACAAAAAGGACATGGATAAGTTTATGA	180
PAS2_NSP2	AGCTATTAAGCTATGCTGACAGCTAAAGTAGACAAAAAGGACATGGATAAGTTTATGA	180
NSP2-SA11	TTCAATTATTTATGGAATAGCACC GCCTCCTCAATTTAAGAAACGGTATAATACTAATGA	240
PAS10_NSP2	TTCAATTATTTATGGAATAGCACC GCCTCCTCAATTTAAGAAACGGTATAATACTAATGA	240
PAS8_NSP2	TTCAATTATTTATGGAATAGCACC GCCTCCTCAATTTAAGAAACGGTATAATACTAATGA	240
PAS6_NSP2	TTCAATTATTTATGGAATAGCACC GCCTCCTCAATTTAAGAAACGGTATAATACTAATGA	240
PAS2_NSP2	TTCAATTATTTATGGAATAGCACC GCCTCCTCAATTTAAGAAACGGTATAATACTAATGA	240
NSP2-SA11	TAATTCAAGAGGCATGAATTTTGAACAATTATGTTTACTAAGGTGGCTATGTTGATATG	300
PAS10_NSP2	TAATTCAAGAGGCATGAATTTTGAACAATTATGTTTACTAAGGTGGCTATGTTGATATG	300
PAS8_NSP2	TAATTCAAGAGGCATGAATTTTGAACAATTATGTTTACTAAGGTGGCTATGTTGATATG	300
PAS6_NSP2	TAATTCAAGAGGCATGAATTTTGAACAATTATGTTTACTAAGGTGGCTATGTTGATATG	300
PAS2_NSP2	TAATTCAAGAGGCATGAATTTTGAACAATTATGTTTACTAAGGTGGCTATGTTGATATG	300
NSP2-SA11	TGAAGCTCTAAATTCATTGAAAGTGACGCAAGCAAACGTCTCTAATGTATTATCACGAGT	360
PAS10_NSP2	TGAAGCTCTAAATTCATTGAAAGTGACGCAAGCAAACGTCTCTAATGTATTATCACGAGT	360
PAS8_NSP2	TGAAGCTCTAAATTCATTGAAAGTGACGCAAGCAAACGTCTCTAATGTATTATCACGAGT	360
PAS6_NSP2	TGAAGCTCTAAATTCATTGAAAGTGACGCAAGCAAACGTCTCTAATGTATTATCACGAGT	360
PAS2_NSP2	TGAAGCTCTAAATTCATTGAAAGTGACGCAAGCAAACGTCTCTAATGTATTATCACGAGT	360
NSP2-SA11	AGTATCAATAAGGCATTTAGAAAAATTTGGTGATACGTAAGAAAAATCCACAGGATATTTCT	420
PAS10_NSP2	AGTATCAATAAGGCATTTAGAAAAATTTGGTGATACGTAAGAAAAATCCACAGGATATTTCT	420
PAS8_NSP2	AGTATCAATAAGGCATTTAGAAAAATTTGGTGATACGTAAGAAAAATCCACAGGATATTTCT	420

PAS6_NSP2	AGTATCAATAAGGCATTTAGAAAATTTGGTGATACGTAAAGAAAATCCACAGGATATTCT	420
PAS2_NSP2	AGTATCAATAAGGCATTTAGAAAATTTGGTGATACGTAAAGAAAATCCACAGGATATTCT	420
NSP2-SA11	ATTTTCATTCAAAAAGATTTACTTTTTGAAATCAACACTGATTGCTATTGGACAGTCTAAAGA	480
PAS10_NSP2	ATTTTCATTCAAAAAGATTTACTTTTTGAAATCAACACTGATTGCTATTGGACAGTCTAAAGA	480
PAS8_NSP2	ATTTTCATTCAAAAAGATTTACTTTTTGAAATCAACACTGATTGCTATTGGACAGTCTAAAGA	480
PAS6_NSP2	ATTTTCATTCAAAAAGATTTACTTTTTGAAATCAACACTGATTGCTATTGGACAGTCTAAAGA	480
PAS2_NSP2	ATTTTCATTCAAAAAGATTTACTTTTTGAAATCAACACTGATTGCTATTGGACAGTCTAAAGA	480
NSP2-SA11	AATTGAAACTACAATAACTGCAGAAGGAGGAGAAAATTGTATTTCAAACGCTGCCTTCAC	540
PAS10_NSP2	AATTGAAACTACAATAACTGCAGAAGGAGGAGAAAATTGTATTTCAAACGCTGCCTTCAC	540
PAS8_NSP2	AATTGAAACTACAATAACTGCAGAAGGAGGAGAAAATTGTATTTCAAACGCTGCCTTCAC	540
PAS6_NSP2	AATTGAAACTACAATAACTGCAGAAGGAGGAGAAAATTGTATTTCAAACGCTGCCTTCAC	540
PAS2_NSP2	AATTGAAACTACAATAACTGCAGAAGGAGGAGAAAATTGTATTTCAAACGCTGCCTTCAC	540
NSP2-SA11	CATGTGGAAACTAACTTATTTAGAACATCAATTGATGCCAATTCGGATCAGAATTTTAT	600
PAS10_NSP2	CATGTGGAAACTAACTTATTTAGAACATCAATTGATGCCAATTCGGATCAGAATTTTAT	600
PAS8_NSP2	CATGTGGAAACTAACTTATTTAGAACATCAATTGATGCCAATTCGGATCAGAATTTTAT	600
PAS6_NSP2	CATGTGGAAACTAACTTATTTAGAACATCAATTGATGCCAATTCGGATCAGAATTTTAT	600
PAS2_NSP2	CATGTGGAAACTAACTTATTTAGAACATCAATTGATGCCAATTCGGATCAGAATTTTAT	600
NSP2-SA11	TGAATATAAAGTTACATTGAACGAAGATAAAACCAATTTTCAGATGTTTCATGTTAAAGAATT	660
PAS10_NSP2	TGAATATAAAGTTACATTGAACGAAGATAAAACCAATTTTCAGATGTTTCATGTTAAAGAATT	660
PAS8_NSP2	TGAATATAAAGTTACATTGAACGAAGATAAAACCAATTTTCAGATGTTTCATGTTAAAGAATT	660
PAS6_NSP2	TGAATATAAAGTTACATTGAACGAAGATAAAACCAATTTTCAGATGTTTCATGTTAAAGAATT	660
PAS2_NSP2	TGAATATAAAGTTACATTGAACGAAGATAAAACCAATTTTCAGATGTTTCATGTTAAAGAATT	660
NSP2-SA11	AGTCGCTGAAC TTCGATGGCAATATAACAAGTTTGCTGTAATCACACATGGTAAGGGTCA	720
PAS10_NSP2	AGTCGCTGAAC TTCGATGGCAATATAACAAGTTTGCTGTAATCACACATGGTAAGGGTCA	720
PAS8_NSP2	AGTCGCTGAAC TTCGATGGCAATATAACAAGTTTGCTGTAATCACACATGGTAAGGGTCA	720
PAS6_NSP2	AGTCGCTGAAC TTCGATGGCAATATAACAAGTTTGCTGTAATCACACATGGTAAGGGTCA	720
PAS2_NSP2	AGTCGCTGAAC TTCGATGGCAATATAACAAGTTTGCTGTAATCACACATGGTAAGGGTCA	720
NSP2-SA11	TTATAGAATTGTAAAGTATTCATCAGTTGCTAATCACGCTGACAGAGTATATGCAACTTT	780
PAS10_NSP2	TTATAGAATTGTAAAGTATTCATCAGTTGCTAATCACGCTGACAGAGTATATGCAACTTT	780
PAS8_NSP2	TTATAGAATTGTAAAGTATTCATCAGTTGCTAATCACGCTGACAGAGTATATGCAACTTT	780
PAS6_NSP2	TTATAGAATTGTAAAGTATTCATCAGTTGCTAATCACGCTGACAGAGTATATGCAACTTT	780
PAS2_NSP2	TTATAGAATTGTAAAGTATTCATCAGTTGCTAATCACGCTGACAGAGTATATGCAACTTT	780
NSP2-SA11	CAAGAGTAATGTTAAAAC TGGAGTTAATAATGATTTTAACTTAC TTGATCAAAGAATTAT	840
PAS10_NSP2	CAAGAGTAATGTTAAAAC TGGAGTTAATAATGATTTTAACTTAC TTGATCAAAGAATTAT	840
PAS8_NSP2	CAAGAGTAATGTTAAAAC TGGAGTTAATAATGATTTTAACTTAC TTGATCAAAGAATTAT	840
PAS6_NSP2	CAAGAGTAATGTTAAAAC TGGAGTTAATAATGATTTTAACTTAC TTGATCAAAGAATTAT	840
PAS2_NSP2	CAAGAGTAATGTTAAAAC TGGAGTTAATAATGATTTTAACTTAC TTGATCAAAGAATTAT	840
NSP2-SA11	TTGGCAAAC TGGTATGCATTTACATCATCAATGAAACAGGGTAATACACTTGACGTGTG	900
PAS10_NSP2	TTGGCAAAC TGGTATGCATTTACATCATCAATGAAACAGGGTAATACACTTGACGTGTG	900
PAS8_NSP2	TTGGCAAAC TGGTATGCATTTACATCATCAATGAAACAGGGTAATACACTTGACGTGTG	900
PAS6_NSP2	TTGGCAAAC TGGTATGCATTTACATCATCAATGAAACAGGGTAATACACTTGACGTGTG	900
PAS2_NSP2	TTGGCAAAC TGGTATGCATTTACATCATCAATGAAACAGGGTAATACACTTGACGTGTG	900
NSP2-SA11	TAAAAGGTTGCTTTTCCAAAAATGAAACCAGAAAAAAATCCATTTAAAGGGCTGTCAAC	960
PAS10_NSP2	TAAAAGGTTGCTTTTCCAAAAATGAAACCAGAAAAAAATCCATTTAAAGGGCTGTCAAC	960
PAS8_NSP2	TAAAAGGTTGCTTTTCCAAAAATGAAACCAGAAAAAAATCCATTTAAAGGGCTGTCAAC	960
PAS6_NSP2	TAAAAGGTTGCTTTTCCAAAAATGAAACCAGAAAAAAATCCATTTAAAGGGCTGTCAAC	960
PAS2_NSP2	TAAAAGGTTGCTTTTCCAAAAATGAAACCAGAAAAAAATCCATTTAAAGGGCTGTCAAC	960
NSP2-SA11	GGATAGAAAAATGGACGAAGTTTCTCAAGTTGGCGTTTAATTCGCTATCAATTTGAGGAT	1020
PAS10_NSP2	GGATAGAAAAATGGACGAAGTTTCTCAAGTTGGCGTTTAATTCGCTATCAATTTGAGGAY	1020
PAS8_NSP2	GGATAGAAAAATGGACGAAGTTTCTCAAGTTGGCGTTTAATTCGCTATCAATTTGAGGAY	1020
PAS6_NSP2	GGATAGAAAAATGGACGAAGTTTCTCAAGTTGGCGTTTAATTCGCTATCAATTTGAGGAY	1020
PAS2_NSP2	GGATAGAAAAATGGACGAAGTTTCTCAAGTTGGCGTTTAATTCGCTATCAATTTGAGGAT	1020
NSP2-SA11	GATGATGGCTTAGCAAGAATAGAAAGCGCTTATGTGACC	1059
PAS10_NSP2	GATGATGGCTTAGCAAGAATAGAAAGCGCTTATGTGACC	1059
PAS8_NSP2	GATGATGGCTTAGCAAGAATAGAAAGCGCTTATGTGACC	1059
PAS6_NSP2	GATGATGGCTTAGCAAGAATAGAAAGCGCTTATGTGACC	1059
PAS2_NSP2	GATGATGGCTTAGCAAGAATAGAAAGCGCTTATGTGACC	1059

GENOME SEGMENT 9:

NSP3-SA11	GGCATTTAATGCTTTTCAGTGGTTGATGCTCAAGATGGAGTCTACGCAACAGATGGCCGT	60
PAS10_NSP3	GGCWTTTAATGCTTTTCAGTGGTTGATGCTCAAGATGGAGTCTACGCAACAGATGGCCGT	60
PAS8_NSP3	GGCATTTAATGCTTTTCAGTGGTTGATGCTCAAGATGGAGTCTACGCAACAGATGGCCGT	60
PAS6_NSP3	GGCATTTAATGCTTTTCAGTGGTTGATGCTCAAGATGGAGTCTACGCAACAGATGGCCGT	60
PAS2_NSP3	NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNTCAGTGGTTGATGCTCAAGATGGAGTCTACGCAACAGWTGGCCGT	60
NSP3-SA11	CTCAATTATTAACCTCTTCTTTTGAAGCTGCAGTTGTAGCTGCAACCTCAGCTCTTGAGAA	120
PAS10_NSP3	CTCAATTATTAACCTCTTCTTTTGAAGCTGCAGTTGTAGCTGCAACCTCAGCTCTTGAGAA	120
PAS8_NSP3	CTCAATTATTAACCTCTTCTTTTGAAGCTGCAGTTGTAGCTGCAACCTCAGCTCTTGAGAA	120
PAS6_NSP3	CTCAATTATTAACCTCTTCTTTTGAAGCTGCAGTTGTAGCTGCAACCTCAGCTCTTGAGAA	120
PAS2_NSP3	CTCAATTATTAACCTCTTCTTTTGAAGCTGCAGTTGTAGCTGCAACCTCAGCTCTTGAGAA	120
NSP3-SA11	TATGGGAATAGAATATGATTATCAGGATATATATTTCTAGAGTAAAGAATAAATTTGATTT	180
PAS10_NSP3	TATGGGAATAGAATATGATTATCAGGATATATATTTCTAGAGTAAAGAATAAATTTGATTT	180
PAS8_NSP3	TATGGGAATAGAATATGATTATCAGGATATATATTTCTAGAGTAAAGAATAAATTTGATTT	180
PAS6_NSP3	TATGGGAATAGAATATGATTATCAGGATATATATTTCTAGAGTAAAGAATAAATTTGATTT	180
PAS2_NSP3	TATGGGAATAGAATATGATTATCAGGATATATATTTCTAGAGTAAAGAATAAATTTGATTT	180
NSP3-SA11	TGTGATGGACGATTCCTGGTGTAAAAATAATCTGATTGGTAAAGCAATAACTATTGATCA	240
PAS10_NSP3	TGTGATGGACGATTCCTGGTGTAAAAATAATCTGATTGGTAAAGCAATAACTATTGATCA	240
PAS8_NSP3	TGTGATGGACGATTCCTGGTGTAAAAATAATCTGATTGGTAAAGCAATAACTATTGATCA	240
PAS6_NSP3	TGTGATGGACGATTCCTGGTGTAAAAATAATCTGATTGGTAAAGCAATAACTATTGATCA	240
PAS2_NSP3	TGTGATGGACGATTCCTGGTGTAAAAATAATCTGATTGGTAAAGCAATAACTATTGATCA	240
NSP3-SA11	AGCTTTGAATAATAAATTTGGATCTGCTATAAGAAATAGAAACTGGCTTGCTGATACTTC	300
PAS10_NSP3	AGCTTTGAATAATAAATTTGGATCTGCTATAAGAAATAGAAACTGGCTTGCTGATACTTC	300
PAS8_NSP3	AGCTTTGAATAATAAATTTGGATCTGCTATAAGAAATAGAAACTGGCTTGCTGATACTTC	300
PAS6_NSP3	AGCTTTGAATAATAAATTTGGATCTGCTATAAGAAATAGAAACTGGCTTGCTGATACTTC	300
PAS2_NSP3	AGCTTTGAATAATAAATTTGGATCTGCTATAAGAAATAGAAACTGGCTTGCTGATACTTC	300
NSP3-SA11	TAGAGCAGCTAAATTAGATGAGGATGTAAACAAACTAAGAATGATGTTATCATCAAAAGG	360
PAS10_NSP3	TAGAGCAGCTAAATTAGATGAGGATGTAAACAAACTAAGAATGATGTTATCATCAAAAGG	360
PAS8_NSP3	TAGAGCAGCTAAATTAGATGAGGATGTAAACAAACTAAGAATGATGTTATCATCAAAAGG	360
PAS6_NSP3	TAGAGCAGCTAAATTAGATGAGGATGTAAACAAACTAAGAATGATGTTATCATCAAAAGG	360
PAS2_NSP3	TAGAGCAGCTAAATTAGATGAGGATGTAAACAAACTAAGAATGATGTTATCATCAAAAGG	360
NSP3-SA11	AATTGATCAAAAAATGAGAGTTTTAAACGCATGCTTCAGTGTAAAAAGAATACCTGGAAA	420
PAS10_NSP3	AATTGATCAAAAAATGAGAGTTTTAAACGCATGCTTCAGTGTAAAAAGAATACCTGGAAA	420
PAS8_NSP3	AATTGATCAAAAAATGAGAGTTTTAAACGCATGCTTCAGTGTAAAAAGAATACCTGGAAA	420
PAS6_NSP3	AATTGATCAAAAAATGAGAGTTTTAAACGCATGCTTCAGTGTAAAAAGAATACCTGGAAA	420
PAS2_NSP3	AATTGATCAAAAAATGAGAGTTTTAAACGCATGCTTCAGTGTAAAAAGAATACCTGGAAA	420
NSP3-SA11	ATCATCATCTATTATTAATGCACAAAATTGATGCGTGATAAATTGGAACGTGGTGAAGT	480
PAS10_NSP3	ATCATCATCTATTATTAATGCACAAAATTGATGCGTGATAAATTGGAACGTGGTGAAGT	480
PAS8_NSP3	ATCATCATCTATTATTAATGCACAAAATTGATGCGTGATAAATTGGAACGTGGTGAAGT	480
PAS6_NSP3	ATCATCATCTATTATTAATGCACAAAATTGATGCGTGATAAATTGGAACGTGGTGAAGT	480
PAS2_NSP3	ATCATCATCTATTATTAATGCACAAAATTGATGCGTGATAAATTGGAACGTGGTGAAGT	480
NSP3-SA11	TGAAGTGGATGATTCATTTGTGGATGAAAAAATGGAAGTGGATACCATTGACTGGAAATC	540
PAS10_NSP3	TGAAGTGGATGATTCATTTGTGGATGAAAAAATGGAAGTGGATACCATTGACTGGAAATC	540
PAS8_NSP3	TGAAGTGGATGATTCATTTGTGGATGAAAAAATGGAAGTGGATACCATTGACTGGAAATC	540
PAS6_NSP3	TGAAGTGGATGATTCATTTGTGGATGAAAAAATGGAAGTGGATACCATTGACTGGAAATC	540
PAS2_NSP3	TGAAGTGGATGATTCATTTGTGGATGAAAAAATGGAAGTGGATACCATTGACTGGAAATC	540
NSP3-SA11	GCGCTATGAGCAATTGGAGCAAAGGTTTGAATCATTGAAATCCAGGGTAAATGAAAAATA	600
PAS10_NSP3	GCGCTATGAGCAATTGGAGCAAAGGTTTGAATCATTGAAATCCAGGGTAAATGAAAAATA	600
PAS8_NSP3	GCGCTATGAGCAATTGGAGCAAAGGTTTGAATCATTGAAATCCAGGGTAAATGAAAAATA	600
PAS6_NSP3	GCGCTATGAGCAATTGGAGCAAAGGTTTGAATCATTGAAATCCAGGGTAAATGAAAAATA	600
PAS2_NSP3	GCGCTATGAGCAATTGGAGCAAAGGTTTGAATCATTGAAATCCAGGGTAAATGAAAAATA	600
NSP3-SA11	TAATAATTGGGTGTTGAAAGCAAGAAAAATGAATGAAAAATATGCATTCTCTTCAAAATGT	660
PAS10_NSP3	TAATAATTGGGTGTTGAAAGCAAGAAAAATGAATGAAAAATATGCATTCTCTTCAAAATGT	660
PAS8_NSP3	TAATAATTGGGTGTTGAAAGCAAGAAAAATGAATGAAAAATATGCATTCTCTTCAAAATGT	660
PAS6_NSP3	TAATAATTGGGTGTTGAAAGCAAGAAAAATGAATGAAAAATATGCATTCTCTTCAAAATGT	660
PAS2_NSP3	TAATAATTGGGTGTTGAAAGCAAGAAAAATGAATGAAAAATATGCATTCTCTTCAAAATGT	660
NSP3-SA11	CATCTCTCAACAGCAAGCACATATAGCTGAGCTTCAAGTGTACAATAATAAAGTAGAACG	720
PAS10_NSP3	CATCTCTCAACAGCAAGCACATATAGCTGAGCTTCAAGTGTACAATAATAAAGTAGAACG	720

PAS8_NSP3	CATCTCTCAACAGCAAGCACATATAGCTGAGCTTCAAGTGTACAATAATAAAC TAGAACG	720
PAS6_NSP3	CATCTCTCAACAGCAAGCACATATAGCTGAGCTTCAAGTGTACAATAATAAAC TAGAACG	720
PAS2_NSP3	CATCTCTCAACAGCAAGCACATATAGCTGAGCTTCAAGTGTACAATAATAAAC TAGAACG	720
NSP3-SA11	TGATTTGCAAAAATAAAATTGGATCCCTTACTTCTTCGATTGAATGGTATTTAAGATCAAT	780
PAS10_NSP3	TGATTTGCAAAAATAAAATTGGATCCCTTACTTCTTCGATTGAATGGTATTTAAGATCAAT	780
PAS8_NSP3	TGATTTGCAAAAATAAAATTGGATCCCTTACTTCTTCGATTGAATGGTATTTAAGATCAAT	780
PAS6_NSP3	TGATTTGCAAAAATAAAATTGGATCCCTTACTTCTTCGATTGAATGGTATTTAAGATCAAT	780
PAS2_NSP3	TGATTTGCAAAAATAAAATTGGATCCCTTACTTCTTCGATTGAATGGTATTTAAGATCAAT	780
NSP3-SA11	GGAATTAGACCTGAAATAAAGGCAGACATTGAACAGCAAATTAACTCAATTGATGCGAT	840
PAS10_NSP3	GGAATTAGACCTGAAATAAAGGCAGACATTGAACAGCAAATTAACTCAATTGATGCGAT	840
PAS8_NSP3	GGAATTAGACCTGAAATAAAGGCAGACATTGAACAGCAAATTAACTCAATTGATGCGAT	840
PAS6_NSP3	GGAATTAGACCTGAAATAAAGGCAGACATTGAACAGCAAATTAACTCAATTGATGCGAT	840
PAS2_NSP3	GGAATTAGACCTGAAATAAAGGCAGACATTGAACAGCAAATTAACTCAATTGATGCGAT	840
NSP3-SA11	AAATCCATTGCACGCTTTTGTAGACTTAGAATCAGTAATACGTAATTTGATATCTGATTA	900
PAS10_NSP3	AAATCCATTGCACGCTTTTGTAGACTTAGAATCAGTAATACGTAATTTGATATCTGATTA	900
PAS8_NSP3	AAATCCATTGCACGCTTTTGTAGACTTAGAATCAGTAATACGTAATTTGATATCTGATTA	900
PAS6_NSP3	AAATCCATTGCACGCTTTTGTAGACTTAGAATCAGTAATACGTAATTTGATATCTGATTA	900
PAS2_NSP3	AAATCCATTGCACGCTTTTGTAGACTTAGAATCAGTAATACGTAATTTGATATCTGATTA	900
NSP3-SA11	TGACAAATTATTCCTTATGTTCAAAGGATTAATACAGAGATGTAATTATCAATATTCATT	960
PAS10_NSP3	TGACAAATTATTCCTTATGTTCAAAGGATKAMTRCAGAGATGTAATTATCAATATTCATT	960
PAS8_NSP3	TGACAAATTATTCCTTATGTTCAAAGGATKAMTRCAGAGATGTAATTATCAATATTCATT	960
PAS6_NSP3	TGACAAATTATTCCTTATGTTCAAAGGATKAMTRCAGAGATGTAATTATCAATATTCATT	960
PAS2_NSP3	TGACAAATTATTCCTTATGTTCAAAGGATKAMTRCAGAGATGTAATTATCAATATTCATT	960
NSP3-SA11	TGGTTGCGAATAACCATTTTGATACATGTTGAACAATCAAATACAGTGTAGTATGTTGT	1020
PAS10_NSP3	TGGTTGCGAATAACCATTTTGATACATGTTGAACAATCAAATACAGTGTAGTATGTTGT	1020
PAS8_NSP3	TGGTTGCGAATAACCATTTTGATACATGTTGAACAATCAAATACAGTGTAGTATGTTGT	1020
PAS6_NSP3	TGGTTGCGAATAACCATTTTGATACATGTTGAACAATCAAATACAGTGTAGTATGTTGT	1020
PAS2_NSP3	TGGTTGCGAATAACCATTTTGATACATGTTGAACAATCAAATACAGTGTAGTATGTTGT	1020
NSP3-SA11	CATCTATGCATAACCCCTCTATGAGCACAATAGTTAAAAGCTAACACTGTCAAAAACCTAA	1080
PAS10_NSP3	CATCTATGCATAACCCCTCTATGAGCACAATAGTTAAAAGCTAACACTGTCAAAAACCTAR	1080
PAS8_NSP3	CATCTATGCATAACCCCTCTATGAGCACAATAGTTAAAAGCTAACACTGTCAAAAACCTAR	1080
PAS6_NSP3	CATCTATGCATAACCCCTCTATGAGCACAATAGTTAAAAGCTAACACTGTCAAAAACCTAR	1080
PAS2_NSP3	CATCTATGCATAACCCCTCTATGAGCACAATAGTTAAAAGCTAACACTGTCAAAAACCTAA	1080
NSP3-SA11	ATGGCTATAGGGGCGTTATGTGGCC	1105
PAS10_NSP3	ATGGCTATAGGGGCGTTATGTGGCC	1105
PAS8_NSP3	ATGGCTATAGGGGCGTTATGTGGCC	1105
PAS6_NSP3	ATGGCTATAGGGGCGTTATGTGGCC	1105
PAS2_NSP3	ATGGCTATAGGGGCNNNNNNNNNNNN	1105

GENOME SEGMENT 10:

NSP4-SA11	GGCTTTTAAAAGTTCTGTTCCGAGAGAGCGCGTGC GGAAAGATGGAAAAGCTTACCGACC	58
PAS10_NSP4	GGCTTTTAAAAGTTCTGTTCCGAGAGAGCGCGTGC GGAAAGATGGAAAAGCTTACCGACC	60
PAS6_NSP4	GGCTTTTAAAAGTTCTGTTCCGAGAGAGCGCGTGC GGAAAGATGGAAAAGCTTACCGACC	60
PAS8_NSP4	GGCTTTTAAAAGTTCTGTTCCGAGAGAGCGCGTGC GGAAAGATGGAAAAGCTTACCGACC	60
PAS2_NSP4	NNNNNNNNNNNGTTCTGTTCCGAGAGAGCGCGTGC GGAAAGATGGAAAAGCTTACCGACC	60
NSP4-SA11	TCAATTATACATTGAGTGTAACTACTCTAATGAACAATACATTGCACACAATACTTGAGG	118
PAS10_NSP4	TCAATTATACATTGAGTGTAACTACTCTAATGAACAATACATTGCACACAATACTTGAGG	120
PAS6_NSP4	TCAATTATACATTGAGTGTAACTACTCTAATGAACAATACATTGCACACAATACTTGAGG	120
PAS8_NSP4	TCAATTATACATTGAGTGTAACTACTCTAATGAACAATACATTGCACACAATACTTGAGG	120
PAS2_NSP4	TCAATTATACATTGAGTGTAACTACTCTAATGAACAATACATTGCACACAATACTTGAGG	120
NSP4-SA11	ATCCAGGAATGGCGTATTTTCCCTTATATAGCATCTGTCTTAACAGTTTTGTTTGCCTAC	178
PAS10_NSP4	ATCCAGGAATGGCGTATTTTCCCTTATATAGCATCTGTCTTAACAGTTTTGTTTGCCTAC	180
PAS6_NSP4	ATCCAGGAATGGCGTATTTTCCCTTATATAGCATCTGTCTTAACAGTTTTGTTTGCCTAC	180
PAS8_NSP4	ATCCAGGAATGGCGTATTTTCCCTTATATAGCATCTGTCTTAACAGTTTTGTTTGCCTAC	180
PAS2_NSP4	ATCCAGGAATGGCGTATTTTCCCTTATATAGCATCTGTCTTAACAGTTTTGTTTGCCTAC	180
NSP4-SA11	ATAAAGCATCCATCCAACAATGAAAATTGCATTGAAAACGTCAAATGTTTCATATAAAG	238
PAS10_NSP4	ATAAAGCATCCATCCAACAATGAAAATTGCATTGAAAACGTCAAATGTTTCATATAAAG	240
PAS6_NSP4	ATAAAGCATCCATCCAACAATGAAAATTGCATTGAAAACGTCAAATGTTTCATATAAAG	240

PAS8_NSP4	ATAAAGCATCCATCCAACAATGAAAATTGCATTGAAAACGTCAAATGTTTCATATAAAG	240
PAS2_NSP4	ATAAAGCATCCATCCAACAATGAAAATTGCATTGAAAACGTCAAATGTTTCATATAAAG	240
NSP4-SA11	TGGTGAAATATTGTATTGTAACAATTTTTAATACGTTGTTAAAAATTGGCAGGTTATAAAG	298
PAS10_NSP4	TGGTGAAATATTGTATTGTAACAATTTTTAATACGTTGTTAAAAATTGGCAGGTTATAAAG	300
PAS6_NSP4	TGGTGAAATATTGTATTGTAACAATTTTTAATACGTTGTTAAAAATTGGCAGGTTATAAAG	300
PAS8_NSP4	TGGTGAAATATTGTATTGTAACAATTTTTAATACGTTGTTAAAAATTGGCAGGTTATAAAG	300
PAS2_NSP4	TGGTGAAATATTGTATTGTAACAATTTTTAATACGTTGTTAAAAATTGGCAGGTTATAAAG	300
NSP4-SA11	AGCAGATAACTACTAAAGATGAGATAGAAAAGCAAATGGACAGAGTAGTCAAAGAAATGA	358
PAS10_NSP4	AGCAGATAACTACTAAAGATGAGATAGAAAAGCAAATGGACAGAGTAGTCAAAGAAATGA	360
PAS6_NSP4	AGCAGATAACTACTAAAGATGAGATAGAAAAGCAAATGGACAGAGTAGTCAAAGAAATGA	360
PAS8_NSP4	AGCAGATAACTACTAAAGATGAGATAGAAAAGCAAATGGACAGAGTAGTCAAAGAAATGA	360
PAS2_NSP4	AGCAGATAACTACTAAAGATGAGATAGAAAAGCAAATGGACAGAGTAGTCAAAGAAATGA	360
NSP4-SA11	GACGCCAGCTAGAAAATGATTGACAAAATTGACTACACGTGAAATTGAACAAGTAGAGTTGC	418
PAS10_NSP4	GACGCCAGCTAGAAAATGATTGACAAAATTGACTACACGTGAAATTGAACAAGTAGAGTTGC	420
PAS6_NSP4	GACGCCAGCTAGAAAATGATTGACAAAATTGACTACACGTGAAATTGAACAAGTAGAGTTGC	420
PAS8_NSP4	GACGCCAGCTAGAAAATGATTGACAAAATTGACTACACGTGAAATTGAACAAGTAGAGTTGC	420
PAS2_NSP4	GACGCCAGCTAGAAAATGATTGACAAAATTGACTACACGTGAAATTGAACAAGTAGAGTTGC	420
NSP4-SA11	TTAAACGCATTTACGATAAAATTGACGGTGCAAACGACAGGTGAAATAGATATGACAAAAG	478
PAS10_NSP4	TTAAACGCATTTACGATAAAATTGACGGTGCAAACGACAGGTGAAATAGATATGACAAAAG	480
PAS6_NSP4	TTAAACGCATTTACGATAAAATTGACGGTGCAAACGACAGGTGAAATAGATATGACAAAAG	480
PAS8_NSP4	TTAAACGCATTTACGATAAAATTGACGGTGCAAACGACAGGTGAAATAGATATGACAAAAG	480
PAS2_NSP4	TTAAACGCATTTACGATAAAATTGACGGTGCAAACGACAGGTGAAATAGATATGACAAAAG	480
NSP4-SA11	AGATCAATCAAAAAACGTTGAGAACGCTAGAAGAAATGGGAAAGTGGAAAAATCCTTATG	538
PAS10_NSP4	AGATCAATCAAAAAACGTTGAGAACGCTAGAAGAAATGGGAAAGTGGAAAAATCCTTATG	540
PAS6_NSP4	AGATCAATCAAAAAACGTTGAGAACGCTAGAAGAAATGGGAAAGTGGAAAAATCCTTATG	540
PAS8_NSP4	AGATCAATCAAAAAACGTTGAGAACGCTAGAAGAAATGGGAAAGTGGAAAAATCCTTATG	540
PAS2_NSP4	AGATCAATCAAAAAACGTTGAGAACGCTAGAAGAAATGGGAAAGTGGAAAAATCCTTATG	540
NSP4-SA11	AACCAAGAGAAGTGACTGCAGCAATGTAAGAGGTTGAGCTGCCGTCGACTGTCCTCGGAA	598
PAS10_NSP4	AACCAAGAGAAGTGACTGCAGCAATGTAAGAGGTTGAGCTGCCGTCGACTGTCCTCGGAA	600
PAS6_NSP4	AACCAAGAGAAGTGACTGCAGCAATGTAAGAGGTTGAGCTGCCGTCGACTGTCCTCGGAA	600
PAS8_NSP4	AACCAAGAGARRTGACTGCAGCAATGTAAGAGGTTGAGCTGCCGTCGACTGTCCTCGGAA	600
PAS2_NSP4	AACCAARAGARRTGACTGCAGCAATGTAAGAGGTTGAGCTGCCGTCGACTGTCCTCGGAA	600
NSP4-SA11	GCGGCGGAGTTCCTTACAGTAAGCACCATCGGACCTGATGGCTGACTGAGAAGCCACAGT	658
PAS10_NSP4	GCGGCGGAGTTCCTTACAGTAAGCACCATCGGACCTGATGGCTGACTGAGAAGCCACAGT	660
PAS6_NSP4	GCGGCGGAGTTCCTTACAGTAAGCACCATCGGACCTGATGGCTGACTGAGAAGCCACAGT	660
PAS8_NSP4	GCGGCGGAGTTCCTTACAGTAAGCACCATCGGACCTGATGGCTGACTGAGAAGCCACAGT	660
PAS2_NSP4	GCGGCGGAGTTCCTTACAGTAAGCACCATCGGACCTGATGGCTGACTGAGAAGCCACAGT	660
NSP4-SA11	CAGCCATATCGCGTGTGGCTCAAGCCTTAATCCCGTTTAACCAATCCGGTCAGCACCGGA	718
PAS10_NSP4	CAGCCATATCGCGTGTGGCTCAAGCCTTAATCCCGTTTAACCAATCCGGTCAGCACCGGA	720
PAS6_NSP4	CAGCCATATCGCGTGTGGCTCAAGCCTTAATCCCGTTTAACCAATCCGGTCAGCACCGGA	720
PAS8_NSP4	CAGCCATATCGCGTGTGGCTCAAGCCTTAATCCCGTTTAACCAATCCGGTCAGCACCGGA	720
PAS2_NSP4	CAGCCATATCGCGTGTGGCTCAAGCCTTAATCCCGTTTAACCAATCCGGTCAGCACCGGA	720
NSP4-SA11	CGTTAATGGAAGGAACGGTCTTAATGTGACC	749
PAS10_NSP4	CGTTAATGGAAGGAACGGTCTTAATGTGACC	751
PAS6_NSP4	CGTTAATGGAAGGAACGGTCTTAATGTGACC	751
PAS8_NSP4	CGTTAATGGAAGGAACGGTCTTAATGTGACC	751
PAS2_NSP4	CGTTAATGGAAGGAACGNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN	751

GENOME SEGMENT 11:

NSP5-SA11	GGCTTTTAAAGCGCTACAGTGATGCTCTCAGTATGACGTGACGAGTCTTCCTTCTATT	60
PAS10_NSP5	GGCTTTTAAAGCKTRCAGTSATGCTCTCAGTATGACGTGACGAGTCTTCCTTCTATT	60
PAS8_NSP5	GGCTTTTAAAGCKTRCAGTSATGCTCTCAGTATGACGTGACGAGTCTTCCTTCTATT	60
PAS6_NSP5	GGCTTTTAAAGCKTRCAGTSATGCTCTCAGTATGACGTGACGAGTCTTCCTTCTATT	60
PAS2_NSP5	NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNTGCTCTCAGTATGACGTGACGAGTCTTCCTTCTATT	60
NSP5-SA11	CCTTCAACTATATATAAGAATGAATCGTCTTCAACAACGTCAACTCTTTCTGGAAAAATCT	120
PAS10_NSP5	CCTTCAACTATATATAAGAATGAATCGTCTTCAACAACGTCAACTCTTTCTGGAAAAATCT	120
PAS8_NSP5	CCTTCAACTATATATAAGAATGAATCGTCTTCAACAACGTCAACTCTTTCTGGAAAAATCT	120
PAS6_NSP5	CCTTCAACTATATATAAGAATGAATCGTCTTCAACAACGTCAACTCTTTCTGGAAAAATCT	120

PAS2_NSP5	CCTTCAACTATATATAAGAATGAATCGTCTTCAACAACGTCAACTCTTTCTGGAAAATCT	120
NSP5-SA11	ATTGGTAGGAGTGAACAGTACATTTACCAGATGCAGAAGCATTCATAAATACATGCTG	180
PAS10_NSP5	ATTGGTAGGAGTGAACAGTACATTTACCAGATGCAGAAGCATTCATAAATACATGCTG	180
PAS8_NSP5	ATTGGTAGGAGTGAACAGTACATTTACCAGATGCAGAAGCATTCATAAATACATGCTG	180
PAS6_NSP5	ATTGGTAGGAGTGAACAGTACATTTACCAGATGCAGAAGCATTCATAAATACATGCTG	180
PAS2_NSP5	ATTGGTAGGAGTGAACAGTACATTTACCAGATGCAGAAGCATTCATAAATACATGCTG	180
NSP5-SA11	TCGAAGTCTCCAGAGGATATTGGACCATCTGATTCGCTTCAAACGATCCACTCACCAGT	240
PAS10_NSP5	TCGAAGTCTCCAGAGGATATTGGACCATCTGATTCGCTTCAAACGATCCACTCACCAGT	240
PAS8_NSP5	TCGAAGTCTCCAGAGGATATTGGACCATCTGATTCGCTTCAAACGATCCACTCACCAGT	240
PAS6_NSP5	TCGAAGTCTCCAGAGGATATTGGACCATCTGATTCGCTTCAAACGATCCACTCACCAGT	240
PAS2_NSP5	TCGAAGTCTCCAGAGGATATTGGACCATCTGATTCGCTTCAAACGATCCACTCACCAGT	240
NSP5-SA11	TTTTCGATTAGATCGAATGCAGTTAAGACAAACGCAGACGCTGGCGTGTCTATGGATTCA	300
PAS10_NSP5	TTTTCGATTAGATCGAATGCAGTTAAGACAAACGCAGACGCTGGCGTGTCTATGGATTCA	300
PAS8_NSP5	TTTTCGATTAGATCGAATGCAGTTAAGACAAACGCAGACGCTGGCGTGTCTATGGATTCA	300
PAS6_NSP5	TTTTCGATTAGATCGAATGCAGTTAAGACAAACGCAGACGCTGGCGTGTCTATGGATTCA	300
PAS2_NSP5	TTTTCGATTAGATCGAATGCAGTTAAGACAAACGCAGACGCTGGCGTGTCTATGGATTCA	300
NSP5-SA11	TCAGCACAATCACGACCTTCAAGTAATGTCCGATGCGATCAAGTGGATTTCTCCTTAAAT	360
PAS10_NSP5	TCAGCACAATCACGACCTTCAAGTAATGTCCGATGCGATCAAGTGGATTTCTCCTTAAAT	360
PAS8_NSP5	TCAGCACAATCACGACCTTCAAGTAATGTCCGATGCGATCAAGTGGATTTCTCCTTAAAT	360
PAS6_NSP5	TCAGCACAATCACGACCTTCAAGTAATGTCCGATGCGATCAAGTGGATTTCTCCTTAAAT	360
PAS2_NSP5	TCAGCACAATCACGACCTTCAAGTAATGTCCGATGCGATCAAGTGGATTTCTCCTTAAAT	360
NSP5-SA11	AAAGGCTTAAAAGTAAAAGCTAATTTGGACTCATCAATATCAATATCTACGGATACTAAA	420
PAS10_NSP5	AAAGGCTTAAAAGTAAAAGCTAATTTGGACTCATCAATATCAATATCTACGGATACTAAA	420
PAS8_NSP5	AAAGGCTTAAAAGTAAAAGCTAATTTGGACTCATCAATATCAATATCTACGGATACTAAA	420
PAS6_NSP5	AAAGGCTTAAAAGTAAAAGCTAATTTGGACTCATCAATATCAATATCTACGGATACTAAA	420
PAS2_NSP5	AAAGGCTTAAAAGTAAAAGCTAATTTGGACTCATCAATATCAATATCTACGGATACTAAA	420
NSP5-SA11	AAGGAGAAATCAAAACAAAACCATAAAAAGTAGGAAGCACTACCCAAGAATTGAAGCAGAG	480
PAS10_NSP5	AAGGAGAAATCAAAACAAAACCATAAAAAGTAGGAAGCACTACCCAAGAATTGAAGCAGAG	480
PAS8_NSP5	AAGGAGAAATCAAAACAAAACCATAAAAAGTAGGAAGCACTACCCAAGAATTGAAGCAGAG	480
PAS6_NSP5	AAGGAGAAATCAAAACAAAACCATAAAAAGTAGGAAGCACTACCCAAGAATTGAAGCAGAG	480
PAS2_NSP5	AAGGAGAAATCAAAACAAAACCATAAAAAGTAGGAAGCACTACCCAAGAATTGAAGCAGAG	480
NSP5-SA11	TCTGATTAGATGATTATGTACTGGATGATTAGATAGTATGATGATGGTAAATGTAAGAAC	540
PAS10_NSP5	TCTGATTAGATGATTATGTACTGGATGATTAGATAGTATGATGATGGTAAATGTAAGAAC	540
PAS8_NSP5	TCTGATTAGATGATTATGTACTGGATGATTAGATAGTATGATGATGGTAAATGTAAGAAC	540
PAS6_NSP5	TCTGATTAGATGATTATGTACTGGATGATTAGATAGTATGATGATGGTAAATGTAAGAAC	540
PAS2_NSP5	TCTGATTAGATGATTATGTACTGGATGATTAGATAGTATGATGATGGTAAATGTAAGAAC	540
NSP5-SA11	TGTAATATAAGAAGAAATACTTCGCATTAAGAATGAGAATGAAACAAGTCGCAATGCAA	600
PAS10_NSP5	TGTAATATAAGAAGAAATACTTCGCATTAAGAATGAGAATGAAACAAGTCGCAATGCAA	600
PAS8_NSP5	TGTAATATAAGAAGAAATACTTCGCATTAAGAATGAGAATGAAACAAGTCGCAATGCAA	600
PAS6_NSP5	TGTAATATAAGAAGAAATACTTCGCATTAAGAATGAGAATGAAACAAGTCGCAATGCAA	600
PAS2_NSP5	TGTAATATAAGAAGAAATACTTCGCATTAAGAATGAGAATGAAACAAGTCGCAATGCAA	600
NSP5-SA11	TTGATTGAAGATTTGTAAGTCTGACCTGGGAACACACTAGGGAGCTCCCCACTCCCGTTT	660
PAS10_NSP5	TTGATTGAAGATTTGTAAGTCTGACCTGGGAACACACTAGGGAGCTCCCCACTCCCGTTT	660
PAS8_NSP5	TTGATTGAAGATTTGTAAGTCTGACCTGGGAACACACTAGGGAGCTCCCCACTCCCGTTT	660
PAS6_NSP5	TTGATTGAAGATTTGTAAGTCTGACCTGGGAACACACTAGGGAGCTCCCCACTCCCGTTT	660
PAS2_NSP5	TTGATTGAAGATTTGTAAGTCTGACCTGGGAACACACTAGGGAGCTCCCCACCCCGNNN	660
NSP5-SA11	TGTGACC	667
PAS10_NSP5	TGTGACC	667
PAS8_NSP5	TGTGACC	667
PAS6_NSP5	TGTGACC	667
PAS2_NSP5	NNNNNNN	667

Supplemental materials and methods

rRV/VP4-BAP passages in cell culture. One ml of infected cell lysate was activated with 80 µg/ml trypsin for 30 min at 37°C. Then, the virus was diluted to 3 ml of serum-free DMEM and added to a confluent monolayer of MA104 in a T75 cell culture flask. The virus was allowed to be adsorbed for 1 h at 37°C before adding 7 ml of serum-free DMEM supplemented with trypsin to a final concentration of 80 µg/ml. The cells were incubated until complete cytopathic effect was reached. Next, the cells and medium were harvested, followed by three cycles of liquid nitrogen freeze and thawing at 37°C in a water bath. The sample was spun-down at 3500 rpm for 10 min at 4°C and the supernatant was recovered. These steps were repeated until virus passage ten was reached. Then, 5×10^5 MA104 cells were infected with 200 µl of each virus passage. At 6 hpi, cells were harvested with trypsin-EDTA and centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 2 min. The cell pellet was resuspended in 400µl TRI Reagent® solution (Invitrogen), and RNA was purified using a quick RNA miniprep Plus kit (Zymo Research) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The cDNA was then synthesized using random primers and an AMV reverse transcription system (Promega). Finally, 2 µl of cDNA was amplified using specific primers to detect gs4-BAP (forward: 5'-cattctgatcgagcccaac-3' and reverse: 5'-cgttgttgaataatgtcctgtc-3') using Phusion® high-fidelity DNA polymerase (New England Biolabs). Each PCR reaction was loaded in an 0.8% agarose gel; the specific band was purified using QIAquick gel extraction kit (Qiagen), and Sanger sequenced using above-forward primers. Sequences were analyzed using SnapGene® version 6.0.2.

Deep sequencing of RV genome segments. DNA was obtained from clarified supernatant of different passages of rRV/VP4-BAP infected MA104 cells prepared as

described previously by Kubacki *et al.* 2021(1). The samples were then sequenced using an Agilent 2200 TapeStation (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, California, USA) with a D1000 HS ScreenTape (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, California, USA) to measure the size distribution and molarity of each sample. Sample denaturation, dilution, and sequencing were performed at the Functional Genomics Center Zurich on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 system using a paired-end NGS run and 2 x 150 nucleotide according to the manufacturer protocols (Illumina, San Diego, California, USA). A PhiX Control v3 Library was used as run quality control according to the manual (Illumina, San Diego, California, USA). The data were analysed by trimming the PCR primers, sequencing adaptors, and low-quality ends in raw reads using Trimmomatic (version 0.36) and cutadapt (version 2.9). Quality controlled reads were aligned to the simian rotavirus SA11 genome segments used for reverse genetics (2) and pT₇-V4-BAP (this study) in the metagenomic/population assembly pipeline of the SeqMan NGen v17.3 (DNASTar, Lasergene, Madison, Wisconsin, USA). Each segment of the viral genome was built using the contig sequences.

Modelling of VP4 with and without BAP tag. Rosetta-commons comparative modelling algorithm with multi-templates approach was used to generate full VP4 protein structure, as there was no captured crystal structure for the full protein of simian rotavirus A strain SA11. The crystal structures used in the modelling approach to predict the 3D confirmation of the full SA11-VP4 were 4V7Q (3IYU obsolete ID), IKQR 1SLQ, 6WXF, 2P3J and 4YG3. These crystal structures are either protein complex captured including VP4 protein or captured VP8* subunit of VP4. The structural modelling was performed using a molecular dynamics approach with

MDAnalysis python library associated to gromax and amber Tools to evaluate to the captured crystal structures.

Supplementary references.

1. Kubacki J, Fraefel C, Bachofen C. 2021. Implementation of next-generation sequencing for virus identification in veterinary diagnostic laboratories. *J Vet Diagn Invest* 33:235-247.
2. Kanai Y, Komoto S, Kawagishi T, Nouda R, Nagasawa N, Onishi M, Matsuura Y, Taniguchi K, Kobayashi T. 2017. Entirely plasmid-based reverse genetics system for rotaviruses. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 114:2349-2354.